

MES-CoBraD

Multidisciplinary Expert System
for the Assessment & Management
of Complex Brain Disorders

D6.2

MES-CoBraD Advanced Analytics
Release 1.00

October 2022

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PREFACE

The Multidisciplinary Expert System for the Assessment & Management of Complex Brain Disorders (MES-CoBraD) is an interdisciplinary project combining Real-World Data (RWD) from multiple clinical and consumer sources through comprehensive, cost-efficient, and fast protocols towards improving diagnostic accuracy and therapeutic outcomes in people with Complex Brain Disorders (CoBraD), as reflected in Neurocognitive (Dementia), Sleep, and Seizure (Epilepsy) disorders and their interdependence.

- 1 It brings together internationally recognized experts in medicine, engineering, computer science, social health science, law, and marketing and communication from across Europe, and combines clinical information and scientific research in CoBraD with technical innovation in secure data-sharing platforms, artificial intelligence algorithms, and expert systems of precision and personalized care, with a primary focus on improving the quality of life of patients, their caregivers, and the society at large.
- 2 It leverages RWD from diverse CoBraD populations across cultural, socioeconomic, educational, and health system backgrounds, with special attention on including vulnerable populations and minorities in an equitable manner and engaging key stakeholders to maximize project impact.
- 3 The project will deliver a rigorous and self-standing methodology that will drive the MES-CoBraD implementation and define its operational principles; The MES-CoBraD solution, through the implementation of novel, self-standing AI based components and their integration under a common platform for scientific exploitation will assist focusing on the evaluation and validation of the solution, the spread of the excellence gained, the expansion of its ecosystem and the real-life sustainability.

CONSORTIUM

NTUA	National Technical University of Athens	EL
NIA	Neurological Institute of Athens	EL
HSCSP	Fundació privada Institut de Recerca de l'Hospital de la Santa Creu i Sant Pau	IR
VUB - LSTS	VRIJE UNIVERSITEIT BRUSSEL	BE
UU	UPPSALA UNIVERSITY	SE
CHS-RMC	Clalit Health Services- Rabin Medical Center Cognitive Neurology and Epilepsy Clinics	IL
KCL	King's College London	UK
HOLISTIC	HOLISTIC P.C.	EL
SIMAVI	Software Imagination & Vision	RO
LIBER	STICHTING LIBER	NL
ENG	Engineering - Ingegneria Informatica S.p.A.	EN
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MULTIDISCIPLINARY EXPERT SYSTEM FOR THE ASSESSMENT & MANAGEMENT OF COMPLEX BRAIN DISORDERS

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation / Acronym	Description
Dx.y	Deliverable number y belonging to WP x
Tx.y	Task number y belonging to WP x
GA	General Assembly
ToC	Table of Contents
WP	Work Package
MES-CoBraD	Multidisciplinary Expert System for the Assessment & Management of Complex Brain Disorders
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network
API	Application Programming Interface
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
CPU	Central Processing Unit
TPU	Tensor Processing Unit
PCA	Principal Component Analysis
CSF	Critical Success Factors
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ML	Machine Learning
TAI	Trustworthy AI
XAI	Explainable AI
GUI	Graphical User Interface
ES	Expert System
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier
ES	Expert System

Executive Summary

Expert Systems (ES) can provide an alternative methodology in analysing data to identify variables with the highest correlation to the outcome using the most appropriate data analysis and algorithms. By applying their effective machine learning (ML) abilities, significant research time and costs can be saved. The study aims to systematically review the applications of ES in neurological research and their methodological models for effective multi-variate analysis. Their domains, development and validity will be identified on WP6.

The scope of the ES is to:

- › Implement general problem-solving AI techniques and explicitly modelled hypotheticodeductive behaviour.
- › Maintain and update a central knowledge base, filtered by a fact checking database and an inference engine.
- › Handle the knowledge base acquired from WP4 and WP8, but also from the scientific community through regular integrations.
- › Provide symbolic rather than numeric representations of pertinent knowledge from domain of application.
- › Provide categoric schemes for dealing with domain uncertainty.

The ES is tested for accuracy, feasibility, and acceptability in real-world practice. Artificial Intelligence (AI) knowledge-based system for data analysis and interpretation includes an algorithm and software to emulate human cognitive functions in the analysis, interpretation, and comprehension of heterogenous data. Data analytics according to the definitions of previous WPs and especially WP4 include visualisation, query definition and multi-purpose analytics. Interactive and intuitive visualisations (dashboards) assist clinicians to develop actionable insights about patients' health condition and take the necessary corrective actions. The objective of the development of AI modules is:

- › To be updatable based on acquired RWD.
- › Improve data processing.
- › Advance development of knowledge databases.
- › Mimic human cognitive decision processes.
- › Rely on supervised and unsupervised deep learning and machine learning techniques.

The present deliverable provides the basic structure of the algorithm that includes all variables that have been identified and result in the creation of the basic structure that hosts the data analysis. The system can receive a variety of variables analysed through AI algorithm and provide the end users with the appropriate results.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 STRUCTURE OF THE DELIVERABLE

The deliverable is structured based on the content and its scope in the following sections:

- › **The Introduction:** defining the purpose, objectives, and relations with other WPs
- › **The Landscape Analysis:** including Evidence-Based Medicine, Hypothesis Testing in Medicine, Process Modelling and Management, Data Analytics and Processing and Artificial Intelligence
- › **State-Of-The-Art Analysis:** Expert System - Process Modelling and Management – Comparative Analysis, Data Analytics and Visualisations – Comparative Analysis, Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning – Comparative Analysis
- › **Requirements' Elaboration:** Expert System - Process Modelling and Management, Query Builder, Data Analytics, Hypothesis Testing Interface, Data and Results Visualisation, Artificial Intelligence, Integration
- › **Advanced Analytics Architecture:** Overall Architecture, Components
- › **Advanced Analytics Mockups:** User Interface, Expert System - Process Modelling and Management, Query Builder, Data Analytics, Hypothesis Testing Interface, Data, and Results Visualisation
- › **APIs' Specification:** Query Builder and MES-CoBraD Data Lake, Expert System - Process Modelling and Management, Data Analytics, Data and Results Visualisation, Artificial Intelligence
- › **Implementation:** Overview, Expert System - Process Modelling and Management, Query Builder, Data Analytics, Hypothesis Testing Interface, Data and Results Visualisation, Artificial Intelligence, User Interface
- › **Integration:** Integration between components, Integration with the MES-CoBraD Platform
- › **Testing:** Expert System - Process Modelling and Management, Query Builder, Data Analytics, Hypothesis Testing Interface, Data and Results Visualisation, Artificial Intelligence, Integration Testing
- › **Conclusions and Next Steps**
- › **References**

Figure 1 – Structure of the deliverable

1.2 RELATION TO OTHER DELIVERABLES/WPS/TASKS

The Expert System (ES) developed and validated, that is also used in WP4, relies on artificial intelligence algorithms that will guide decision making. The ES works as knowledge acquisition, model-based reasoning and system integration that gives decision support on diagnosis, prognosis, and therapy. Decision support will rely on RWD acquired through WP8 that leads to a flexible, hierarchical, and modular decision tree algorithm. This module is designed on a programmer-friendly Application Programming Interface (API) provided by WP7. The interactions of WP6 with other tasks and WPs is provided in the following figure.

Figure 2 – Relation of WP6 with other WPs and Tasks

2 LANDSCAPE ANALYSIS

Landscape analysis provides an overview of the clinical decision-making process of evidence-based medicine with reference to the historical background, the methodological process, observation studies and advantages and limitations. Moreover, hypothesis testing is stated, indicating the significance and statistical analysis of the procedure. A state of the art of process modelling and management is reported with reference to healthcare systems, clinicians, and medical research. Data analytics and processing is provided including analysis of structured, inhomogeneous, and multimodal data, feature selection, diagnosis, Classification and visualisation and statistical overview. Updates would be based in acquired and reviewed RWD through the AI platform Artificial Intelligence and its role and benefits in medical systems in analysed with reference to explainable and trustworthy AI.

2.1 EVIDENCE-BASED MEDICINE

2.1.1 DEFINITION OF EVIDENCE-BASED MEDICINE

Evidence-based medicine, in healthcare, refers to the clinical decision-making process, which incorporates the latest and most accurate scientific evidence with the clinical experience and the patients' values, in a prudent and sensible manner[1][2]. The first key element of evidence-based medicine is scientific evidence, which should rely on current and precise scientific developments and can appropriately be integrated into the clinical practice. The procedure of finding out this evidence encompasses both the fundamental scientific research and the clinical studies on the effectiveness and safety of diagnostic, prognostic, and treatment methods and protocols. Clinical studies may be randomised clinical trials, observational studies if randomised trials are not accessible, or clinical observations and assessments, in case none of the previous studies can be obtained. Clinical experience, which is the next essential component, represents clinicians' knowledge, skills, and efficiency in medical problem solving, acquired during clinical practice. The last evidence-based medicine's critical element highlights the procedure of harmonising the patients' values, beliefs, desires, priorities, fears, concerns, and socioeconomic situation with the healthcare process. There is a continuous interaction of the above-described elements in evidence-based medicine[1].

Evidence-based medicine can be described as a method of identifying, evaluating, and applying accurate research outcomes in clinical procedure. To reach the point of application of scientific evidence, a long, systematic, and critical study of research advancements should precede. The core decision that evidence-based medicine must obtain is whether there is adequate evidence that specific diagnostic, prognostic, and treatment methods may be beneficial or not. Its main purpose is to support clinical decision-making operations by enhancing the use of significant, unbiased medical research developments. It is a patient-oriented process, which relies on the outlook that patients' care necessitates a systematic and lifelong education on clinical advancements[1][3].

Since evidence-based medicine is established on the integration of all these three elements: scientific evidence, clinical expertise, and patients' aspirations, none of them is treated as a priority. External scientific evidence works in a supportive way and feeds clinical practice with knowledge but can never substitute her. Clinical experience is also responsible for answering the critical question of whether specific evidence is indeed applicable to the treatment of the individual patient, but also to indicate the most appropriate way in which it will be put into practice and integrated into the clinical decision[3]. Similarly, patients' values should be considered in the way patients are diagnosed and treated, but they should not obstruct the clinical process's proper functioning [2].

Conventionally, health professionals' decisions regarding the diagnosis, treatment, and prognosis of patients are based solely on clinical knowledge and experience. The goal of evidence-based medicine is to transform the way these clinical procedures are performed. In fact, evidence-based medicine requires that clinical practice not only rely on conventional methods, but that it be carried out in the form of the

strongest evidence[1]. Moreover, it attaches great emphasis on the practice of medical science with compassion for patients, brings the patient at the centre of diagnosis and treatment and focuses on cost-effective, patient-centred healthcare[2].

2.1.2 HISTORY OF EVIDENCE-BASED MEDICINE

The journey of evidence-based medicine goes back to the seventeenth century. At that time, when comparing patients receiving bleeding during their cholera treatment with those who were not treated in this way, it was found that the mortality rate increased after treatment with bleeding. Gordon Guyatt of McMaster University pioneered the concept of "Scientific Medicine" in 1990. Guyatt, later, suggested evidence-based medicine as a compulsory subject in resident training programs.

The theory of "Clinical Epidemiology", was next introduced by Feinstein. It was a combination of epidemiological statistical techniques and clinical inference and was proposed as a new direction in clinical education. Feinstein criticised public medical studies for lacking academic rigor in terms of specified hypotheses, bias, inadequate data, and unsound inference of cause. Sackett et al. presented "Critical Appraisal" as a new approach of reading medical literature in a collection of articles published in the Canadian Medical Association Journal. They requested that the perspectives of not only readers of literature but also users of knowledge should be considered. As a result, they introduced the term "clinical practice guideline". According to them, this term could be used by all clinicians to comprehend a specific piece of literature.

Following this, the Cochrane Collaboration was established. The specific name of the institution was given in honour of Archie Cochrane and his efforts to eliminate bias in medical research through randomised controlled trials. The British National Health Service (NHS) subsequently adopted evidence-based medicine as the primary objectives and processes for the development of the medical system [4][5].

2.1.3 ANALYSIS OF THE DIFFERENT STEPS OF EVIDENCE-BASED-MEDICINE

Evidence-based medicine is carried out in five steps. The first step is to formulate the clinical question, while the second is to find the appropriate evidence to answer that clinical question. The third step consists of a thorough critical analysis of the evidence: the accuracy and usefulness of the evidence are evaluated. In the fourth step, the results of the evaluation of the previous step are applied in clinical practice. The fifth step entails assessing the overall performance of the preceding process.

> First step: Formulation of the clinical question

The necessary procedure to be carried out is to transform the clinical question into an answerable question. More specifically, the first step involves the formulation of an answerable clinical question which is based on a patient's case. A clinical question can be considered valid if it is precise, clearly communicated, meaningful, directly focused on the problem, clear in its purpose and need for research, answerable by searching the medical literature, and limits the effort required to obtain the answer.

The use of the PICO-SD standard is highly recommended when formulating a clinical question. The initials of this abbreviation represent the following: Patients or Population (e.g., patients undergoing sedation therapy), Intervention or Exposure (e.g., combination therapy with propofol and another sedative), Comparison or Control (e.g., propofol monotherapy), Outcomes (e.g., Risk of adverse effect), Study design (e.g., randomised controlled trial).

> Second step: Finding the right evidence

Having already formulated the clinical question, the next step is to look for evidence that will allow an answer this specific question, identifying resources, including scientific publications such as books, reports, and journals, individual experience, and peer perspectives. It also involves generating appropriate keywords, selecting a literature survey database (e.g., MEDLINE, EMBASE, CINAHL) and finally conducting the research.

› Third step: Critical appraisal of the evidence

Following the acquisition of the best evidence, the next step is to evaluate the evidence in terms of accuracy, importance, and clinical applicability to the patients of interest. Risk of bias reflects the quality of the research. The most common type of bias is known as selection bias. The presence of selection bias proves that proper randomisation was not done, and the sample of the study is not representative. A biased study may reach an invalid conclusion, overestimate, or underestimate the outcome.

› Fourth step: Application of the results of the previous step's evaluation in clinical practice

After conducting a survey and evaluating the evidence, the results are reviewed, and a decision is made about whether this evidence can be applied in clinical practice. This decision should consider the patient's values, desires, and priorities. The cost and availability of the specific treatment in each health facility must also be considered. The clinician should ensure that the patient makes an informed decision and is aware of both the effectiveness and risks of the evidence.

› Fifth step: Assessment of the overall evidence-based medicine procedure

As a particular evidence-based approach is integrated into regular clinical practice, a feedback mechanism should be developed to regularly evaluate this approach and suggest possible improvements [4][5].

2.1.4 RANDOMISED CONTROL TRIALS AND OBSERVATIONAL STUDIES

Clinical research questions in evidence-based medicine can be answered by evidence based on a variety of study designs. The most significant of these studies is the randomised control trial (RCT), in which participants are randomly assigned to either an experimental or a control group. The expected difference between these two groups is the outcome under investigation. RCTs sometimes are not indicated or ethically correct to address a clinical research question. At the next levels of the hierarchy, observational studies, which are also a significant type of research design, are placed. This kind of study is presented as the next more appropriate method for answering clinical questions.

Both randomised control trials and observational studies are grouped under the umbrella of analytic studies. The difference between these two studies is the presence or absence of an intervention. In observational studies, an observation and assessment of the significance of the association between an exposure and a disease variable is conducted, and no intervention takes place. The three types of observational studies are cohort studies, cross-sectional studies, and case-control studies. Case-control and cohort studies measure the disease occurrence and its association with an exposure (intervention/treatment or naturally occurring exposure) and focus on the time factor (i.e., prospective, or retrospective study design). Cross-sectional studies, on the other hand, focus on the study of the disease and its association with an exposure at a specific time point. At the lowest levels of evidence, we find non-analytical studies such as case reports, which are reports on diagnosis and treatment of a patient, and case series, which is a collection of case reports of patients given similar treatment.

A RCT is more appropriate when evaluating an intended effect, an outcome, of an intervention. For example, an intervention may be the prescription of a drug and the intended effect to be evaluated may be the prevention of mortality from that drug. On the other hand, in observational studies examine the effects of exposure: there are no intended or unintended effects, only outcomes [4][5].

2.1.5 ADVANTAGES AND LIMITATIONS

Implementing evidence-based medicine helps establish national standards for patient care at the lowest possible cost and develop specific criteria for measuring and rewarding performance-based clinical practice. Evidence-based medicine has also helped to reform medical ethics and ensure that the best

evidence is used in practice. Implementation of evidence-based medicine also promotes treatment consistency and optimal clinical outcomes. A significant contribution of evidence-based medicine is the Cochrane Collaboration, which produces more than four hundred systematic reviews of clinical trials of a variety of medical treatments each year.

The limitations of medicine include the possibility of insufficient evidence and the possible existence of obstacles to the application of that evidence in the treatment of an individual patient. Limitations may also include the lack of skills and time of clinicians, as well as the lack of resources in the clinical settings for adequate research and evaluation [4][5].

2.2 HYPOTHESIS TESTING IN MEDICINE

2.2.1 DEFINITION OF HYPOTHESIS TESTING

Healthcare providers rely on evidence-based medicine to support clinical decision-making procedures. Researchers conducting studies require research questions and hypotheses to guide their analyses. They often identify a gap in the existing clinical practice or research by starting with broad research questions. Research questions do not imply presumptions or projections. Instead, research hypotheses should be formulated. A hypothesis is a predefined declaration about a research question in which the researcher makes a precise, educated guess about the study's outcome. Subsequently, an explicit clinical question is formulated, and the appropriate research hypothesis is tested. The results are provided usually with p values, confidence intervals, or even both. Furthermore, the researchers estimate or determine the level of statistical or research significance [6].

In hypothesis testing, there are two statistical hypotheses, which should be defined explicitly and a priori. One of these two statistical hypotheses is called the null hypothesis (represented by the symbol H_0) and it is the one to be tested. The scientist conducting testing of a hypothesis will either end up rejecting the null hypothesis or failing to reject it. The null hypothesis is defined with the sole purpose of rejecting it. The other statistical hypothesis is named the alternative hypothesis, or the research hypothesis (often represented by the symbol H_A). The alternative hypothesis is the one that is sought to be proven. The testing of a hypothesis requires the finding of convincing evidence intending to accept the alternative hypothesis. In other words, hypothesis testing aims to reject the null hypothesis in favour of the alternative hypothesis [7][8].

For example, a common clinical research question may be whether a particular medication is effective in fighting a particular disease. The null hypothesis, in this example, can state that no statistical difference exists between two groups, the one receiving an already existing drug and the other receiving the new drug its effectiveness is being tested. The research hypothesis can state that the new drug, in comparison to the already existing drug, significantly reduces the disease's symptoms, based on specific statistic values [6].

2.2.2 ERRORS IN HYPOTHESIS TESTING

There are two types of errors that can occur during a hypothesis testing. A type I error (false-positive) occurs when the null hypothesis is rejected, but it is true in the population. A type II error (false-negative) occurs if the researcher fails to reject the null hypothesis, but it is false. It is easy to understand that by increasing the sample size, the range of these errors can be reduced, while they can never be avoided entirely [9].

2.2.3 P-VALUES

P-values and level of significance are two important tools needed during the decision-making process of rejecting or not the null hypothesis.

P-value is the probability of obtaining an effect at least as extreme (equal or rarer) as the one in the

sample data set, assuming that the null hypothesis is true. In a case that in a recent study the sample mean is quite different from the mean in the previous one, there are two possibilities: either the means are different, or this observation is a result of random sampling. Calculating the p-value, if it is small enough, the difference of means is quite unlikely to exist due to random sampling [10].

2.2.4 SIGNIFICANCE

The significance level, often noted as alpha “ α ”, is the probability of making a type I error. So, it is the probability of rejecting the null hypothesis when it is true in the population. A significance level of 0.05, for example, demonstrates a 5% risk of concluding that a difference was found (rejecting the null hypothesis), with regards to a statistical value, when there is no actual difference in the population. The significance level indicates the critical region in a statistical test. The critical region defines how far the sample statistic should deviate from the null hypothesis value, to reach the conclusion that it is unusual enough and therefore the null hypothesis is rejected. It is important that the significance level is chosen before the beginning of a study. It provides protection to the researcher against choosing a significance level because it conveniently delivers significant results. Statistical significance is the probability that the correlation or difference that is identified in a sample data set did occur by complete coincidence, and it does not exist in the general population. When a p-value is less than or equal to the significance level, the null hypothesis is rejected in favour of the alternative hypothesis. If the p-value does not fall within the critical region, then the researcher fails to reject the null hypothesis. Data with a $p < 0.05$ or $p < 0.01$ level of significance is considered statistically significant [11].

It is very important that healthcare providers should consider, also, the clinical significance of statistical research findings. When evaluating biomedical research, clinicians must distinguish statistical from clinical significance. For example, a study with large sample size and statistically significant correlation findings may be meaningless and irrelevant to healthcare professionals. The evaluation of the practical significance of studies through a clinical judgment is of great value. Clinicians who perform evidence-based medicine to guide practice should carefully evaluate the design, the sample size, the probabilities of type I and type II errors, the process of data analysis, the statistical findings and finally evaluate the result using practical clinical evidence [12].

2.2.5 STATISTICAL HYPOTHESIS TESTS

Parametric statistical hypothesis tests are based on certain assumptions regarding the distribution of the population from which the sample was derived. All hypothesis parametric tests for means of continuous outcomes, are performed given the assumption that the outcome follows approximately a normal distribution in the population (i.e., most scores are around the mean, while fewer are at either extreme). Many parametric tests remain robust and maintain their statistical power, even though the normality assumption is violated, when the size of the sample is adequately large. On the other hand, non-parametric statistical tests rely on fewer assumptions and can be applied to population data that does not follow a normal distribution. In medical research, the use of non-parametric methods is recommended since normally distributed data is an exception rather than the rule. However, the fact that they are based on fewer hypotheses makes them lose some of their statistical power resulting in a lower probability of rejecting the null hypothesis when the alternative is correct [13][14][15].

2.2.5.1 Parametric hypothesis tests

2.2.5.1.1 T-test

Student's t-test is a parametric statistical hypothesis test that is mainly used to examine if the two means of two samples are reliably different from each other. Student's t-test compares the expectations of two populations and presupposes independent sampling from normal distributions with equal variation. The test statistic follows a student's t-test distribution under the null hypothesis, with $n_1 + n_2 - 2$ degrees of

freedom: $T = \frac{m1-m2}{s \sqrt{\frac{1}{n1} + \frac{1}{n2}}}$, where m1 and m2 denote the observed sample means, n1 and n2 denote the

sample sizes of the two groups, s denotes an estimate of the common standard deviation.

There are three main types of t-tests: the one-sample t-test, the independent-samples t-test (also referred to as unpaired or two-sample t-test), and the paired-samples t-test.

- › One sample: The one-sample t-test examines if the mean of a population has a value specified in a null hypothesis.
- › Two-sample: The two-sample t-test examines if the means of two different groups are reliably different.
- › Paired samples: In paired samples t-tests, a sample of matched pairs of similar units or one group of units that has been tested twice is used. A common application of the repeated measures t-test is when participants are examined prior to receiving therapy, such as for high blood pressure, and then again after receiving treatment with a blood pressure-lowering medicine. The same patient's numbers are compared before and after therapy.

2.2.5.1.2 ANOVA

Analysis of variance (ANOVA) is one of the most used statistical tools in medical research and can be described as an extension to t-test. ANOVA is a non-parametric statistical method for comparing the means of two or more samples. In this method, the variance is used to infer the means, rather than the analysis of means.

The method is based on the comparison of variances between groups and within each group. The test statistic is denoted by F and is the ratio of the between and within group variances. The F-value will be high if the variance between the groups is greater than the variance inside the group. The null hypothesis of the test claims that the groups' means are equal. A high F value provides evidence for the rejection of the null hypothesis [16].

2.2.5.2 Non-parametric hypothesis tests

2.2.5.2.1 Chi-squared test

Chi-squared test is a non-parametric statistical hypothesis test that is basically used to examine if two categorical variables are independent. It is, also, used, to test how closely a sample variable fits the distribution of a known population (goodness of fit test) or to examine whether the distributions of two or more independent samples differ on a specific variable (test of homogeneity). Therefore, it is used in hypothesis testing regarding one or two categorical variables. The null hypothesis of this test defines that the observed values match the expected values used for hypothesis testing regarding one or two categorical variables. All three tests in Karl Pearson family of chi-square tests (independence, goodness of fit, homogeneity) use the same formula. The most significant distinction between the three tests is in the different scenarios in which they should be applied. Following the rejection of the null hypothesis, each of these statistical tests has its own set of hypotheses and possibilities. The test statistic has a chi-squared distribution, and it is calculated using the formula below:

$$x^2 = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{(O_i - E_i)^2}{E_i}$$

where n denotes the table's number of cells. The derived test statistic is compared to a critical value from the chi-square distribution with $(r - 1)(c - 1)$ degrees of freedom. The level of significance is, also determined at the beginning of the test. O_i denotes the observed values, while E_i denotes the expected values [17].

The chi-square test of independence is used to evaluate if two categorical variables in a sample are independent or related. An example could be a survey with each person responding with their marital status (e.g. never married, married, divorced, widowed) and qualification (e.g., middle school, high school, bachelor's, master's, PhD). The test could be used to examine if the marital status and the qualification level are independent. According to the null hypothesis, the one variable is not associated with the second variable, while according to the alternative hypothesis the variables of interest (marital status and qualification) are related. A chi-squared test with high significance that rejects the null hypothesis implies that the marital status is associated with the qualification level, and therefore there is not independence between the two variables [17].

2.2.5.2.2 Mann-Whitney U Test

The Mann-Whitney U Test (also named Wilcoxon rank-sum test) is a non-parametric alternative method to the unpaired (two-sample) Student's t-test, and it is used for the comparison of a continuous outcome in two independent samples. More explicitly, this method is performed to determine whether two samples belong out of the same population. The test statistic is denoted by U and is calculated using the following formula:

$$U = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^m S(X_i, Y_j), \text{ with } S(X, Y) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } X > Y \\ \frac{1}{2}, & \text{if } Y = X \\ 0, & \text{if } X < Y \end{cases}$$

The null hypothesis claims that the two populations are equal, while the research hypothesis states that the two populations are different. The null hypothesis is rejected in favour of the alternative if the observed test statistic U is less than or equal to the critical value [13][14][15][18].

2.2.5.2.3 Wilcoxon signed-rank test

Wilcoxon signed-rank test is a non-parametric statistical hypothesis method, which is considered as an alternative test to the paired samples t-test, on a set of paired samples. Unlike the student's t-test it is not based on the assumption that the differences between matched samples follow a normal distribution. This non-parametric test is used to compare two paired samples of a continuous outcome.

The difference scores (concerning the two different situations) are calculated, ranked, and signed. The null hypothesis states that the mean difference is zero, while the research hypothesis could claim that there is a positive median difference. The sums of positive and negative ranks are calculated, and the test statistic (denoted as W) is defined as the smaller value of these two sums. The null hypothesis gets rejected in favour of the alternative hypothesis, when there are more higher and positive ranks, and therefore the sum of positive ranks is substantially larger than the sum of negative ranks [13][14][15].

2.2.5.2.4 Kruskal Wallis test

The Kruskal-Wallis method, first introduced in 1952 by Kruskal and Wallis, is a non-parametric test for comparing median value among more than two groups. Here, The Mann-Whitney U test is expanded to include k>2 comparison groups. This method is, also, commonly referred to as an ANOVA with ranks instead of data. Unlike the ANOVA, the Kruskal-Wallis method does not assume that the underlying data are normally distributed.

The null hypothesis states that the means of k groups are equal, while the alternative hypothesis states that not all the medians are the same. According to the test technique, first all the groups' observations are combined into a single pool, keeping track of to which sample each observation belongs. Then, the observations are ranked lowest to highest. The test statistic is denoted by H and is calculated as follows:

$$H = \left(\frac{12}{N(N+1)} \sum_{j=1}^k \frac{R_j^2}{n_j} \right) - 3(N+1), \text{ where } k=\text{number of comparison groups, } N=\text{total sample size,}$$

n_j =sample size in the j^{th} group, and R_j is the sum of ranks in the j^{th} group. By establishing a critical value for the test statistic, obtained from a table of critical values for the Kruskal Wallis test or a software - for a specific predefined alpha level, the null hypothesis can be rejected in favour of the research hypothesis, if the observed test statistic exceeds this critical value [13][14][15].

2.3 PROCESS MODELLING AND MANAGEMENT

2.3.1 IN HEALTHCARE

Healthcare across Europe and globally faces a tremendous pressure. While the quantity and quality of healthcare has improved significantly, the scale and complexity of healthcare requirements have increased. Most countries have been oriented towards a digital transformation to close the gap between the supply of resources and the demand for healthcare. This will result to the increase of efficiency and effectiveness of service delivery benefiting both patients and clinicians.

Over the past decade numerous EU policies, directives, regulations, and funding programs have emerged to support the digitalisation of healthcare systems. Specifically, in April 2018, the European Commission published a definitive communication that included a comprehensive overview of previous actions taken to promote the digitalisation of health and several commitments to put forward digital transformation. A survey of 1.800 clinicians and interviews with over 40 stakeholders across seven countries (Denmark, Germany, Italy, the Netherlands, Norway, Portugal, and the UK demonstrated that the top three challenges faced by clinicians were bureaucracy in healthcare (57%), the cost of technologies (50%) and finding the right technologies (49%).[19] Figure 3 summarises the benefits of digital transformation. Digital transformation of healthcare involves multiple stakeholders from different disciplines. Fig. shows the benefits of digital transformation while Figure 4 presents the stakeholders involved in the digital transformation of healthcare.

Figure 3 – The benefits of digital transformation (Source: Deloitte research and analysis 2020)

Figure 4 – Stakeholders involved in the digital transformation of healthcare (Source: Deloitte research and analysis 2020)

Given the continuous challenges that healthcare faces in the past years, many interventions have focused on process improvements with the objective of enhancing efficiency and efficacy to improve patient outcomes while controlling costs. At the same time the quality of care and patient safety remain the major concern. In this context, several tools have been developed to support process improvement through process mapping.

Among the various application domains suitable to be addressed by a Business Process Management (BPM) approach, the healthcare domain is probably the most challenging. The emphasis of performance management in health care is shifting from an output-based to a system-based approach. Systems that follow a BPM approach improve their interoperability between other systems and applications, that is, the ability of one system to interact and communicate with another, due to the more uniform process management.

Healthcare faces difficulties and problems in process management. These management problems can be categorised in three main categories: strategic, tactical, and operational. From a BPM perspective, problems at a strategic level, which are at the highest level of importance in the categorisation, are related to process-oriented management, support and IT, organisation of processes and administration problems. The tactical level of problems addresses the difficulties in process modelling, measurement of process and methodological performance. Finally, at the operational level, the problems are related to difficulties in the technologies that support process management. Table 1 presents the general problems that fall within the categories mentioned above [20], [21]

Table 1 – General problems of process management[22]

Strategic Level	Tactical level	Operational Level
Lack of governance	Lack of standards and norms	Lack of support tools for process visualization
Lack of training for employees	Process specification weaknesses	Gaps between process design and process execution
Lack of knowledge sharing	Lack of methodologies	Lack of communication and tool handling capabilities
Connection failure between measures and organisational strategy		

Process-driven healthcare organisations can better take advantage of data, respond to developments in the industry, reduce errors, improve the bottom line, and provide a higher level of patient care. Process based change needs to begin with a shared understanding of the landscape and that in turn requires a common vocabulary when it comes to processes. Healthcare organisations can progress to modelling, analysing, redesigning, and automating critical business processes with BPM. BPM can also be instrumental in assuring compliance. it’s essential to ensure that operational processes remain in compliance with regulations and health-care professionals follow currently mandated procedures. BPM is now recognised as a major trend in technology and many healthcare organisations are looking to use BPM to improve the efficiency of operations[23]

The potential benefits of applying BPM in the healthcare environment include the following:

- › Automate non-value-added tasks and eliminate non-value-added ones
- › Monitor and improve care delivery as it occurs
- › Visualize functions and processes, for example by representing them as easy-to-understand flowcharts
- › Identify and avert resource bottlenecks
- › Redesign the processes suffering from inefficiencies and bottlenecks.
- › Analyse and measure the outcome of processes according to specific key performance indicators (KPIs) after executing and monitoring them.
- › Fine-tune these processes based on data gathered in the previous phases.
- › Automate the identification of critical conditions using analytics
- › Manage task assignments, statuses, roles, and history with intuitive dashboards
- › Monitor cost, quality, and compliance metrics

The biggest healthcare organisations have grown and complexity, integrating bigger care facilities that have been established to improve health quality and patient satisfaction in terms of accessibility, cost-effectiveness, and participation. Subsequently, medical treatments have become primarily multidisciplinary, including also social and daily life aspects. As a result, all the processes used to represent healthcare procedures have to consider numerous factors and must be able to harmonise human, physical, and informational resources. These facts suggests that the understanding of healthcare processes and related information, when combined with proper knowledge management, supports clinicians in scheduling and their work, making the right decisions. Indeed, a lot of clinical tasks, such as

clinical diagnosis and drug treatment are knowledge intensive by nature, that is, medical knowledge plays the most important role in driving care providers actions and decisions [24], [25].

A healthcare process, sometimes called a care-flow, is any set of activities performed to provide medical care for one or more patients presenting a specific clinical condition. Healthcare processes integrate medical and organisational tasks, and each one of them is performed by one or more process participants (agents), often covering a medical or administrative role in the organisation entitled of care provision.

2.3.1.1 Business Process Management Examples in Healthcare

As healthcare rapidly evolves, the industry requires tools that can keep up. Here are three examples of vital healthcare processes that can be improved with BPM[26].

2.3.1.2 Claims Processing

Claims processing is a complex task that also encompasses compliance and reporting activities and requires a smooth flow of information. BPM technology can simplify these processes by streamlining each associated activity. Claims and patient appeals can be handled more quickly and monitored at every step, to make it easier to track and prioritise claims.

2.3.1.3 Big Data

Big Data refers to the massive amount of data now available to businesses through the proliferation of the Internet. It is defined in terms of volume, velocity, and variety. Thanks to electronic health records, a rapidly growing amount of healthcare information is now available and shareable. BPM technology allows organisations to manage their data and improve the way it is utilised.

For example, monitoring regional disease trends can help gauge the effectiveness of certain vaccines and predict future needs. BPM offers opportunities to leverage big data to improve healthcare for individuals and the general population, through preventive care and proactive responses.

2.3.1.4 Software Applications

BPM can help fill in the gaps that occur when multiple software applications are used in performing routine healthcare processes. It forges links that capture information not covered by existing applications and provides information more quickly to expedite patient care. BPM also bridges gaps from manual functions, such as face-to-face or email patient interactions, that can raise costs and place an organisation at risk of non-compliance.

The following table (Table 2) provides a summary of the main complexity areas of clinical processes. For each of the sources of complexity, sub-areas are specified that become the requirement for the modelling effort[27][28].

Table 2 – Complexity areas of clinical processes

Clinical process complexity areas	Sub-areas	Modelling requirement to represent the sub-area
Medical knowledge	Evidence based medicine, guidelines, recommendations	R1: Compliance to guidelines R2: Deal with dynamic evolution of medical evidence-based knowledge
	Local practices	R3: Manage flexibility (from meta-model to local context)
	Clinician personal experience, habits and skills	R4: Bind the design to interaction and cooperation between analysts and domain experts

	Learning by practice	R5: Deal with learning curves (process change)
	Building evidence from practice	R6: Foresee process mining with big data analysis
Response to treatment	Timeframe short-term or long-term response	R8: Manage uncertainty
	Compliance – depending on patient’s engagement	R9: Manage indeterminacy
	Expected outcomes	R10: Define outcome variables
	Patient feedback to reshape therapy – depending on patient’s empowerment and education	R11: Integrate patient-reported outcome measures
		R8: Manage uncertainty
Personalization of care	Patient-centric approach – treatment definition considering patients preferences and history	R7: Manage exceptions R3: Manage flexibility
	Treatment adaptation considering occurring changes	R3: Manage flexibility

2.3.2 IN MEDICAL RESEARCH

Process management in medical research is fundamental in raising the efficiency of the decision-making process and performed actions, cost optimisation, time reduction, and reduction of used resources.

The initial phase attempts to describe patient treatment from a process-based perspective. This is achieved through the identification of diagnostic and therapeutic processes called clinical pathways, which are, in essence, the standard procedure in each healthcare unit. In effect, when implementing process management in healthcare, the following points should be taken into account:

- › The process should be patient and not disease oriented
- › Different clinical and extra-clinical pathways (management, support, logistics, and others) should comprise a cohesive system.
- › Clinical pathways should be reflected in IT systems, used on an ongoing basis by physicians and other relevant personnel.
- › The management of knowledge used in planning treatments and treating patients. From this perspective, clinical pathways should perform the role of a repository of knowledge and a model against which both current and new knowledge from patient treatment is verified.

The goal of the current research is to use various assumptions and models of situational awareness in combination with models of clinical decision making as a "theoretical lens" to capture and describe the decision-making requirements (i.e., knowledge/expertise, goals, resources, and information, communication/coordination needs) related to the perception, understanding, and projection of a situation leading to a critical decision. The goal is to explore how we can model these requirements as extensions of traditional process modelling languages (e.g., BPMN), possibly in the form of a discrete decision perspective. In MES-CoBraD preliminary research, we identified the following questions:

- › Will the advancement from written procedures and flowcharts to draw the detailed business process address the complexity of interrelations?

- › Will the implementation of dynamic BPM be performed in a way that matches its documentation?
- › Will the use of a discrete decision perspective in process models lead to a better understanding of how we can design information systems to support decision-making tasks in dynamic work environments?

To answer these questions, we need to design and evaluate a set of modelling constructs that allow us to represent aspects of coordination, communication, and decision making in clinical processes. This requires identifying relevant cases from the healthcare work environment and collecting data through participant observation and interviewing individuals in their natural work environment, which can serve as a basis for further research.

Critical success factors (CSFs) contributing to successful development and implementation of the clinical pathway include [29], among others:

- › Analysis of related works to determine the best clinical practice for each medical condition and incorporating it into the clinical pathways.
- › Definition of the care process in each clinical pathway.
- › Creation of the multi-disciplinary teams and granting ownership of each pathway disciplines involved in the care process.
- › Invitation of all medical professions to comment on each pathway before their implementation.
- › Incorporation of clinical pathways into the patients' medical records.
- › Implementation of the regular feedback loop to all health professionals involved in the clinical pathway.

Complexity issues require the development of the following:

- › Standard procedures dividing processes into hierarchical levels: maps, process models, and action.
- › Charts with information, with the adequate level of detail and adequate scope of subject matter.
- › Standard goals and rules of dividing the entire process into sub-processes on specific levels, and a clear presentation of their interrelations.

Notation of description of processes, independent of the country in question, the geographical area, and the IT tool used to model processes (e.g., Business Process Model and Notation—BPMN).

The issues of describing clinical pathways result from the lack of consequence in using methodologies and process tools, when dealing with diagnostic and therapeutic processes. To avoid such issues, descriptions of clinical pathways should be prepared with the use of principles, methodologies, and notations, commonly and successfully adapted in process management [30].

2.4 DATA ANALYTICS AND PROCESSING

Data analysis purpose is usually the extraction of information from data and to provide actionable input to a decision-making process. Usually it requires several steps, like cleaning and transforming the initial dataset before applying statistical methods to them. Visualisation is one of the key cognitive abilities that allows the humans to interpret and understand data. Visualisation tools' focus should be to provide

adequate interpretability and explainability of the data, especially those that have already been through the data analysis process.

Data analysis and visualisation applications in medical fields faces specific industry issues the platform aims to address[31]. Specifically:

- › Analysis of structured, inhomogeneous, and multimodal data
 - The platform should allow the users to create a model with the appropriate level of complexity to allow for robust results. Also choose the appropriate level of interpretability and provide the capability of assessing it in the context of the application domain. It should allow the choice of the correct model to represent specific biomedical data. Additionally, it should provide measure to detect similarity and dissimilarity of structured data.
- › Feature selection

The platform should aid with the identification, selection, and verification of relevant biomarkers in complex data structures. These features will be used for the data analysis and predictions about specific diseases or behaviours. It should also provide methods to infer the non-Euclidian structure of biomedical data in some manner.
- › Diagnosis Classification
 - The platform should allow classification that is robust with respect to noise and missing values. It should aid with improving their sensitivity for diagnostic processes. Additionally, it should allow the modelling of temporal aspect like stages and progression/regression under treatment.
- › Visualisation
 - The platform should aid with select the most appropriate visualisation techniques for heterogenous and structured data. It should allow the clear display of errors and uncertainties, especially those resulting from embedding high-dimensional data into low dimensional spaces.

Finally in the traditional application of data analysis in the medical sector there exists an additional sub cycle in the process, where medical experts seek several things from the data analysts, which the platform should consider. In this cycle of feedback, the data analyst is asked to, guarantee the interpretability and explainability of the models, to comply with clinical protocol and guidelines and comply with system human interaction workflow at the point of care. On the other hand, the medical experts need to, have a realistic understanding of the limitation and possibilities of analytical models, clearly state the medical requirements, clearly describe the medical decision process and verify the results [32].

2.4.1 STATISTICAL METHODS AND DATA ANALYSIS IN MEDICAL RESEARCH

In medical research, various statistical methods are used for the analysis of data as well as for the extraction of patterns and knowledge. In statistics, correlation is a well-known technique that is used to assess a possible two-way linear association or any other relationship between two continuous variables[33]. The correlation coefficient is the numerical measure of the correlation and reflects the linear association of two continuous variables. It is a dimensionless quantity and takes values from -1 to 1. The values ± 1 indicate perfect linear relationship, while 0 indicates no linear relationship[34]. There are two main types of correlation coefficients, Pearson's product moment and Spearman's rank, which are used depending on the types of variables [35].

Regression analysis is another process for accessing the possible relationships between a dependent variable and one or more independent variables [36]. The existence of a dependent variable constitutes the main difference between regression and correlation. In other words, Regression attempts to establish how one variable affects another variable, while Correlation measures the strength of the relationship between two variables. There are three types of regression analysis: Linear Regression, Multiple Linear Regression and Nonlinear Regression[36].

Moreover, in medical research the basic statistical methods and metrics, such as Variance and Standard Deviation, Mean, Method of Least Squares etc. are used for the extraction of information and for the analysis of data [37]. For instance, the standard deviation and the estimated standard error are used to interpret the results of a statistical analysis [38].

Regarding the Neuroimaging data, the clinicians and the researchers perform various transformations before the process and the analysis of the data. This step is a part of the pre-processing of the data, in which a large number of transformations takes place. The most important ones are the following:

- › Spatial Normalisation: Spatial normalisation is a special form of image registration, which is a process of transforming different sets of data into a single unified coordinate system [39], that maps a subject's PET or MRI image to a reference brain space in order to allow comparisons across subjects with varied brain morphologies.
- › Spatial Smoothing: Spatial smoothing is the process in which the data points are averaged with their neighbours acting as a low pass filter. This has as a result the sharp "edges" to be blurred and the spatial correlation within the data to be more distinct [40].
- › Coregistration: Coregistration is a process that implements the alignment of functional and structural images from the same subject to map functional information into anatomical space. It is applied in order to correct any movements of the head during an experimental run.
- › Generalised linear model (GLM): GLM can be thought of as an extension of a more familiar statistical technique, linear regression. Linear regression, sometimes called trend-line analysis, is a method used to calculate the "best fitting" line for a set of experimental data.
- › Slice time correction: Slice time correction is a transformation applied to correct slice-dependent delays, achieved by shifting the time series of each slice to temporally align all slices to a reference time-point [41].

Regarding the analysis of electroencephalograms (EEGs), the clinicians and the researchers are using specific methods for the handling of the signal. Some of these methods are presented below:

- › Time frequency analysis: The time frequency analysis of EEG signals provides the correct visualization of EEG signals to extract the various rhythms of frequencies like alpha, beta, gamma waves. The short-time Fourier transform (STFT) provides some information on both the timing and the frequencies at which a signal event occurs.

The Wavelet Transform (WT) can be thought of as an extension of the classic Fourier transform, except that, instead of working on a single scale (time or frequency), it works on a multi-scale basis. This multi-scale feature of the WT allows the decomposition of a signal into a number of scales, each scale representing a particular coarseness of the signal under study [42].

- › Time series analysis: Time series analysis involves developing models that best capture or describe an observed time series in order to understand the underlying causes. This field of study seeks the "why" behind a time series dataset.

- › Time series forecasting: Several approaches have been introduced for forecasting seizures, including ARMA, ARIMA models, etc.
- › Repairing artifacts: Artifacts are parts of the recorded signal that arise from sources other than the source of interest (i.e., neuronal activity in the brain). As such, artifacts are a form of interference or noise relative to the signal of interest.
- › Down-up sampling: As the name suggests, the process of converting the sampling rate of a digital signal from one rate to another is Sampling Rate Conversion. Increasing the rate of already sampled signal is Upsampling, whereas decreasing the rate is called downsampling.

What is more, the statistical tests constitute a significant part of the Medical Research. These tests are used to determine the strength of a relationship or to evaluate a hypothesis. A number of well-known tests are the following: Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) test, T-test, Z-test, Chi-square test, McNemar's test. These tests are presented in detail in Section 2.2.5.

Data analytics are used in Medical Research in order to provide insights about the trends as well as to facilitate in decision making. The health data contain information that must be interpreted in the most accurate and efficient way. The clinicians and the researchers cannot reveal the whole information since the data are in complex format and their correlation as well as trends are not easy to be understood. Therefore, the clinicians turn to Data Analytics in order to have accurate and insightful data alongside with the health data of the patients. Data Analytics can be categorised into 4 categories [43]:

- › Descriptive analytics: uses data from the past to extract knowledge about trends and patterns, helping the people to understand better what happened in the past.
- › Predictive analytics: uses forecasting models to predict what is likely to happen in the future.
- › Prescriptive analytics: uses machine learning to propose strategies and actions by analysing the potential impact of these actions.
- › Discovery analytics: uses machine learning to analyse raw data in order to identify patterns and relationships among the data. It helps people understand what is needed to be explored further.

There is a large number of applications of data analytics in healthcare, which attempts to facilitate the work of the clinicians by providing more accurate and correct data and techniques. For instance, some applications of the data analytics in Health aim at evaluating and developing tools and methods, which are used by Practitioners for the detection of anomalies in Scans as well as the Prediction of outbreaks [44]. Moreover, there are various techniques used in Medicine for data mining and extraction of knowledge [45]. In addition, in medical research and trials the survival analysis is used widely. The survival analysis is a branch of statistics for analysing the expected duration of time until one event occurs, such as death in biological organisms. Kaplan Meier analysis measures the survival time between a certain time and a significant event. Therefore, it is clear that the survival analysis is crucial in medical research [46].

2.4.2 DATA VISUALIZATIONS

In neuroscience, the clinicians use widely the visualisation of data in order to have a more complete view of the data, since patterns, trends, outbreaks and outliers are visible. In this subsection, some of these visualisations are presented below:

- › Heatmap: Heatmaps, which are also called intensity maps or point density interpolation, are visual structures for a spatial visualisation of the data. Figure 5 shows a heatmap of a correlation matrix.

Figure 6 – Hypnogram

- › EEG Topography: EEG Topography is a neuroimaging technique in which the brain activity is presented with several tones of colour depending on the intensity of the brain activity. The input derives from EEG electrodes that have been placed onto the head of the patient. Figure 7 shows an EEG Topography.

Figure 7 – EEG Topography

- › Spectrogram: Spectrogram is a time-frequency image processing technique used for the analysis of EEGs. This technique is used in Short Time Fourier Transform, in which the signal is mapping into two-dimensional function of frequency or time. Figure 8 illustrates a STFT spectrogram.

Figure 8 – STFT spectrogram

2.5 ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

2.5.1 THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

Artificial intelligence (AI) is a branch of computer science that focuses on developing computers and machines that can perform tasks that usually require human intelligence. Such software systems operate in an intentional, intelligent, and adaptive manner. Artificial intelligence has evolved dramatically in recent years and - although it is often the subject of exaggeration or even catastrophic scenarios - it is enough to focus on real technological advances to realise its exciting potential.

Avoiding technical terminology, an artificial intelligence system could be defined as a computer system that can perform cognitive functions while adapting and 'learning' to become more efficient. Modern artificial intelligence systems can 'understand' their environment in real time and make optimal decisions. 'Understanding the environment' is the efficient processing of multiple signals and data streams. Computer Vision and Natural Language Processing technologies allow computer systems to 'understand' images, videos, and speech and to react in the best possible way. The applications are unlimited and impressive: from autonomous cars that can 'see' and perceive their environment in real time, to special applications such as several AI systems that help people with severe visual impairments to better understand the environment. In this example, the visually impaired user can ask the system for a detailed description of the environment or brief updates of the changes that are taking place - by simply communicating in natural language. Computer Vision technology provides new capabilities in a wide range of applications such as navigation, robotics, medical diagnostics, more efficient management of online content, security systems, etc.

The ability of computers to 'see' is undoubtedly an important achievement. Image resolution algorithms can now identify the entities represented in a random image or video, with great accuracy and speed. For example, they can identify people, cars, houses, roads, trees, etc. in an image. In addition, they can estimate other parameters of the image and the entities it includes - in the example above, the make and

type of cars, the number of people, their gender, age or even their emotional state. The algorithm can also identify the occasion being depicted or implied - for example a children's party, a sporting event, a business meeting, or a gathering of people in a square.

Furthermore, Machine learning (ML) is the science of designing algorithms that learn on their own from data and adapt without human correction.

We can think of machine learning (ML) as the science of getting computers to learn automatically. It's a form of artificial intelligence (AI) that allows computers to act like humans and improve their learning as they encounter more data[48].

According to Encyclopedia Britannica, Artificial Intelligence (AI) is “the ability of a digital computer or computer-controlled robot to perform tasks commonly associated with intelligent beings”.

Arthur Samuel defines AI as the “field of study that gives computers the ability to learn without being explicitly programmed”.

Tom Mitchell defines AI as a well-paced learning problem and gives a more streamlined approach to it. “A computer program is said to learn from Experience (E) with respect to some Task (T) and some Performance measure (P), if its performance on T, as measured by P, improves with experience E”.

From the above, we understand that AI is an algorithmic approach, so that the computer program executes algorithms with different mathematical and statistical methods in an intentional, intelligent, and adaptive manner. Since the founding of AI, various sub-objectives have been developed that focus on specific objectives and can be categorised in types, like:

- > Problem solving
- > Perception
- > Reasoning
- > Natural Language Processing
- > Machine Learning

Given a sequence of events of a running case, the objective of process prediction is to forecast how certain aspects of the case unfold in the future. Originally, the focus was to utilise deep learning for next-step prediction and outcome prediction, i.e., to predict the next activity or the last activity of a case based on a sequence of seen activities. This was motivated by the recent success of deep learning for language modelling in the field of natural language processing and its high similarity with process prediction from a conceptual point of view. Key aspects of AI are presented in Figure 9 and Table 3 show the main differences between AI and machine learning[49].

Figure 9 – Key aspects of AI

Table 3 – Key aspects of AI

Topic	Artificial Intelligence	Machine learning
Key Aspects	Artificial intelligence is a technology which enables a machine to simulate human behaviour.	Machine learning is a subset of AI which allows a machine to automatically learn from past data without programming explicitly.
	In AI, we make intelligent systems to perform any task like a human.	In ML, we teach machines with data to perform a particular task and give an accurate result.
	Machine learning and deep learning are the two main subsets of AI.	Deep learning is a main subset of machine learning.
	Based on capabilities, AI can be divided into three types, which are, Weak AI, General AI, and Strong AI.	Machine learning can also be divided into mainly three types that are Supervised learning, Unsupervised learning, and Reinforcement learning.
	It includes learning, reasoning, and self-correction.	It includes learning and self-correction when introduced with new data.
Goals	The goal of AI is to make a smart computer system like humans to solve complex problems.	The goal of ML is to allow machines to learn from data so that they can give accurate output.

	AI is working to create an intelligent system which can perform various complex tasks.	Machine learning is working to create machines that can perform only those specific tasks for which they are trained.
	AI system is concerned about maximising the chances of success.	Machine learning is mainly concerned about accuracy and patterns.
	AI has a very wide range of scope.	Machine learning has a limited scope.
Scopes	The main applications of AI are Siri, customer support using chatbots, Expert System, Online game playing, intelligent humanoid robot, etc.	The main applications of machine learning are Online recommender system, Google search algorithms, Facebook auto friend tagging suggestions, etc.
	AI completely deals with Structured, semi-structured, and unstructured data.	Machine learning deals with Structured and semi-structured data.

2.5.2 AI IN MEDICINE

Since the concept of “artificial intelligence” was introduced in 1956, it has led to numerous technological innovations in human medicine and completely changed the traditional model of medicine[50].

With the rapid development and advancement of artificial intelligence (AI), its influence on clinical diagnosis and treatment is growing. Machine learning and in particular deep learning, which are key digital technologies of AI, are being widely used to assist diagnosis and treatment[51].

Image recognition is the technology of processing and analysing images through computers. It is an important technology in the field of AI, which is based on deep learning. The development of image recognition technology includes three stages—text recognition, digital image recognition, and object recognition. The recognition process can be divided into five steps, including processing the input, image pre-processing, image extraction, classifier construction, and producing the output. This technology can process image data rapidly and efficiently. Image recognition technology has been highly significant in the diagnosis and treatment of intertrochanteric fractures. In addition, it is also widely used in disease prediction, diagnosis, and lesion identification.

Deep learning is a subset of artificial intelligence that is formally defined as “computational models that are composed of multiple processing layers to learn representations of data with multiple levels of abstraction.” A deep learning algorithm consists of a structure referred to as a deep neural network of which a convolutional neural network (CNN) is one type frequently used in imaging[52].

The key difference between deep learning and other types of machine learning is that CNNs develop their own representations needed for pattern recognition rather than requiring human input to structure the data and design feature extractors. In plain language, the algorithm learns for itself the features of an image that are important for classification. Therefore, the algorithm has the freedom to discover classification features that might not have been apparent to humans (particularly when datasets are large) and thereby improve the performance of image classification.

The expert system exhibits a strong ability of clinical decision-making and shows advantages in terms of identification and diagnosis of diseases. However, it is also necessary to enhance the accuracy of the system, combine the system with the patient's medical history, and simultaneously integrate the doctor's clinical experience. In addition, the knowledge and findings in medicine must be constantly updated to

provide doctors with frontier diagnosis and treatment plans.

2.5.3 TRUSTWORTHY AI

In recent years, the rapid spread of AI systems mainly arising from the needs created, it makes the presence of Trustworthy AI necessary. With the development of Trustworthy AI, we can answer reliability questions of the system, but also to prove that the algorithms run transparently. It was not a few, the times where in the past there were cases that the data collected was used for commercial purposes, violating users' personal data. For this reason, the independent High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligent (AI HLEG) was drafted by the European Union, which established some guidelines to produce Trustworthy AIs [53]–[55].

Trustworthy AI systems consist of three main components, so they should be legal, ethical, and robust. At every point of operation of the system, they must obey the relevant legislation, guarantee compliance with the moral principles and not to cause harm to society by having always good intentions. Finally, they should follow the following five (5) principles: Respect for the autonomy of the individual, the avoidance of harm, justice, and the ability to be explained.

Trustworthy AI (TAI) bases on the idea that trust builds the foundation of societies, economies, and sustainable development, and that individuals, organisations, and societies will therefore only ever be able to realise the full potential of AI, if trust can be established in its development, deployment, and use[56].

Trust in IT artifacts based on system characteristics:

Functionality: The belief that the specific technology has the capability, functionality, or features to do for one what one needs to be done.

Helpfulness: The belief that the specific technology provides adequate and responsive help for users.

Reliability / Predictability: The belief that the specific technology will consistently operate properly, and its behaviour can be forecast.

Main benefits of trustworthy AI are summarised in Figure 10.

Figure 10 – Main benefits of Trustworthy AI

2.5.4 EXPLAINABLE AI

Explainable AI (XAI) is a branch of Artificial Intelligence that aims to deconstruct processes in a system, to fully understand the operation, but also the result of this.

When designing and creating an AI system, many times it becomes difficult to interpret the algorithms, but also to explain how they came up with any result. In the literature these systems are called "black boxes". They are systems that on the one hand give great accuracy to the correctness of the results, but they are so complex that they prevent its full understanding on the other hand, the "white box" systems are simpler and quite straight forward without great complexity but lack flexibility and predictive capacity.

Using explainable AI models, we can use the positive elements from the black-box and white-box systems and manufacture models that have great accuracy and high accuracy, but at the same time they are understood by the final users, who can trust the result and evaluate it. This is very important in the field of medicine, since clinicians can with the representation of models accelerate the diagnosis, analyse more easily all the images, and make decisions with transparency and traceability.

To date, XAI is used in neuroscience and behavioural neurostimulation applications, genomics, breast cancer and public health intervention evaluation. In neuroscience, XAI interferes with Deep Learning Models, such as Deep Neural Networks (DNN), Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) and Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN), which contribute to image recognition, image classification and movement recognition. Diseases such as epilepsy have already benefited from XAI solutions, but diseases involving neurophysiological and behavioural data need room for improvement[57]–[66].

Explainable artificial intelligence (XAI) is a set of processes and methods that allows human users to comprehend and trust the results and output created by machine learning algorithms. Explainable AI is used to describe an AI model, its expected impact, and potential biases. It helps characterise model accuracy, fairness, transparency, and outcomes in AI-powered decision making. Explainable AI is crucial for an organisation in building trust and confidence when putting AI models into production. AI explainability also helps an organisation adopt a responsible approach to AI development.

ML models are often thought of as black boxes that are impossible to interpret. Neural networks used in deep learning are some of the hardest for a human to understand. Bias, often based on race, gender, age or location, has been a long-standing risk in training AI models. Further, AI model performance can drift or degrade because production data differs from training data. This makes it crucial for a business to continuously monitor and manage models to promote AI explainability while measuring the business impact of using such algorithms. Explainable AI also helps promote end user trust, model auditability and productive use of AI. It also mitigates compliance, legal, security and reputational risks of production AI.

Explainable AI is one of the key requirements for implementing responsible AI, a methodology for the large-scale implementation of AI methods in real organisations with fairness, model explainability and accountability. To help adopt AI responsibly, organisations need to embed ethical principles into AI applications and processes by building AI systems based on trust and transparency[67].

- › Building trustworthiness: Humans are better able to trust the AI model when the characteristics and rationale of the AI output have been explained.
- › Satisfying legal requirements: Financial and healthcare industries may be required to incorporate machine learning models into their complex risk assessment strategies to fulfil regulatory requirements for effective risk management.
- › Providing ethics-related justification (and removing unconscious biases): Because XAI is transparent and able to more easily be debugged, unconscious biases can be removed, and ethical decisions explained.
- › Deriving actionable and robust insights: AI and Machine Learning (ML), provide the ability to derive actionable and robust insights, however, XAI enables humans to understand how and why the XAI algorithm was able to determine the “next best action.”

This is because the majority of AI with ML operates in what is referred to as a “black box,” that is, in an area that is unable to provide any discernible insights as to how it comes to make decisions. Many AI/ML applications are moderately benign decision engines that are used with online retail recommender systems, so it is not necessary to ensure transparency or explainability. For other, more risky decision processes, such as medical diagnoses in healthcare, investment decisions in the financial industry, and safety-critical systems in autonomous automobiles, the stakes are much higher. As such, the AI used in those systems should be explainable, transparent, and understandable to be trusted, reliable, and consistent.

Figure 11 Summarises the benefits of Explainable artificial intelligence (XAI) and Figure 12 shows the advancement of (XAI).

Figure 11 – Benefits of Explainable artificial intelligence (XAI)

Figure 12 – Advancement of Explainable artificial intelligence (XAI) Source: DARPA[60]

3 STATE-OF-THE-ART ANALYSIS

In this chapter a state of the art of expert systems is provided, identifying, analysing, and comparing their characteristics. Comparative analysis of process modelling management tools including data analytics and visualizations is also provided giving an overview of weaknesses and strengths. For each tool the features, compatibility, activity, open-Source information, analytics, and visualisations are summarised. A comparative analysis of Artificial Intelligence and machine learning is also provided.

3.1 EXPERT SYSTEM - PROCESS MODELLING AND MANAGEMENT – COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS

3.1.1 OVERVIEW

All the tools that will be used in our final product, do not differ from a practical process, however they offer added speed and convenience for users, thus speeding up decision-making. The purpose of Machine learning is to allow a system to interpret information from the past or present and use that information to make predictions or decisions about known and unknown future class labels. The term “learning” refers to the process of extracting useful patterns from unstructured data. The three types of algorithms used in machine learning are supervised learning, unsupervised learning, and reinforcement learning. In supervised learning patterns are inferred from the labelled input file, which aids in the prediction of outcomes from unexpected results. These tools depict the supervised machine learning workflow. Building, evaluating, and tuning the model, and then deploying it getting back predictions are all part of the supervised machine learning workflow. On the other hand, unsupervised learning uses machine learning algorithms to analyse and cluster unlabelled data sets. These algorithms discover hidden patterns in data without the need for human intervention. Unsupervised learning models are used for three main directions: clustering, association, and dimensionality reduction. In conclusion, in Supervised Learning, the goal is to generate formula based on input and output values. In Unsupervised Learning, we find an association between input values and group them. In Reinforcement Learning an agent learn through delayed feedback by interacting with the environment.

3.1.2 PROCESS MODELLING AND MANAGEMENT TOOLS

In this section, we give a detailed perspective of the tools used for the process modelling stage, plus the tools for managing the whole expert system.

SpiffWorkflow: SpiffWorkflow is a BPMN and non-BPMN diagram application that organises business logic. Provides a graphical user interface, creates questionnaires with multiple complex paths and allows to create/modify processes without heavy technical knowledge.

SpiffWorkflow’s benefits:

- > Dynamically and programmatically create BPMN and Non-BPMN workflow models
- > Open source
- > Optional UI designer
- > Powerful API
- > Import/Export BPMN models from xml files
- > Import/Export Non-BPMN models from python classes or JSON files
- > Create custom task and executables

SpiffWorkflow’s limitations:

- > The tool can be used to create a variety of workflow patterns, but there is not capable of

scalable work of actions. Furthermore, there is not a big community for support, bugs and problem solving while that's an open-source software.

Figure 13 – SpiffWorkflow’s optional UI

Airflow[68]: provides a programmatic interface to create and manage workflows that follow the Directed Acyclic Graph (DAG) properties. Airflow is Python-based but you can execute a program irrespective of the language. For example, the first stage of your workflow must execute a R-based program to perform analysis and then a Python-based program to transfer that information to storage.

Airflow’s benefits:

- › Programmatically create workflows as Directed Acyclic Graphs (DAGs) of tasks
- › Open source
- › Powerful Dashboards
- › Import/Export workflows from python files
- › Create custom task and executables
- › Can be extended with a variety of plugins

Airflow’s limitations:

- › Airflow is based on DAG representation and doesn’t have a concept of input or output, just of flow. Better for big scalable applications that fit well with 3rd party applications.

Figure 14 – Airflow: List of DAGs

Figure 15 – Airflow: DAG structure

Figure 16 – Airflow: Gantt diagram of execution times[68]

ProcessMaker: The modeler empowers business users to design business processes in days, not months. Drag and drop tasks and decision points on to the modelling canvas, and then add in your forms, users, data connectors and more. The ProcessMaker modeler is BPMN 2.0 compliant, intuitive, and powerful. Business users can easily design elegant forms and display screens that are used in the workflows with no-code. Forms are used to capture data, display data from other systems, and design approval screens for managers to make decisions. Furthermore, can connect to existing third-party systems via API and dramatically improve the way people work. You'll generate much greater value from the same data.

ProcessMaker's benefits:

- › Dynamically create BPMN models
- › Open source (with limited features vs the paid version)
- › Powerful Dashboards
- › UI designer
- › Import/Export BPMN models from xml files
- › Create custom forms, tasks, and UI screens
- › Limited code executions on data

ProcessMaker's limitations:

- › Difficult to develop and learn all the reporting features that's a big part of the tool.

- › ProcessMaker has limited features on the free plan and paid ones starts from high pricing plans.
- › Old model user interface.

Figure 17 – ProcessMaker’s graphical interface

N8n[69]: n8n (pronounced n-eight-n) helps you to interconnect every app with an API in the world with each other to share and manipulate its data without a single line of code. It is an easy to use, user-friendly and highly customisable service, which uses an intuitive user interface for you to design your unique workflows very fast. Hosted on your server and not based in the cloud, it keeps your sensible data very secure in your own trusted database.

N8n’s benefits:

- › Dynamically and programmatically create BPMN workflow models
- › Open-source – extend through code contribution (fair-code licensed under Apache 2.0 with Commons Clause)
- › Low-code UI designer – excellent integration with 3rd party providers
- › High-code integration if needed on each step
- › Implement custom integrations

N8n’s limitations:

- › Limited already integrated 3rd party providers
- › Steep learning curve, plus the interface is not mapped as a linear process but is based on a flowchart.

Figure 18 – N8n’s graphical interface

Lightflow[70]: Lightflow is a Python 3.5+ library and command-line tool for executing workflows, composed of individual tasks, in a distributed fashion. It is based on Celery and provides task dependencies, data exchange between tasks and an intuitive description of workflows.

Lightflow’s benefits:

- › Programmatically create workflows as Directed Acyclic Graphs (DAGs) of tasks
- › Open source
- › Low-level code execution and task monitoring
- › Import/Export workflows from python files and CLI
- › Create custom task and executables

Lightflow’s limitations:

- › Poor user interface.
- › Difficult development creations until you reach a good level of knowledge.
- › Poor documentation that includes just the basics.

Pipefy: Pipefy brings customers, vendors, and partners onto the same platform as your internal team, making it easy to collaborate and track a process from start to finish. Trade chaotic to-do lists and email threads for clean, repeatable workflows.

Pipefy’s benefits:

- › Dynamically create BPMN models
- › Paid only version

- › Powerful Dashboards
- › Includes a Kanban board management method
- › Low-code/no-code process orchestration
- › Create automation tasks, forms, and integrations with 3rd party applications

Pipefy's limitations:

- › Not easy usable for non-familiar users.
- › Poor expert advice and community.
- › Best use for small projects and businesses.

Figure 19 – Pipefy: Marketing campaign example

Kissflow: Kissflow is a best-in-class BPM software that enables organisations to reinvent existing business processes for digital optimisation. Its no-code development nature allows business users to automate process flows, enforce business rules, and make ad-hoc process changes without any coding. Best of all, Kissflow is not just restricted to structured and repeatable business processes, it also supports all types of work (process, case, projects, and more). Its intuitive process stream allows stakeholders to collaborate with each other efficiently and securely.

Some of the best features of Kissflow include user-friendly dashboards, custom report templates, and advanced workflow and form design. It also integrates with other software solutions and standard productivity apps seamlessly.

Kissflow's benefits:

- › Dynamically create workflows (BPM)
- › Low-code/no-code process orchestration
- › Visual forms and Designer
- › Algorithmic task management
- › Automated workflow routing

Kissflow's limitations:

- › Paid only version and every stakeholder needs another license.
- › There are no native integrations with several popular business applications, including major CRMs and other management systems.
- › Cannot Request tracking for external stakeholders.

Pm4py: PM4Py is a software product, developed by the Fraunhofer Institute for Applied Information Technology (FIT). PM4Py is developed by the process mining group of Fraunhofer FIT. PM4Py is created with a few goals in mind, for example:

Making state-of-the-art process mining algorithms available to the public; The process mining group of Fraunhofer FIT is affiliated with the Process and Data Science group of Prof. Wil van der Aalst. Together, they are considered the world-wide leading group in process mining research. Through this connection, novel developments are integrated in PM4Py extremely fast. Furthermore, some of the developers of PM4Py have been active in process mining research for several years and published in numerous scientific venues, on various process mining topics.

Supporting Collaborations between Academia and Industry; The development team of PM4Py develops numerous related products, e.g., connectors to several different enterprise systems such as SAP, Camunda, etc., a web-service that wraps around and a scalable cloud solution. All these products allow us to integrate the core of PM4Py, i.e., state-of-the-art process mining, within industrial enterprise. This allows us to actively integrate our solutions within the day-to-day operations of industry partners. Note that, the goal of these products is to foster industry-driven research, i.e., Fraunhofer is a non-profit research institute.

Pm4py's benefits:

- › Process Mining Tool – Discovers processes from event logs
- › Filters Event Data
- › Provides statistics (e.g., throughput time, case arrival, etc.)
- › Evaluates fitness, precision, generalisation and simplicity

Pm4py's limitations:

- › The documentation of the package is being re-written and is currently lacking clarity and examples.
- › Difficult to use and connect all the available modules to create a final workflow.
- › Few functionalities regarding DFG.

BPMN.io: is an opensource web-based tooling for BPMN, DMN workflows and Forms. Provides JavaScript based packages that can be integrated to any application and help to create dynamic workflows that follow the BPMN or DMN standards.

BPMN.io's benefits:

- › Open source
- › Provides a wide variety of independent libraries
- › Provides friendly and easy to use UI tools

- › Export workflows that can be used on any application.

BPMN.io’s limitations:

- › Poor user interface that makes it difficult for users that have not use a BPMN again.
- › Best for small workflows that will be used on unexperienced users.

3.1.2.1.1 Overview

Table 4 – BPMN and Workflow tools

Tool	Documentation	Activity	Open source	Ease of use
SpiffWorkflow	Good	Active	Yes	Easy
Airflow	Well	Active	Yes	Easy
ProcessMaker	Good	Active	Yes	Medium
n8n	Good	Active	Yes*	Difficult
Lightflow	Good	Archaic	Yes	Easy
Pipefy	-	Active	No	Difficult
Kissflow	-	Active	No	Difficult
Pm4py	Well	Active	Yes	Medium
BPMN.io Tool case	Well	Active	Yes	Easy

3.2 DATA ANALYTICS AND VISUALISATIONS – COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS

3.2.1 OVERVIEW

As we already discussed in the previous section, data analysis and visualisation applications in the healthcare research sector, face sector - specific challenges. As such the tools that will be used in the platform need to be able to support certain functionalities, especially those tools that have not been natively designed around the healthcare sector.

The platforms’ application veers from this traditional process, but should still take into account the necessities and requirements in that process for they still exist in our implementation [32].

After conducting an extensive state-of-the-art analysis about the methods used for the analysis of electrophysiology, actigraphy, MRI data and hypothesis testing, we had a first in-depth discussion with the clinical partners. The results of this discussion are reported in ANNEX I :. More specifically, the methods used for the analysis of electrophysiology and actigraphy data are reported in Table 18, while the methods used for the analysis of MRI data are reported in Table 19. Finally, Table 20 reports some general methods, which are used for statistical analyses.

3.2.2 TOOLS USED FOR DATA PROCESSING AND ANALYTICS

In this section, we present some libraries and tools used for statistical analyses, hypothesis testing, and analyses of neuroimaging and electrophysiological data.

3.2.2.1 General Tools/Libraries used for Data Processing, Statistical Analysis, and Hypothesis Testing

NumPy: NumPy is an open-source Python library providing a multidimensional array object along with array-aware functions that operate on it [71]. This library has been used as a foundation, over which other libraries have been created including scikit-learn, SciPy, statsmodels, Matplotlib, etc.

NumPy's Benefits:

- › Through NumPy the user has the ability to have access to specific elements of arrays via indexing. In addition, NumPy offers the functionality of broadcasting, meaning that the dimensions of the arrays may differ. Also, the NumPy library provides the user the opportunity to apply reduction operations along one or more axes. Operations include amongst others the summation, mean, etc.
- › Also, the NumPy Python library offers the opportunity to the users to apply statistics, including order statistics, averages and variances, correlations, and computation of histograms. In terms of the order statistics, one can compute the minimum, maximum, range of values (maximum – minimum), q-th percentile of the data, etc. When it comes to the correlation functions supported by the NumPy library, one compute the Pearson product-moment correlation coefficients, the Cross-correlation of two 1-dimensional sequences and estimate the covariance matrix given data and weights. Finally, one can compute the histogram of a dataset, the bi-dimensional histogram of two data samples, the multidimensional histogram of some data, etc.

NumPy's Limitations:

- › One limitation of NumPy is the fact that there is not a wide range of implementations for pure statistical purposes. Since statistical analyses comprise a fundamental part of the MES-CoBraD project, we intend to use the SciPy and statsmodels libraries in Python, which are presented in detail in the following sections.

Pandas: Pandas is an open-source Python library used for working with structure datasets pertinent to statistics, finances, and many other fields [72]. Functionalities offered by the Pandas library include among others: handling missing data, operations between different datasets (add, concatenation, etc.), access to specific columns, rows, group data by identifiers, etc. Below we mention some of the advantages and limitations of this library, which will be used throughout the MES-CoBraD project.

Pandas Benefits:

- › In medical data, the phenomenon of missing values is widely known. In Pandas, one can deal with missing values by using the *dropna* and *fillna* methods. Specifically, the *fillna* method is equipped with some interpolation methods to propagate values forward and backward, which is really important in time series data. The same functionality is offered via the method called *reindex*.
- › In statistical data analysis problems, one simple phenomenon is to group data by some identifiers and then apply aggregations, transformations, or visualisations. Similar to SQL, one can use the method *groupby* in the Pandas library, in order to group data based on some characteristics. Also, the user may use the *describe* method, in order to get the descriptive statistics of a specific column, row, etc.
- › Similar to SQL, one can combine, merge, or join related datasets.

- › Moreover, one can compute correlations via the Pandas library, including the Pearson correlation, Spearman rank correlation, and Kendall Tau correlation. It is worth mentioning that the user may create also his/her own correlations via a callable function. The correlations can be computed between two Series, DataFrames, or columns.

Pandas Limitations:

- › As it is highlighted in the documentation, *pandas* may not be the ideal tool for all the situations. For instance, if one works with very large datasets and a tool like PostgreSQL fits the needs and requirements of the project, then this tool may be the right choice. What is also worth mentioning is the fact that the documentation recommends the usage of other libraries, including *Dask*, which can operate more efficiently with larger datasets in parallel.
- › Although using the Pandas library, one can deal with missing values, the methods supported by the library are not always ideal when dealing with patient data.

DASK: Dask is a Python library used for parallel computing [73], [74]. This library consists of two parts, namely the dynamic task scheduling, which is optimised for computation, and the big data collections, which aim to extend the capabilities and utilities provided by other libraries, such as NumPy, Pandas, and more.

DASK's Benefits:

- › Dask arrays implement most of the NumPy utilities, including reduction along axes, arithmetic and scalar mathematics, slicing, linear algebra, and many more. In addition, Dask Array provides the capability to compute on arrays larger than memory. This is achieved by using blocked algorithms.
- › Dask can use multiple threads or processes on a single machine, or a cluster of machines to process data in parallel. The Dask DataFrame provided many utilities offered via the Pandas library, including pearson correlation, drop duplicates, row-wise selections, and many more.

DASK's Limitations:

- › Some of the functions provided by the NumPy library are not available in Dask Arrays which may narrow down the available option for the users. For instance, utilities via the module `numpy.linalg`, operations like *sort* or *tolist*, and more are not available via the Dask library.
- › Dask DataFrame does not implement all the functionalities provided via the Pandas library. For example, setting a new index from an unsorted column is expensive and as a consequence performing operations like `groupby-apply` and `join` on unsorted columns is expensive too.

SciPy: SciPy [75] constitutes an open-source Python library offering a wide number of algorithms for many problems, including optimisation, integration, interpolation, eigenvalue problems, algebraic equations, differential equations, signal or image processing, etc. SciPy started in the year 2001 and throughout the years it has become one of the most famous libraries due to the variety of possibilities it offers to the user. Moreover, SciPy is built upon NumPy, while it has been used in other libraries, including scikit-learn. In addition, several packages are available through SciPy, which will be mentioned in detail below. The benefits of SciPy rendering it a useful library for the implementation of the requirements of the MES-CoBraD project are as follows:

SciPy's Benefits:

- › One of the packages of SciPy, which is pertinent to the MES-CoBraD project, is undoubtedly the *signal* package. Specifically, this package is focused on signal processing and basic linear systems theory. It includes among others: convolutions, splines, filters, peak finding, spectral analysis, etc.
- › The *fft* package is also highly related to the MES-CoBraD project, since it implements Fast Fourier Transforms, including 1-D, 2, and N-D discrete Fourier transforms, Discrete Cosine Transforms, Discrete Sine Transforms, and the Fast Hankel Transform.
- › The *stats* package includes probability distributions, summary and frequency statistics, correlations functions and statistical tests, etc. Regarding statistical tests, which will be used extensively in the MES-CoBraD platform, some typical examples are the following: t-test, Mann-Whitney U rank test, Wilcoxon signed-rank test, Kruskal-Wallis H-test, etc. In terms of the frequency statistics, one can plot cumulative frequency histograms, and more, while with regards to summary statistics, mean, variance, kurtosis, skewness, etc. can be computed. Some of the available correlation functions are the point biserial, Spearman, Pearson, etc. which return the correlation value along with the p-value (used for test significance).
- › SciPy may also be used for image processing via the package called *ndimage*. It is used mainly in medical and biological imaging, where images of high dimensionality need to be analysed. This package offers some of the following functionalities: linear and non-linear filtering, i.e., Gaussian, median, Sobel filter, etc., region labelling and processing, B-spline interpolation, etc.

SciPy's Limitations:

- › To the best of our knowledge, one disadvantage of SciPy is the fact that it does not support multiple tests for hypothesis testing and consequently the correction of p-values. This functionality is offered by another Python library called *statsmodels*, which will be presented in detail below.

Scikit-learn: Scikit-learn [76] is an open-source Python library providing a wide number of functionalities, including classification or regression algorithms, clustering techniques, dimensionality reduction methods, algorithms for model selection, and methods for preprocessing the data. Scikit-learn is accessible to everyone and is built upon NumPy, SciPy, and matplotlib.

Scikit-learn's Benefits:

- › Scikit-learn provides algorithms targeting the imputation of missing values, which is a common problem in real-world datasets. Some of the algorithms offered by scikit-learn are the following, univariate-multivariate imputation, nearest neighbours imputation, etc.
- › Scikit-learn provides also functions for clustering and dimensionality reduction, such as Principal Component Analysis (PCA), t-SNE, and many more.

Scikit-learn's Limitations:

- › Although scikit-learn provides many functions which can be used for the analysis of neuroimaging and time-series data, there are libraries, such as Nilearn, MNE, etc., which are used solely for these purposes.

statsmodels: *Statsmodels* is a library for statistical and econometric analysis in Python [77]. It was started by Jonathan Taylor, as part of the SciPy library under the name *models*. It includes packages related to the Regression and Linear models, Time Series Analysis, Statistics, and more. It includes statistical models and hypothesis tests. We mention below some of the advantages and disadvantages of this library.

Statsmodels' Benefits:

- › *Statsmodels* includes the package called *tsa*, which is focused on time series analysis and offers the possibility to the user to exploit univariate autoregressive models (AR), vector autoregressive models (VAR), and univariate autoregressive moving average models (ARMA). In addition, descriptive statistics are available via this package, including autocorrelation, partial autocorrelation function, periodogram, etc. It also offers functionalities for filtering, i.e., Baxter-King bandpass filter, Hodrick-Prescott filter, etc.
- › In comparison to the SciPy library, the *statsmodels* library provides more statistical tests and tools via the package called *stats*. More specifically, the user is able to apply multiple tests for p-value correction. Some of the available methods used for testing and adjustment of p-values are the following: Bonferroni, Benjamini-Hochberg [78], Simes-Hochberg, Holm-Sidak, etc.
- › In terms of the imputation of missing values, the *statsmodels* library implements the Multiple Imputation with Chained Equations (MICE) via the module called MICE. Also, one can exploit the Bayesian Imputation using a Gaussian model.

Statsmodels' Limitations:

- › *Statsmodels* does not offer some of the functionalities offered by SciPy, i.e., multidimensional image processing, peak finding, or spectral analysis of signals. Thus, it may be used in conjunction with SciPy.

pmdarima: *pmdarima* is a Python library providing implementations of ARIMA estimators to the user [79].

pmdarima's Benefits:

- › *pmdarima* provides the R's implementation of *auto.arima* in Python. More specifically, *auto.arima* discovers automatically the optimal order of an ARIMA model. Therefore, *pmdarima* renders Python suitable for data science without requiring from the users to be familiar with the R language.
- › *pmdarima* provides several statistical tests, including CH test for seasonality, KPSS test for stationarity, OCSB test for seasonality, and PP test for stationarity. In addition, it includes some plotting functions, including autocorrelation, partial autocorrelation, and decomposition of a time series.
- › *pmdarima* provides an easy-to-read documentation with a lot of examples.

pmdarima's Limitations:

- › The *pmdarima* library provides more functionalities for time series analysis and statistical tests. However, one should not overlook that *pmdarima* provides the implementation of *auto.arima* function.

sktime: sktime constitutes a scikit-learn compatible Python library with a unified interface for machine learning with time series [80], [81].

sktime's Benefits:

- › sktime provides functionalities for time series classification, time series regression, time series clustering, time series forecasting, and time series annotation.

sktime's Limitations:

- › Both the library and the documentation are under development. Therefore, there are not so many examples for the reader/user.

Pingouin: Pingouin constitutes a Python library including some of the main statistical tests that scientists use on a daily basis [82]. It is written in Python 3 and is based mainly on Pandas and NumPy. Pingouin has an extensive documentation and also includes workflows, which help the user choose which functions/statistical tests are suitable for the user's analysis.

Pingouin's Benefits:

- › Pingouin offers a great number of functions, including ANOVA, t-test, bayes factors, multivariate tests, and many more. Similar to the *statsmodels* library, the user has the ability to apply multiple tests targeting the correction of the p-values.
- › One advantage of Pingouin over SciPy is the fact that SciPy for example returns only the T-value and the p-value. By contrast, the *t-test* function of Pingouin returns the T-value, the p-value, the degrees of freedom, the effect size (Cohen's d), the 95% confidence intervals of the difference in means, the statistical power and the Bayes Factor (BF10) of the test.

Pingouin's Limitations:

- › The *statsmodels* library offers more statistical tests and methods for multiple tests than Pingouin.
- › Pingouin is used mainly for statistical analyses, in contrast to SciPy which includes also methods to apply transforms on signals, etc.

3.2.2.2 Tools/Libraries for Processing Neuroimaging and Electrophysiology Brain data

Nitime: Nitime [83] is an open-source Python library used mainly for time-series analysis of data derived by neuroimaging experiments. Although it has been mainly developed for time-series analysis of functional Magnetic Resonance Imaging (fMRI) data, the algorithms implemented via this library can be used in other applications too. Below, we mention some of the advantages and limitations of the Nitime library.

Nitime's Benefits:

- › Through the package *nitime.algorithms*, the user is able to apply a lot of algorithms, including spectral transforms, coherency, regularised coherency, and event-related analysis. Specifically, regarding the spectral transforms, algorithms towards the calculation of a standard periodogram and cross-spectral density estimates based on both the regular and multi-taper periodograms are provided. With regards to the coherency, it corresponds to an

analog of cross-correlation calculated between two time-series in the frequency domain. For a more robust computation of coherence in the presence of small denominators, the regularised coherency is also available. In terms of the event-related analysis, a set of univariate statistics is calculated separately for the time-series in each voxel or each Region of Interest (ROI), including standard least squares estimate of the hemodynamic response function, cross-correlation between a series of events and a time-series, etc.

Nitime's Limitations:

- › Nitime is a library focusing on the implementation of advanced algorithms rather than the pre-processing stages of MRI, time-series data, etc. Thus, other libraries need to be used for the purposes of the pre-processing stage.

MNE: MNE [84] is an open-source Python library for analysing human neurophysiological data, including MEG, EEG, sEEG, ECoG, NIRS, and many more. It provides a wide number of tools, including source estimation, machine learning, encoding models, statistics, connectivity, and visualisations.

MNE's Benefits:

- › Firstly, MNE includes a wide number of functions, which are used for reading data from several file formats. For example, one can read EEG data in the following formats: BrainVision (.vhdr, .vmrk, .eeg), European data format (.edf), BioSemi data format (.bdf), General data format (.gdf), Neuroscan CNT (.cnt), and more.
- › MNE provides many functions and utilities for preprocessing data. More specifically, one can use several filters via the MNE library, including the bad-pass, low-pass, high-pass, bad-stop, and notch filtering. In addition, MNE implements algorithms for the detection and removal of artifacts. More specifically, the removal of artifacts is implemented using regression [85], signal-space projection (SSP) [86], or independent component analysis (ICA).
- › MNE also offers a full and easy-to-read documentation, which provides guidelines regarding the usage of statistical tests, hypothesis testing, and correction of the p-values after multiple tests. It implements functions for statistical analysis, including parametric statistics, mass-univariate multiple comparison correction, non-parametric (clustering) resampling methods, and computation of adjacency matrices for cluster-level statistics.

MNE's Limitations:

- › As mentioned in the documentation, one can refer to `scipy.stats` and `statsmodels` libraries in Python for more options regarding the usage of functions for statistical analysis.

YASA: YASA (Yet Another Spindle Algorithm) [87] is a Python package used for analysing polysomnographic sleep recordings. YASA is accompanied with a full and easy-to-read documentation, which includes also a lot of examples.

YASA's Benefits:

- › YASA implements algorithms targeting the event detection, including sleep spindles, slow waves and rapid eye-movements, on single or multi-channel EEG data.
- › YASA offers also some functions pertinent to spectral analysis, such as the calculation of the spectral band power, separation of the aperiodic components of the EEG power spectrum

using the IRASA method [88], computation of epoch-per-epoch non-linear features, and many more.

- › YASA provides also the functionality of the automatic sleep staging of polysomnographic data. Specifically, the automatic sleep staging function requires that the data are loaded using the MNE python library. Finally, the automatic sleep stages classification can be done using the SleepStaging class.
- › Moreover, YASA implements various hypnogram tools, such as the creation of a state-transition matrix from an hypnogram, the conversion of a string hypnogram array to an integer, and more. One can also extract sleep statistics from an hypnogram, i.e., sleep efficiency, WASO, time in bed, sleep period time, latencies of sleep stages from the beginning of the record, and many more.

YASA's Limitations:

- › YASA does not apply preprocessing steps. Thus, MNE may be used for the purposes of the preprocessing stages.

WONAMBI[89]: WONAMBI constitutes a Python library used for the analysis of EEG, ECoG, and other electrophysiology modalities.

WONAMBI's Benefits:

- › WONAMBI can read files of many formats, including European Data Format (.edf), Fieldtrip (.mat), and many others.
- › It is used for the computation of frequency analysis (spectrogram), time-frequency analysis (short-time spectrogram, Morlet wavelet).
- › WONAMBI also provides algorithms for the detection of spindles and slow waves.

WONAMBI's Limitations:

- › WONAMBI offers less algorithms than those implemented by YASA.

SleepPy: SleepPy is an open-source Python library processing multi-day streams of raw accelerometer data (X, Y, and Z) from wrist-worn wearable devices and produces sleep reports for each recording day [90].

SleepPy's Benefits:

- › One can load raw accelerometer data via an input file and then SleepPy can split them into 24-hour segments and process them. The output of the SleepPy is a table, where one can have access to the total sleep time in minutes, percentage of the major rest period during the sleep state, wake after sleep onset (WASO) in minutes, the sleep onset latency (SOL), and the number of wake bouts, which indicates the number of times the subject transitioned from sleep to wake after the first sleep state. The SleepPy library plots also a visualisation report, which will be mentioned in detail in Section 3.2.3.2.

SleepPy's Limitations:

- › SleepPy can work with data generated by the GeneActiv wrist-worn devices (GeneActiv .bin files). It can also support .csv files generated by GeneActiv's software.

PyActigraphy: PyActigraphy constitutes an open-source Python library used for actigraphy data visualization and analysis [91]. Below, we mention some of the benefits of the PyActigraphy library as well as its main limitations.

PyActigraphy's Benefits:

- › PyActigraphy provides many functionalities and utilities for reading data from many file formats. More specifically, it supports output files from:
 - Actigraph: wGT3X-BT
 - CamNtech: Actiwatch 4 and MotionWatch 8
 - Condor Instrument: ActTrust 2
 - Daqtix: Daqtometer
 - Respironics: Actiwatch 2 and Actiwatch Spectrum (plus)
 - Tempatilumi (CE Brasil)
- › PyActigraphy also implements algorithms for detecting rest periods, including Cole-Kripke's [92], Oakley's [93], Sadeh's [94], Scripps' [95], Crespo's [96], and Roenne-berg's [97] algorithms.
- › It provides also advanced signal processing functions, including Cosinor analysis [98], Detrended Fluctuation Analysis [99], [100], Functional Linear Modelling [101], Locomotor Inactivity during sleep [102], Singular Spectrum Analysis [103], and many more.

PyActigraphy's Limitations:

- › PyActigraphy package is currently under progress and many more features are expected to be implemented.

Visbrain: Visbrain [104] constitutes an open-source Python package used for both neuroimaging and electrophysiological brain data. Visbrain comes with an easy-to-read documentation and is accompanied by examples and datasets.

Visbrain's Benefits:

- › Visbrain provides functions related to signal processing. More specifically, de-trending, de-meaning, or filtering, i.e., lowpass, highpass, bandpass, bandstop, are implemented via the submodule of the Visbrain called Signal. In addition, one can extract the amplitude, phase, or power in specific power bands.
- › Via the submodule of the Visbrain library, called Sleep, one can apply time-frequency methods to the signals for computing the fourier-based spectrogram, the morlet's wavelet, and the multitaper-based Wigner spectrogram. It must be noted that the fourier-based spectrogram is implemented in SciPy, while the multitaper-based Wigner spectrogram [105] is provided via the library *Isopot*[106]. Moreover, the Visbrain library implements semi-automatic algorithms for the detection of events, such as sleep spindles, K-complexes, rapid-eye movements, slow waves, muscle twitches, and peaks.
- › Regarding the utilities offered by the submodule called *Brain*, details are given in Section

3.2.3.2.

Visbrain's Limitations:

- › As mentioned in [104], Visbrain does not provide data analysis functions, which are available in other libraries, such as SciPy, Pandas, or statsmodels.

Neuropycon: Neuropycon [107] constitutes an open-source Python library used for the analysis of multimodal brain data and provides Python-based templates pipelines for multiprocessing of MEG, EEG, functional and anatomical MRI. It is focused mainly on connectivity and graph theoretical analyses. Neuropycon contains two packages, namely the ephypype and the graphpype, which are designed for electrophysiology analysis and functional connectivity respectively.

Neuropycon's Benefits:

- › The ephypype package provides algorithms for preprocessing, cleaning by automatic removal of eyes and heart related artefacts, etc. More specifically, one can perform filtering, downsample the MEG raw data, or run an ICA algorithm, which is implemented via the MNE library. One can also compute the Power Spectral Density for each frequency band. In addition, the computation of the connectivity matrices in the frequency domain is available, since Neuropycon provides functions implemented in the MNE library.
- › The graphpype package can be exploited for the computation of graph metrics for multiple modalities, including modular partitions.
- › Neuropycon can import raw MEG/EEG data, time-series, fMRI data, and connectivity matrices.
- › Neuropycon provides also the utilities for conducting group-level statistical analyses in a lot of ways. The graphpype package offers functions for calculating statistics on connectivity and graph data, including paired and unpaired t-test, binomial, Mann-Whitney, etc.

Neuropycon's Limitations:

- › One may face difficulties in creating workflows and thus choose other libraries for conducting their analyses.

Nilearn: Nilearn is a Python library aiming to simplify the use of scikit-learn in terms of neuroimaging [108]. Nilearn provides statistical and machine learning tools with instructive documentation. Also, it leverages the scikit-learn Python library for multivariate statistics with applications, such as predictive modelling, classification, decoding, or connectivity analysis.

Nilearn's Benefits:

- › Nilearn analyses fMRI data by employing Generalised Linear models. Nilearn provides also functions for setting up first- and second-level models, performing t-tests, multiple comparisons correction and thresholding. Nilearn outputs html reports, which include all the analyses conducted. These functions are available in the package *nilearn.glm*.
- › Some additional functionalities provided by the Nilearn library are the following: smoothing images by applying a Gaussian filter, computing the mean of the images over time or the 4th dimension (for fMRI), resampling an image to a template, independent component analysis of fMRI, and many more.

- › In addition, Nilearn comes with an easy-to-read documentation accompanied by a lot of examples pertinent to the advanced statistical analysis of brain images.

Nilearn's Limitations:

- › Nilearn does not provide support for reading MRI data. For this purpose, the Nibabel library will be used.

Dipy: Diffusion imaging in Python (Dipy) [109] is an open-source Python library used for the analysis of diffusion magnetic resonance imaging (dMRI) data. Dipy is built upon NumPy, SciPy, Nibabel and libraries for visualisations, including Matplotlib and Python-VTK.

Dipy's Benefits:

- › Dipy includes several methods for statistical analysis, reconstruction, registration, denoising, and preprocessing. More specifically, several metrics for streamlines are available in the Dipy library, including spline interpolation, curvature and torsion calculations along a streamline, the computation of the average length and standard deviation of the streamlines generated after the fiber tracking procedure, and many more. One can also remove the background and keep parts that are in the brain by using the function called *median_tsu*. In addition, one can denoise images by using Non-Local Means (NLMEANS), Local PCA via empirical thresholds, the Marcenko-Pastur PCA algorithm. Also, examples about the suppression of the Gibbs artefacts of MR images are provided. Patch2Self [110], which is a self-supervised learning method for denoising DWI data, is also implemented.

Dipy's Limitations:

- › No significant limitations.

Antropy: Antropy is a Python 3 package providing several time-efficient algorithms for computing the complexity of time-series. It can be used to extract features from EEG signals. Antropy was created and is maintained by Raphael Vallat.

Antropy's benefits:

- › It implements various specialised functions regarding entropy and fractal dimension, including permutation entropy, spectral entropy, Hjorth mobility and complexity, number of zero-crossings, Petrosian fractal dimension, katz fractal dimension etc.

Antropy's limitations:

- › It can extract features from electroencephalography signals but doesn't have much more usability than that.
- › As mentioned in the documentation, the results need to be double-checked.

UK Biobank accelerometer analysis: UK biobank accelerometer analysis [111]–[114] is a tool used for the extraction of information from large accelerometer datasets. It can be installed via Python and also needs Java to be installed.

Benefits:

- › This package can process data from raw GENEActiv. Bin files, raw Actigraph .gt3x files (both versions 1 and 2), raw gzipped CSV files. Moreover, this package provides the opportunity for

processing hundreds of accelerometer files.

- › Questions such as how much time is spent in sleep, sedentary behaviour, or doing physical activity are answered via this package.
- › This package provides functions for classifying different activity types. Some examples of activities are the following: sleep, sit/stand, vehicle, walking, mixed activity, and bicycling.

Limitations:

- › Limited support for various data formats.

PyEEG: PyEEG constitutes an open-source Python module used for extracting features from EEG data [115].

PyEEG's benefits:

- › One can compute the following features using the PyEEG library:
 - Power Spectral Intensity (PSI) and Relative Intensity Ratio (RIR)
 - Petrosian Fractal Dimension (PFD)
 - Higuchi Fractal Dimension (HFD)
 - Hjorth mobility and complexity
 - Spectral Entropy (Shannon's entropy of RIRs)
 - SVD Entropy, etc.

PyEEG's Limitations:

- › PyEEG does not include functions for reading data. Thus, other libraries must be exploited for this purpose.

Eeglib: eeglib is an open-source Python library used for feature extraction from EEG signals and is based on sliding windows [116].

Eeglib's Benefits:

- › Eeglib can import data from three different formats, namely csv files, EDF and NumPy arrays.
- › Regarding the preprocessing stage, the user is able to apply bandpass filter, Independent Component Analysis (ICA) [117], and z-scores normalisation to the raw EEG data.
- › One can also compute the Fast Fourier Transform, Discrete Wavelet Transform, Power Spectral Density, Band Power, Hjorth Parameters, Detrended Fluctuation Analysis, Sample Entropy, and many more.

Eeg's Limitations:

- › MNE imports data from more file formats and implements more algorithms than eeglib.

NiBabel: NiBabel is a Python library used for having access to neuroimaging file formats [118].

NiBabel's Benefits:

- › NiBabel provides access to the most common medical and neuroimaging file formats,

including ANALYZE (plain, SPM99, SPM2 and later), GIFTI, NIFTI1, NIFTI2, MINC1, MINC2, MGH and ECAT as well as Philips PAR/REC.

- › The user can have full or selective access to head information. Access to the image data is made available via the NumPy library.
- › Nibabel comes with a full and easy-to-read documentation with a lot of examples.

NiBabel's Limitations:

- › Very limited support for DICOM.

BIOPAC Systems Actigraphy: It is a toolkit used for sleep and activity analysis. It also correlates activity levels with GPS positioning providing in this way more information. It is a toolkit, which is not freely available and one must pay for having access to it.

BIOPAC Systems Actigraphy Benefits:

- › Regarding sleep analysis, one can compute the sleep onset, percentage of wake, sleep end, wake after sleep onset (WASO), total sleep period length, sleep bouts, sleep time, wake bouts, percentage of sleep, mean sleep bout, wake time, and mean wake bout.
- › In terms of the activity analysis, one can calculate the total low activity time, waking low activity time, total high activity time, total medium activity time, and more.

BIOPAC Systems Actigraphy Limitations:

- › It is not open-source and thus cannot be used.

Koneksa Actigraphy: It is a platform, where one can perform analysis, i.e., sleep and activity analysis, on raw accelerometer-based datasets.

Koneska Actigraphy Benefits:

- › Regarding sleep analysis, one can compute the total sleep time, sleep efficiency, and the number of wake bouts.
- › With regards to the activity analysis, one can compute the activity intensity level, count per worn epoch, etc.

Koneksa Actigraphy Limitations:

- › It is not open-source and thus cannot be used.

MotionWare: It is a software used for the analysis of sleep, circadian rhythm, and physical activity. It is not freely available.

MotionWare's Benefits:

- › MotionWare can import data captured with MotionWatch 8, MotionWatch Rugged, or PRO-Diary.
- › Regarding sleep analysis, one can compute the sleep latency, WASO, Sleep Efficiency, and Sleep Fragmentation.

- › It includes Non-Parametric Circadian Rhythm Analysis (NPCRA).
- › With regards to the analysis of the activity, one can calculate the amount of time spent within each activity category, the vigorous/moderate/low/sedentary activity time, the empty/non-zero/zero time, and more.

MotionWare's Limitations:

- › It is not open-source and thus cannot be used.

Actiware: Actiware is a software package used for the analysis of data derived by Actiwatch models. Several statistics are available through the Actiware software and are mentioned below.

Actiware's Benefits:

- › Regarding activity statistics, one can compute the total activity count, average activity count per minute, average activity count per epoch, standard deviation of activity count for epochs during an interval, and maximum activity count.
- › With regards to the sleep/wake statistics, one can compute the sleep time, percentage sleep, number of sleep bouts, average sleep bout, onset latency, snooze time, sleep efficiency, wake after sleep onset, wake time, percentage wake, number of wake bouts, and averaging wake bouts.
- › Regarding the mobility statistics, one can compute the immobile time, percentage immobile, number of immobile bouts, average immobile bouts, number of 1-minute immobile bouts, percentage of 1-minute immobile bouts, mobile time, percentage mobile time, number of mobile bouts, average mobile bouts, fragmentation index.

Actiware's Limitations:

- › It is a closed-source package.

MedPy: MedPy is a Python library used for reading, writing, and manipulating medical images. It includes image filters and methods for extracting features from images, which can be later used along with the scikit-learn library.

MedPy's Benefits:

- › MedPy provides the opportunity for having access to medical images being in the following formats: ITK MetaImage, Neuroimaging Informatics Technology Initiative (NIFTI), DICOM, Medical Imaging NetCDF, etc.
- › One can also compute the mutual information between two images or the distance between histograms. These functionalities are offered via the module `medpy.metric`.
- › One can apply filters to medical images via the module `medpy.filter`. Also, this module provides the opportunity for image smoothing, hough transform, etc.
- › MedPy includes functions for extracting intensity based features.

MedPy's Limitations:

- › Less algorithms than the `nipy` library.

Skimage: scikit-image is an open-source Python library used for image processing [119].

Skimage's Benefits:

- › There is a forum, where users can ask questions regarding this library.
- › This package has an excellent documentation including examples about the implementation of the algorithms provided via the package.
- › This package provides algorithms for the detection of edges and lines, geometrical transformations and registration, filtering and restoration, detection of features and objects, segmentation of objects, and more.

Skimage's Limitations:

- › Skimage does not provide many functionalities used solely for medical images.

OpenCV: OpenCV is a library available in C++, Java, and Python and is used for image processing. We mention below some benefits and limitations of using this library.

OpenCV's Benefits:

- › OpenCV provides an easy-to-read documentation, which includes a great number of examples.
- › Via the OpenCV library, one can apply filters to smooth images, apply the two common morphological operators, i.e., erosion and dilation, apply transformations, including the Canny edge detector, Hough Line/Circle Transform, and Affine Transformations, and more. In addition, the OpenCV library provides the functionalities of histogram equalisation, calculation, and comparison. Moreover, one can find contours, create bounding boxes and circles for contours, and many more.
- › OpenCV provides a forum, where one could seek for help, if he/she faces difficulties using this library.

OpenCV's Limitations:

- › In contrast to other libraries, which provide functionalities solely for medical images, this library provides more general functionalities.

Fmriprep: fmriprep [120] is a functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) data preprocessing pipeline performing basic preprocessing steps, i.e., coregistration, normalisation, unwrapping, etc. Using many neuroimaging softwares, i.e., FSL, ANTs, FreeSurfer, and AFNI.

Fmriprep's Benefits:

- › It has an easy-to-read documentation and is straightforward to use with only one line of code. Thus, it saves time.
- › The user is not obliged to install the packages used by fmriprep, i.e., FSL, ANTs, FreeSurfer, since the developers of the fmriprep have released a docker container, which includes everything needed for executing the pipeline.

- › There is a forum called Neurostars, where one could ask for help regarding the usage of the fmriprep package.

Fmriprep's Limitations:

- › Although fmriprep is extremely easy to use, it is not easily customisable. For instance, if one wants to change the steps of the pipeline, it may be difficult. In this case, the nipy library is highly recommended.

Nipype: Nipype [121] constitutes an open-source Python package providing interfaces to existing neuroimaging software, including ANTs, FSL, MIPAV (Medical Image Processing, Analysis, and Visualisation), etc.

Nipype's Benefits:

- › Nipype has an easy-to-read documentation at the following website: <https://nipype.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>.
- › Due to the fact that it provides access to a lot of neuroimaging softwares, including, AFNI, ANTs, BrainSuite, BRU2NII, Convert3D, Camino, Camino-TrackVis, CAT12, Connectome Mapper (CMP), dcm2nii, DCMStack, Diffusion Toolkit, DIPY, DTITK, Elastix, FreeSurfer, FSL, MeshFix, MINC Toolkit, MIPAV, MNE, MRTrix, Nifty, Nilearn, NiPy, Nitime, PETPVC, QuickShear, SEM Tools, Statistical Parametric Mapping (SPM), VistaSoft, Connectome Workbench, and 3D Slicer, one can apply a great number of algorithms to the data and compare the algorithms provided by the aforementioned packages.
- › Nipype includes also a forum, where one can ask for help, if he/she faces difficulties using the software package.

Nipype's Limitations:

- › No significant limitations.

NLTools: NLTools is a Python package used for the analysis of neuroimaging data. We mention below some of the benefits and limitations of this package.

NLTools' Benefits:

- › NLTools provides modules for reading the neuroimaging data, applying statistical analyses, downloading datasets, applying masks, plotting, and simulating multivariate data.
- › Some examples of functions and algorithms provided via the NLTools library are the following: identification of spikes from time series data or fMRI time series data, getting the mean or median of each voxel or image, running a mass-univariate regression across voxels, where three types of regression can be run, including Standard OLS, Robust OLS, and ARMA, applying spatial smoothing, calculating one sample t-test across each voxel, performing convolutions using an arbitrary function, computing correlations, adjusting the p-values using the Holm-Bonferroni method, building the Design Matrix, and many more.

NLTools' Limitations:

- › No significant limitations.

ActiLife: ActiLife is ActiGraph's premier actigraphy data analysis software platform and is not freely available.

Actilife's Benefits:

- › One can calculate sleep statistics, including onset, sleep latency, amount of sleep, and sleep efficiency.
- › This software can also detect bouts of physical activity, occurrences, time spent within bouts, and total count levels. Details about a subject's sedentary behaviour can also be computed. It is worth mentioning that ActiLife can classify physical activity intensity using 10 available cut point sets.
- › Heart Rate Analysis is also performed by calculating heart rate variables, including ADL heart rate, average active heart rate, heart rate delta, etc.

Actilife's Limitations:

- › It is not freely available.

FreeSurfer: FreeSurfer is an open source neuroimaging toolkit for processing, analysing, and visualising human brain MR images.

FreeSurfer's Benefits:

- › FreeSurfer can be used for the analysis and visualisation of structural, functional, and diffusion neuroimaging data from cross-sectional and longitudinal studies.
- › FreeSurfer provides the algorithm of recon-all, which includes 31 processing stages, including motion correction and conform, skull strip, spherical mapping/registration, and many more.
- › FreeSurfer supports the functionality of SAMSEG, which is a tool to robustly segment dozens of brain structures from head MRI scans without preprocessing.

FreeSurfer's Limitations:

- › The running time of recon-all may range from some hours to days.

NeuroDesk¹: NeuroDesk constitutes a flexible, scalable and browser-based data analysis environment for reproducible neuroimaging.

NeuroDesk's Benefits:

- › NeuroDesk provides analyses of electrophysiological and neuroimaging data, including functional imaging, hippocampus, image reconstruction/registration/segmentation, structural imaging, spine, statistics, etc.
- › With regards to the electrophysiological data, NeuroDesk provides access to brainstorm,

¹ <https://www.neurodesk.org/>

eeglab, fieldtrip, and MNE.

- › Regarding neuroimaging data, the FreeSurfer is supported. All the analyses supported by FreeSurfer, including visualisation approaches, are provided in NeuroDesk.
- › 3D Slicer is also supported.
- › Documentation for using docker containers is supported.
- › NeuroDesk applications can be also exploited in Google Colab.

NeuroDesk's Limitations:

- › No significant limitations.

3.2.3 TOOLS USED FOR DATA VISUALISATIONS

In this section the tools that can be used for data visualizations are presented. It's divided in three subsections. In the first tools for general visualisations are shown and in the next two we dive deeper with specialised tools and frameworks for visualisations of EEG and MRI data.

3.2.3.1 General Visualisations

AmCharts: AmCharts is a JavaScript library for data visualisation that can work with modern web development toolkits like React, Angular and Vue out of the box. Of course, it can be used in plain JavaScript apps. It was created in 2006 by Antanas Marcelionis as a side project and is maintained by a small team spread out across the globe. Developer products are mainly aimed at web and application developers, looking for a way to add data visualization capabilities to the products they are developing. AmCharts Charts offers a wide variety of chart types such as line, pie, donut, column, bar, area, etc. It, also, provides an addon for full-fledged interactive maps called amCharts Maps.

AmCharts' benefits:

- › Amcharts offers any chart type that may be needed and it also includes date based charts that can be important for the MES-CoBraD project.
- › It works out of the box on all modern web browsers, even some older versions of Internet Explorer.
- › There is extensive documentation, huge configuration and customisation options and integration with the most popular web frameworks.
- › It is an open source and there are various pricing options. For the needs of our project it can be used for free (there will be an amCharts logo present at the corner of the charts)

AmCharts' limitations:

- › It can be slower than other charting frameworks available, especially when a large number of datapoints is involved.

D3.js[122]: D3 is a JavaScript library for manipulating documents based on data. It uses technologies such as HTML, SVG, and CSS. It supports a large number of visualizations, from bar charts and lines to maps and animations.

D3.js' benefits:

- › Many powerful visualization components
- › Data-driven DOM manipulation
- › It has good documentation and a large set of examples

D3.js' limitations:

- › It has generally complex syntax, so it is not suitable for beginners

Chart.js: Chart is a simple and flexible JavaScript library for visualizations.

Chart.js' benefits:

- › Offers all basic types of charts
- › Chart interactivity
- › Most of the times rendering is fast as charts are rendered on canvas elements

Chart.js' limitations:

- › Rendering can become slow for large datasets especially if they are not sorted and consistent

3.2.3.2 EEG and MRI Visualisations

MNE-Python: MNE is an open-source Python module for processing, analysis, and visualization of functional neuroimaging data (electroencephalography(EEG), magnetoencephalography(MEG), sEEG, EcoG, and fNIRS)[84]. It reimplements common M/EEG processing algorithms in pure Python. In addition, it also implements new algorithms, proposed and published by the MNE-Python authors.

MNE's benefits:

- › MNE can handle various types of file formats and it is suitable for processing and analysis of electroencephalography data that is one of the focuses of the project.
- › It can produce a variety of visualisations. Some examples include signal traces and butterfly plots, scalp topographies, arrow maps, joint plots, 3D field maps, etc.
- › Has function to export interactive HTML summaries of the data.

MNE's limitations:

- › It seems to be more tailored for MEG users than EEG users.

Visbrain[104]: Visbrain is an open-source Python 3 package dedicated to brain signals visualization. It is under heavy development and many functionalities are frequently added to the package. It is based on top of VisPy, a Python package providing high-performance 2D and 3D visualization by leveraging the computational power of the graphics card and PyQt, a set of Python bindings for The Qt Company's Qt application framework and is distributed under the 3-Clause BSD license. Visbrain consists of two levels of abstraction: (1) objects which represent highly configurable neuro-oriented visual primitives (3D brain, sources connectivity, etc.) and (2) graphical user interfaces for higher level interactions. Currently there are 4 graphical user interfaces: Brain for visualisations involving a MNI brain, Sleep for polysomnographic data visualization and sleep analysis, Signal for 72 visualisations of multi-dimensional datasets and figures for constructing figure layouts.

Visbrain's benefits:

- › It offers many functionalities that will be needed for the MES-CoBraD project. It has 18 objects (as of now) that are highly configurable (for example: brain object, hypnogram object, connectivity object, etc.) and offers graphical user interfaces to interact with these objects.
- › Additional implemented objects include time-frequency maps, phase-amplitude coupling comodulograms, topographic representations of EEG data, etc.
- › It is in constant development, so new features and functionalities are frequently added to the package.
- › Since it is in development there is a growing community that can help with issues and make our work easier.
- › The Brain gui is especially useful for the needs of MES-CoBraD. Its main features include templates for zoom and rotation of the volume, control of the transparency and appearance, addition and connection of sources to the scene, display of brain sections, volumes, time-series, vectors, etc.

WONAMBI: Wonabi is a Python package for the analysis of EEG, EcoG and other electrophysiology modalities. Allows for visualization of the data and sleep stage scoring in a GUI. Provides automatic detectors for spindles and slow waves.

WONAMBI benefits

- › WONAMBI gives the user the ability to plot 3D images and surfaces from freesurfer.
- › Multiple channel groups can be created. This is useful because each group can have its own reference, filter settings, color, etc. Moreover, montages can be created, saved and loaded. Montages are channel snapshots that are stored in .json format.

YASA[87]: Yasa is a command-line sleep analysis toolbox in Python. Some of its functions are spectral and hypnogram analyses, event detection (for example, rapid eye movements) on multi-channel EEG data and automatic sleep staging of polysomnography data. It was created and maintained by Raphael Varrat.

YASA benefits:

- › YASA can produce a wide variety of visualisations based on its functionalities. These include overlays of detected spindles on EEG data, spectrograms, hypnograms, sleep stage probability transition matrices, topographic plots, etc.

Sensor Motion: Sensor Motion is a python package for analysing sensor-collected human motion data that is developed and maintained by Simon Ho. It allows the user to extract human motion data, such as gait/walking dynamics, directly from accelerometer signals. Additionally, the package allows for the calculation of physical activity (PA) or moderate-to-vigorous physical activity (MVPA) counts. It, also, has a plot module that implements wrappers around various matplotlib pyplot plot calls.

Sensor Motion's benefits:

- › It offers functions for analysing time-series and accelerometer data. It can be especially useful

for filtering signals and finding peaks or valleys in them. Since it contains a plot module, it simplifies the creation of filter frequency response curves and general signal plots over time.

Sensor Motion's limitations:

- › It is developed and maintained by just one person so it is feature light and does not have the support of bigger packages.

PyEMD: PyEMD is a Python implementation of Empirical Mode Decomposition (EMD) and its variations. One of the most popular expansion is Ensemble Empirical Mode Decomposition (EEMD), which utilises an ensemble of noise-assisted executions.

PyEMD's benefits:

- › PyEMD contains a visualization helper that is used for quick and simple result visualization. It can plot and show intrinsic mode functions from a decomposed signal and instantaneous frequencies for the provided IMFs.

Nilearn[108]: Nilearn enables approachable and versatile analyses of brain volumes. It provides statistical and machine-learning tools, with instructive documentation & open community. It supports general linear model (GLM) based analysis and leverages the scikit-learn[123] Python toolbox for multivariate statistics with applications such as predictive modelling, classification, decoding, or connectivity analysis.

Nilearn benefits:

- › Nilearn has a lot of plotting functions to plot brain volumes. It can plot anatomical images, do echo-planar imaging (EPI), produce glass brain visualisations, plot network nodes (markers), etc. It offers various display modes and gives the scientist the ability to add cuts to specific locations. It, also, supports surface plotting
- › A nice benefit of Nilearn is that it has functions for making interactive plots that can be viewed in a web browser.

PySurfer: PySurfer is a Python library and application for visualizing brain imaging data. It is specifically useful for plotting data on a three-dimensional mesh representing the cortical surface of the brain. It offers a wide variety of visualisations ranging from simple to complex tasks. The aim of the library is to enable the user to create visualisations that are both scientifically accurate and beautiful.

PySurfer's benefits:

- › It has a large collection of visualisations that can be really useful for the needs of the project. These visualisations include plotting rgb values on brain surface, displaying fMRI activation and volume, plotting transparent brain, generating surface labels and displaying conjunction maps, ROI values, etc.
- › Gives the user the ability to animate the brain or create a movie from MEG inverse solution and save them as well as showing different brain views and saving set of views. These features add some form of interaction of the user with the results.

Scikit-image[119]: Scikit-image is a collection of algorithms for image processing. It is available free of charge and free of restriction. It builds on `scipy.ndimage` to provide a versatile set of image processing routines in Python and is designed to interoperate with both NumPy and SciPy. The scikit-image library is developed by its community.

Scikit-image's benefits:

- › It offers a lot of processing options regarding images that will certainly benefit the project. Examples include manipulating exposure and colour channels, get edges and lines from images, filtering, object and feature detection, segmentation, etc.
- › It uses NumPy arrays so it is expected to have efficient processing and be generally fast.
- › It incorporates most of the scikit-learn algorithms, namely PCA, clustering, segmentation, ensemble methods, various supervised and unsupervised algorithms, etc.
- › Since it is an open-source project with huge following it has great documentation and support.

Scikit-image's limitations:

- › Does not support video processing as OpenCV does. This will not be a problem though because we will use it as an image processing only library for the project needs.

OpenCV-Python: OpenCV is the Python API of OpenCV[124]. OpenCV is an open-source BSD-licensed library that includes several hundreds of computer vision algorithms. It is the biggest and most used library for image processing.

OpenCV Benefits:

- › Can be used for various computer vision and image processing tasks, such as filtering, background noise removal, object and face detection
- › It has visualisation capabilities, can load, save and show images and even offers a 3D Visualiser module.
- › OpenCV-Python is fast since it's a Python wrapper for the original OpenCV implementation that is written in C/C++
- › Has the ability to support video processing unlike scikit-image
- › Implements more than 2500 algorithms

DIPY[109]: DIPY is a 3D/4D+ imaging library. It contains generic methods for spatial normalisation, signal processing, machine learning, statistical analysis and visualization of medical images. Additionally, it contains specialised methods for computational anatomy including diffusion, perfusion and structural imaging.

DIPY's benefits:

- › Has many functions for visualisations. These include brain volume slicing, visualising bundles and metrics on bundles and an interface to access many of the capabilities available in the Visualization Toolkit framework (VTK) but tailored to the needs of structural and diffusion imaging
- › It's free and open source, implements many state-of-the-art algorithms and offers high

performance as many algorithms are implemented in Python

Nipype[125]: Nipype is a Python project that provides a uniform interface to existing neuroimaging software and facilitates interaction between these packages within a single workflow. It is an open-source, community-developed initiative under the umbrella of NiPy.

Nipype's benefits:

- › It allows for easy interaction with tools from different packages, so it gives a lot of flexibility on the tools used and encourages the exploration of various algorithms
- › Helps create a collaborative platform for neuroimaging software development by combining processing steps from different software packages into new workflows or reusing existing steps from old workflows.
- › It can be used to visualize the workflows so it's easier for the users to understand the flow of the steps taken and make research reproducible

BrainVISA[126]: BrainVISA is a neuroimaging software platform for mass data analysis. It is more of a set of tools than a single software. When using BrainVISA the software that runs is called Axon. Axon provides a graphical user environment, and integrates the different tools and data to make them available for end users. Visualization and interactive edition of data is already integrated in the Axon user interface. Axon can also facilitate the customisation and creation of new specialised visualization tools. Most of them make use of Anatomist, a library of data visualizations and high-level neuroimaging graphical components, specifically its Python adaptation, PyAnatomist. Anatomist offers a framework for interactive visualization of neuroimaging data.

BrainVISA's benefits:

- › Through PyAnatomist there are many visualization options. The user can load and view objects, change the camera parameters (zoom, orientation, etc), view meshes, use custom colour palettes and even do fusion between two volumes
- › BrainVISA is a modular environment, so it is possible to install, use and build on a subset of the tools.

Visualization Toolkit (VTK)[127]: The Visualization Toolkit is an open source software for manipulating and displaying scientific data. It comes with state-of-the-art tools for 3D rendering, a suite of widgets for 3D interaction, and extensive 2D plotting capability. VTK is part of Kitware's collection of supported platforms for software development.

VTK's benefits:

- › VTK provides various tools for 3D rendering and image processing
- › It can produce visualizations of scalar, vector and tensor fields as well as volume data (for example MRI scans) that will be the focus of our research. It, also, offers mesh and polygon processing, image analysis for both 2D and 3D images.

3D Slicer: 3D Slicer is a research software platform, which allows researchers to quickly develop and evaluate new methods and distribute them to clinical users. All features are available and extensible in Python. It is used for visualization and analysis (for example segmentation) of medical image computing data sets.

3D Slicer's benefits:

- › It supports all commonly used data sets and many types of images, segmentations, surfaces, transformations, in 2D, 3D and 4D.
- › Supports multi-modality imaging including, MRI
- › Real-time interface for medical devices, such as surgical navigation systems and sensors
- › It has a large and active community and new features are being added regularly

3.2.4 ANALYSIS - CONCLUSIONS

In this section, we present the tools, which will be used for the implementation of the MES-CoBraD project after the extensive state-of-the-art analysis conducted in Sections 3.2.2 and 3.2.3, as well as the up to date collected information.

- › Regarding electrophysiology signals, i.e., EEG, PSG, etc., the MNE library will be used for having access to the data. More specifically, MNE returns the list of channels, the data per channel, the sampling frequency, and many more information about the provided file. The data per channel are NumPy arrays. Next, for time-series analysis, the SciPy library will be used. More specifically, some functions that will be implemented via the SciPy library per channel are the following: estimation of the power spectral density (PSD) using a periodogram or the Welch's method, computation of the spectrogram with consecutive Fourier transforms, computation of the Short Time Fourier Transform, peak finding, etc. In addition, we will use the YASA library for event detection, including sleep spindles and slow waves. To be more precise, the YASA library returns a Pandas DataFrame, where each row is a detected event, and each column is a parameter (= feature or property) of this event. Due to the fact that the start and end times of the detected events are reported in seconds, we will multiply them with the sampling frequency for getting the starting and ending indexes of the detected events. The Visualization Component will receive these indexes and will assign a colour to the time-series. In addition, YASA provides a function, i.e., `bandpower_from_psd`, for extracting the average bandpower in specified bands from a pre-computed PSD. YASA returns a DataFrame, which will be passed in json format to the Visualization Component. Moreover, the user of the platform will be able to apply filters, including lowpass, bandpass, and highpass, to any channel. To achieve this, the SciPy library will be used. To be more precise, the `scipy.signal.butter` can be used, which receives as arguments the order of the filter, the critical frequency or frequencies, the type of the filter, the type of the output etc. and returns parameters depending on the argument passed to the output. For instance, if the output is equal to 'ba', then the numerator (b) and denominator (a) will be returned, which will be passed to the `scipy.signal.filter` for applying the filter to the data. In terms of the time-series forecasting, the `pmdarima` library will be used. More specifically, the `auto.arima` function will be exploited, since it automatically discovers the optimal order for an ARIMA model. The predictions of the `auto.arima` will be passed to the Visualization Component. Also, `auto.arima` returns the summary of the model, which will be also passed to the Visualization Component. Series' auto-correlation and partial auto-correlation can be achieved either by using the `pmdarima` library or the `statsmodels` library in Python. For the purposes of the visualizations of the electrophysiology signals, the `amCharts` library will be exploited.
- › Regarding actigraphy data analysis, the `pyActigraphy` library will be exploited, since one can read native actigraphy data files with various formats, including Actigraph (wGT3X-BT),

CamNtech (Actiwatch 4 and MotionWatch 8), and many more. Before analysing the data, spurious periods of inactivity, where the actigraph was most probably removed by the participant need to be discarded from the activity recordings. This can be achieved via this library, which automatically masks continuous periods of inactivity. After that, several variables can be calculated, including the day-to-day variance, the activity fragmentation, and the relative difference between the mean activity during the 10 most active hours and the 5 least active ones. The automatic detection of rest and activity periods can be also achieved via several approaches provided by the pyActigraphy library. Finally, pyActigraphy provides advanced signal processing functions. Results may be used for visualization purposes or further analyses.

- › With regards to the MRI processing, the NiBabel library will be exploited first, since it provides access to most neuroimaging file formats. Next, the Nilearn, Dipy, Nipype, and NLTools libraries can be used for statistical purposes and further analyses. The SciPy and OpenCV libraries can also be exploited, since they offer some general functionalities for image processing. Due to the fact that the Nipype library provides interfaces to existing neuroimaging software, including FSL, ANTs, SPM etc. it appears to be the most ideal toolkit. For instance, some of the functionalities, which are provided by these tools, are the following: undistortion, slice time correction, normalisation, smoothing, etc. In addition, NLTools can be used for identifying spikes from fMRI data. When it comes to visualization purposes, the Nilearn library appears to be the most ideal one, since it provides many functionalities for plotting, including plotting an anatomical image, an EPI glass brain visualization, statistical map, plotting Regions of Interest, etc. Plotting functions in Nilearn receive as input the data to be displayed, the name of an image output file, the display mode, the coordinated of the point where the cut is performed, and more. Nilearn supports also interactive plotting, where one can save the viewer as a stand-alone html file. This functionality renders Nilearn ideal for visualization of MRI data.
- › Regarding general statistical analyses, the SciPy, scikit-learn, and statsmodels libraries will be used. More specifically, both the SciPy and statsmodels libraries include statistical tests and correlation functions, which will be applied to the data. In terms of the multiple tests for the adjustment of the p-values, the statsmodels library will be used. In addition, scikit-learn can be used for applying dimensionality reduction techniques, i.e., PCA, t-SNE. These techniques can be used also for visualization purposes. At the same time, the scikit-learn library can be used for scaling the data before performing the analyses.

In Table 5, we present a comparative analysis of the aforementioned tools that could be used for the purposes of the analysis and visualizations of the data.

Table 5 – Data Analytics and Visualisation Tools

Tool	Features	Compatibility	Activity (Last Year)	Open-Source	Analytics	Visualisations
NumPy	Access to specific elements of the arrays. Very useful, since most data are in numpy arrays.		29,245 commits	✓	✓	
Pandas	Dataframes, imputation of missing values, apply transformations to columns/rows, merge/combine/join datasets similarly to SQL		29,078 commits	✓	✓	
DASK	Compute on arrays larger than memories, use of multiple threads or processes on a single machine, Does not implement all the functionalities provided by the Pandas library		7,026 commits	✓	✓	
SciPy	Signal Processing, including filtering, fourier transforms. Statistical tests via the stats package. Image Processing. Does not support multiple comparisons for the adjustment of the p-values.		27,422 commits	✓	✓	
Scikit-learn	Clustering methods, Dimensionality reduction techniques, methods for visualization, etc.		27,948 commits	✓	✓	
Statsmodels	Time-series analysis (ARMA, ARIMA, etc.), multiple tests for the adjustment of p-values, imputation of missing values (Multiple Imputation with Chained Equations)		14,507 commits	✓	✓	
Pmdarima	Time series analysis and forecasting. auto.arima: automatically discover the optimal order for an ARIMA model		1,047 commits	✓	✓	✓

Tool	Features	Compatibility	Activity (Last Year)	Open-Source	Analytics	Visualisations
Sktime	Time series analysis, forecasting, classification. Under development		2,323 commits	✓	✓	
Pinguin	Statistical tests. Multiple tests for the adjustment of p-values.		1,173 commits	✓	✓	
Nitime	Time series analysis of data derived by neuroimaging experiments. Spectral transforms, coherency, periodogram, etc.		1,274 commits	✓	✓	
MNE	Reads data from many formats, i.e., edf, vhdr, eeg, vmrk, etc., Functionalities for preprocessing data, i.e., filtering, repairing of artefacts, etc.	Export as HTML	16,698 commits	✓	✓	✓
YASA	Algorithms for event detection, i.e., sleep spindles/slow waves/rapid eye movements. Spectral analysis	Export predicted hypnogram and stage probabilities to text or csv with standard Python functions	326 commits	✓	✓	✓
WONAMBI	Detection of spindles and slow waves, frequency analysis, time-frequency analysis	Export channels as json	1,521 commits	✓	✓	✓
SleepPy	One can load raw accelerometer data via an input file (.bin or .csv). Extraction of sleep statistics.		70 commits	✓	✓	
PyActigraphy	Reads actigraphy data from many file formats. Detection of rest periods by applying many algorithms. Advanced signal processing techniques.		324 commits	✓	✓	

Tool	Features	Compatibility	Activity (Last Year)	Open-Source	Analytics	Visualisations
Visbrain	EEG, MEG, Fmri, signal plotting, objects animation, time-series, loading from multiple sources	Export hypnogram to png, export sleep statistics to csv, subplots can be animated and exported into a video file or images	3,898 commits	✓	✓	✓
Neuropycon	Pipelines for multiprocessing of MEG, EEG, functional and anatomical MRI.		Ephypype package: 355 commits Graphypype package: 270 commits	✓	✓	
Nilearn	Statistical and Machine Learning tools. Easy-to-read documentation with a lot of examples. A lot of plotting functions for visualising the MRI data.	Export plot as image(png, svg) and pdf	9,566 commits	✓	✓	✓
DIPY	Brain volume slicing, visualising bundles, metrics on bundles and an interface to access many capabilities of VTK		12,045 commits	✓	✓	✓
Antropy	Feature extraction from EEG data.		123 commits	✓	✓	
UK Biobank accelerometer analysis	Extraction of information from large accelerometer datasets. Process data from many file formats. Sleep/activity statistics.		854 commits	✓	✓	
PyEEG	Feature extraction from EEG data.		63 commits	✓	✓	
Eeglib	Feature extraction from EEG data		83 commits	✓	✓	
NiBabel	Read MRI data from many file formats.		5,115 commits	✓	✓	

Tool	Features	Compatibility	Activity (Last Year)	Open-Source	Analytics	Visualisations
	Limited support for DICOM.					
BIOPAC System Actigraphy	Sleep and Activity analysis				✓	
Koneksa Actigraphy	Sleep and Activity analysis				✓	
Motionware	Sleep and Activity analysis				✓	
Actiware	Analysis of data from Actiwatch models				✓	
MedPy	Read/Write/Manipulate medical images. Apply filters, transformations. Compute mutual information between two images or distance between histograms.		324 commits	✓	✓	
Scikit-image	Image processing. Does not provide algorithms and statistical analyses used in medical image processing.	Save images to files	13,106 commits	✓	✓	✓
OpenCV		Video stream, images to API	31,627 commits	✓	✓	✓
Fmriprep	fMRI data preprocessing pipeline		6,559 commits	✓	✓	
Nipype	Combine tools from various packages (FSL, ANTs, etc.), build and share workflows		14,316 commits	✓	✓	✓
NLTools	Analysis of neuroimaging data, Identification of spikes from time series data, Apply spatial smoothing, etc.		1,351 commits	✓	✓	
ActiLife	Actigraphy data analysis				✓	
FreeSurfer	MRIs		30,825 commits	✓	✓	✓
NeuroDesk	Electrophysiological data, MRI data		310 commits	✓	✓	✓
D3.js	Huge variety of charts, interactivity,		38 commits	✓		✓

Tool	Features	Compatibility	Activity (Last Year)	Open-Source	Analytics	Visualisations
	animations		99.4k stars 22.9k forks			
Chart.js	Basic Charts		500+ commits 55.5k stars 11.3k forks	✓		✓
SensorMotion	Analyse time-series, accelerometer data. contains a simple plot module for creation signal plots		No commits 56 stars 24 forks	✓		✓
PyEMD	EMD, EEMD, signal decomposition		24 commits 507 stars 167 forks	✓	✓	✓
PySurfer	Plot rgb values on brain surface, display fMRI activation and volume, plot transparent brain, generate surface labels conjunction		No commits 175 stars 91 forks	✓		✓
BrainVISA/Anatomist	Load and view objects, change camera parameters, view meshes, custom colour palettes, fusion between volumes, modular environment			✓		✓
Visualisation Toolkit (VTK)	3D rendering, image processing, visualizations of scalar, vector and tensor fields, visualization of volume data, mesh and polygon processing, image analysis for 2D, 3D images	Export to 3D model formats (GL2PS, IVE, OBJ, OOGL, RIB, VRML, POV, X3D)	2800+ commits 1.7k stars 924 forks	✓		✓
3D Slicer	Support for many types (images, segmentations, surfaces, transformations, in 2D+), MRI	ScreenCapture module, capture image sequences from slice and 3D views and export them as a	950+ commits 504 stars 229 forks	✓		✓

Tool	Features	Compatibility	Activity (Last Year)	Open-Source	Analytics	Visualisations
		sequence of images or a video file				

3.3 ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND MACHINE LEARNING – COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS

3.3.1 OVERVIEW

This section will analyse different Artificial Intelligence and machine learning techniques for the ideal combination of tools in our system. While our methodology distinguishes the elements to be used according to the variables available to us, Artificial Intelligence techniques are able to extend the analysis to more features as well as to greater depth. In our case, to increase the probability of choosing the right tools, we have thoroughly tested all the tools as well as their derivatives. The results are analysed below in detail for all possible scenarios.

3.3.2 ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND MACHINE LEARNING TOOLS

TensorFlow[128]: is an opensource backwards-compatible platform made by Google that focused on machine learning methods and providing low-level tools and libraries for the end user. It supports execution via GPU, CPU or TPU and can be integrated with many higher-level libraries to help the development of the algorithms and it's very flexible and scalable. In medicine, TensorFlow can use 2D and 3D CNNs (Cascaded Neural Networks) for processing large medical image datasets [129].

Tensorflow's benefits:

- › Has ready-to-use pre-trained datasets
- › Provides math and linear algebra expressions
- › Analyses images, audio and text
- › Supports a wide variety toolbox with Machine Learning Algorithms
- › Provides different model types of Neural Networks

Tensorflow's limitations:

- › Architectural limitations that only allows to execute a model but not the ability to train it.
- › Lags at providing the symbolic loops for indefinite sequences.
- › Version 1 supports only NVIDIA for GPU and python for GPU programming. The updated version 2 can be used on a CPU, but TensorFlow's dependencies must be able to use version also.
- › It has low speed with respect to its competitors. It has less usability in comparison to other frameworks.

PyTorch[130]: is an open-source replacement for NumPy that can be used on Deep Learning applications. One of its key benefits is the GPU (Graphics Processing Unit) integration that can extend its potential and accelerate the process and reduce timings. PyTorch is also very easy to use with the wide variety of options it offers. It can be used by all operating systems (Linux, Mac, and Windows), can be accessed through three programming languages (Python, C++ and Java) and it can use a CPU (Central Processing Unit) or a GPU to run the layers of a Neural Network. Finally, PyTorch uses a dynamic execution technique in a way that we can change how the network model behaves, at any given time, without starting from scratch and with almost with no delays [131].

PyTorch's Benefits:

- › End-to-End Machine Learning Tools
- › Uses torchServe to deploy PyTorch models
- › Supports multi-model serving, logging, metrics

- › Available RESTful API endpoints
- › Native support for asynchronous execution

PyTorch's Limitations:

- › PyTorch is very new to the research field and lack the high variety of features and the community that supports it is not highly developed. Also, it lacks the monitoring and visualization features that other solution, like TensorFlow, support.

Keras[132]: is a high-level Deep Learning API that extends TensorFlow, initially developed for fast Deep Learning experimentation. It is used by many big tech companies, and it's created to be user friendly and easy to integrate. It, also, supports execution with all possible ways (GPU, CPU or TPU) and provides pre-trained models such as (Xception, VGG16, VGG19, ResNet, ResNetV2, InceptionV3, InceptionResNetV2, MobileNet, MobileNetV2, DenseNet and NASNet) [133][134]

On the other hand, the main limitation of Keras is that it cannot support low-level modification of the system, as it's not designed to do so and if an error occurs it may be hard to debug and overcome. Finally, although it supports a lot of features, it lacks some other Machine Learning features like Clustering and PCA (Principal Component Analysis).

Keras's benefits:

- › API-designed Machine Learning tools
- › Tailored for Deep Learning applications
- › Used also in:
 - Computer Vision (image analysis, etc.)
 - Natural Language Processing
 - Structured Data Classification
 - Timeseries
 - Audio processing
 - Reinforcement Learning
 - Graph Neural Networks

Keras's limitations:

- › Using Keras you can face low-level backend errors continuously.
- › It is slow on GPU and takes longer time in computation compared with its backends.
- › Keras does not support features of dynamic chart creation.

NiBabel: is a library created by NIPY, a community of practice devoted to the use of the Python programming language in the analysis of neuroimaging data, and can provide read and write access to a variety of medical file formats, including ANALYZE (plain, SPM99, SPM2 and later), GIFTI, Nifti1, Nifti2, CIFTI-2, MINC1, MINC2, AFNI BRIK/HEAD, MGH and ECAT as well as Philips PAR/REC.

NiBabel's benefits:

- › Used to analyse neuroimaging data

- › Provide read / write access to a variety of medical formats:
 - ANALYZE (plain, SPM99, SPM2 and later)
 - GIFTI
 - NIFTI1 and NIFTI2
 - CIFTI-2
 - MINC1 and MINC2
 - AFNI BRIK/HEAD
 - MGH
 - ECAT
 - Philips PAR/REC

NiBabel's limitations:

- › Small capabilities and features
- › Steep learning curve while it has a small community supporting it

CEML: stands for Counterfactuals for Explaining Machine Learning models and is a Python toolbox for computing counterfactuals. Counterfactuals can be used to explain the predictions of machine learning models. This toolbox supports many a variety of machine learning frameworks like scikit-learn, PyTorch, Keras and Tensorflow. Furthermore, CEML is easy to use and can be extended and integrated very easily.

CEML's benefits:

- › Toolbox for computing counterfactuals
- › Used to explain the predictions of Machine Learning Models
- › Displays statistics for model optimisations
- › Integrated with Tensorflow, scikit-learn, PyTorch and Keras

CEML's limitations:

- › It doesn't have a detailed documentation and support for possible problems.

Clinica: is a software platform for clinical research studies involving patients with neurological and psychiatric diseases and the acquisition of multimodal data, most often with longitudinal follow-up. This tool works as a command-line driven and written in complete Python language. It supports a various integration with Nipype system for pipelining and combines widely used software packages for neuroimaging data analysis like FreeSurfer, FSL, PETPVC, SPM, ANTs, Scikit-learn and the BIDS standard for data organisation. Clinica can provide tools that convert publicly available neuroimaging datasets into BIDS (ADNI, AIBL, NIFD, OASIS, OASIS-3 etc.).

Clinica can process any BIDS-compliant dataset with a set of complex processing pipelines involving different software packages for the analysis of neuroimaging data. This tool can also provide integration between feature extraction and statistics, machine learning or deep learning.

Clinica's features:

- › Neuroimaging data analysis

- › Anatomical MRI
- › Diffusion MRI
- › PET
- › Statistical analysis
- › Machine learning
- › Data management made easy:
- › Standardised data structures for inputs
- › Standardised data structures for outputs
- › Conversion of datasets into BIDS (ADNI, AIBL, NIFD, OASIS, OASIS-3, etc.)

Theano: is a Python library that allows you to define, optimise, and efficiently evaluate mathematical expressions involving multi-dimensional arrays. Theano can have a tight integration with NumPy, can perform data-intensive computations up to 140x faster than on a CPU, can compute derivatives for functions of one or many inputs. Furthermore, can avoid a lot of bugs when computing expressions such as $\log(1+\exp(x))$ for large values of x , evaluate expressions faster and include detecting, plus diagnosing bugs or potential problems.

Theano's Features:

- › Define, Optimise and Evaluate mathematical expressions
- › Can process multi-dimensional arrays
- › Based on NumPy and accelerates its performance on CPU-based computations
- › Provides numerical stability when computes "heavy" expressions on large dataset

SNNTorch: is designed to be intuitively used with a variety of tools like PyTorch, as though each spiking neuron were simply another activation a sequence of layers. All spiking neuron classes are available to be used as activation units with PyTorch. Each of them, consists of an agnostic type to fully connected layers, convolutional layer, residual connections and more. The requirements of snntorch enable small and large networks to be viably trained on CPU when needed. The libraries that snntorch uses take advantage of GPU acceleration in the same way as PyTorch. The default use of PyTorch is unable to calculate the analytical derivative of the spiking neuron graph that is how snntorch overrides the default gradient, using the appropriate methods. The neurons available in snntorch are variants of the LEaky Integrate-and-Fire neuron model:

- › **Leaky** - 1st-Order Leaky Integrate-and-Fire Neuron
- › **Synaptic** - 2nd-Order Integrate-and-Fire Neuron (including synaptic conductance)
- › **Lapicque** - Lapicque's RC Neuron Model
- › **Alpha** - Alpha Membrane Model

SNNTorch's Features:

- › Simulates Spiking Neural Networks using PyTorch
- › Apply deep learning, gradient descent, backpropagation, and neuroscience to biologically plausible Spiking Neural Networks

BindsNET: A Python package used for simulating spiking neural networks (SNNs) on CPUs or GPUs using PyTorch Tensor functionality. BindsNET is a spiking neural network simulation library geared towards the development of biologically inspired algorithms for machine learning.

BindsNET's Features:

- › Simulates Spiking Neural Networks using PyTorch
- › Used to develop biologically inspired algorithms for ML

MXNet: is an open-source python library designed for providing both efficiency and flexibility when developing deep learning frameworks. MXNet contains a dynamic dependency scheduler that automatically parallelises both symbolic and imperative operations on the fly. A graph optimisation layer on top of that makes symbolic execution fast and memory efficient. MXNet is portable and lightweight, scalable to many GPUs and machines (ref: <https://mxnet.apache.org>).

MxNet's Features:

- › Open-source deep learning framework
- › Scalable distributed training
- › Provides performance optimisation
- › Can be extended in computer vision, NLP, time series (and more) through 3rd party tools
 - D2L.ai
 - GluonCV
 - GluonNLP
 - GluonTS

SurPRISE: is a python library that depends on numpy and it's used for creating recommender systems. It is very good at handling datasets either the ones already build in, or custom ones the users may load. It, also, supports many predicting and neighboring algorithms and it can measure and analyse each algorithms performance.

SurPRISE's limitation may be that it's focused on movie recommendations and a rating system based on user input for each specific movie.

SurPRISE's Features:

- › Depends on NumPy
- › Used to create Recommender Systems
- › Supports Predicting and Neighbouring algorithms
- › Focuses on Rating Systems (mainly on movies)

Alibi Explain: is an open-source python library that assists with the monitoring and explaining of black-box and white-box ML models, and it can also expose local and global explanation methods for classification and regression models. Alibi provides a set of algorithms or methods known as explainers. Each explainer provides insight about a model. The set of insights available given a trained model is dependent on several factors. For instance, if the model is a regression model it makes sense to ask how the prediction varies for some regressor. Whereas it doesn't make sense to ask what minimal change is required to obtain a new class prediction.

Alibi's Features:

- › Open source
- › Can be integrated by all implementations
- › Provide high quality reference implementations of black-box ML model explanation algorithms
- › Support multiple use cases (e.g., tabular, text and image data classification, regression)
- › Provide a variety of ML model monitoring and interpretation methods.

Captum: is an open-source python module for explaining the ML models provided by PyTorch. Captum allows researchers to quickly benchmark their work against other existing algorithms available in the library. For model developers, Captum can be used to improve and troubleshoot models by facilitating the identification of different features that contribute to a model's output to design better models and troubleshoot unexpected model outputs.

Captum's Features:

- › Open source
- › Can be integrated with PyTorch
- › Provides a wide variety of gradient-based and perturbation algorithms
- › Provides visualizations
- › Provides ML model debugging and insights.

3.3.2.1 Overview

Table 6 – Artificial Intelligence Tools

Tool	Documentation	Activity	Open source	Ease of use
TensorFlow	Well	Active	Yes	Medium
PyTorch	Well	Active	Yes	Easy
Keras	Well	Active	Yes	Easy
Nipy/NiBabel	Well	Inactive (Last change 28 Noe 2020)	Yes	Easy
CEML	Good	Moderate	Yes	Medium
Clinica	Good	Active	Yes	Medium
Theano	Good	Archaic	Yes	Medium
SnnTorch	Good	Active	Yes	Medium
BindsNET	Good	Moderate	Yes	Easy
MXNet	Well	Active	Yes	Medium
SurPRISE	Good	Inactive	Yes	Difficult
Alibi Explain	Well	Active	Yes	Easy
Captum	Well	Active	Yes	Easy

[135], [136]

4 REQUIREMENTS' ELABORATION

The present section elaborates on the system requirements defining and coding the description. Integration aspects referring to Advanced Analytics components and the MES-CoBraD Platform are also reported.

4.1 EXPERT SYSTEM - PROCESS MODELLING AND MANAGEMENT

Table 7- Expert System requirements

Code		ES-1
Title	Expert System	
User Facing	Yes	
User Roles	Clinician	
Priority	Must have	
Description and Rationale	The system shall provide an Expert System to guide clinical decisions by providing feedback from both patients and clinicians.	

Code		ES-2
Title	Flexible steps sequence within processes	
User Facing	Yes	
User Roles	Scientist / Clinician	
Priority	Should have	
Description and Rationale	The system shall allow for flexibility of relations of priority and posteriority between steps in processes.	

Code		ES-3
Title	Visualization per Step of DSS/ES output	
User Facing	Yes	
User Roles	Scientist / Clinician	
Priority	Must have	
Description and Rationale	The system shall provide to the user the ability to have a visual comprehension of the posterior probabilities of the proposed next step(s) - cutoff for highest probability next steps, for each decision(s) the ES makes.	

Code		ES-4
Title	User control over next step(s) of DSS/ES	
User Facing	Yes	
User Roles	Scientist / Clinician	
Priority	Must have	
Description and Rationale	The system shall allow the user to choose the next step (from the list or outside it), depending on options provided in Visualization per Step of	

DSS/ES output.

Code		ES-5
Title	Coordination aide module - scheduling	
User Facing	Yes	
User Roles	Scientist / Clinician	
Priority	Could have	
Description and Rationale	The system shall allow the coordinator/user to be informed of upcoming steps (e.g., scheduling a specific participant, or calling someone), based on the pilot protocol process of a study.	

Code		ES-6
Title	Coordination aide module - progress/monitoring	
User Facing	Yes	
User Roles	Scientist / Clinician	
Priority	Could have	
Description and Rationale	The system shall provide feedback on the progress of recruited participants and participants performing various tests.	

Code		ES-7
Title	Option for randomisation of participants into an intervention	
User Facing	Yes	
User Roles	Scientist / Clinician	
Priority	Could have	
Description and Rationale	The system shall randomise participants into an intervention.	

Code		ES-8
Title	Developer tool - Protocols	
User Facing	Yes	
User Roles	Scientist / Clinician	
Priority	Must have	
Description and Rationale	The system shall allow to create a flow of actions that reflect a protocol (e.g., PUC1) including timelines, processes. Harmonised protocols can be achieved within and across sites, and ES can identify types of variables present (or missing), to pursue recommendations and analyses.	

Code		ES-9
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Title	Visualize flow of actions
User Facing	Yes
User Roles	Scientist / Clinician
Priority	Must have
Description and Rationale	The system shall allow to visualize flow of actions that reflect the protocol.

Code	ES-10
Title	Observed and latent variables
User Facing	Yes
User Roles	Scientist / Clinician
Priority	Must have
Description and Rationale	The ES shall be able to consider / use both simple / observed and complex / latent decision variables.

Code	ES-11
Title	Selection and execution analytical processes
User Facing	No
User Roles	None
Priority	Must have
Description and Rationale	The system shall allow the user to create a workflow in which every step will have a function for performing a specific analysis task from modules/packages analysis.

Code	ES-12
Title	UI for selecting analytical processes
User Facing	Yes
User Roles	Scientist / Clinician
Priority	Must have
Description and Rationale	The system shall allow the user to create a workflow in which every step will have a function for performing a specific analysis task from modules/packages analysis.

Code	ES-13
Title	ES - Guided steps
User Facing	Yes
User Roles	Scientist / Clinician, Caregiver, Patient
Priority	Should have
Description and Rationale	The system shall permit the user to be informed by the ES on the next recommended diagnostic

	<p>step, so as depending on the data available to the ES at any given time, it can start forming hypotheses based on the "chief complaint" and "deep-phenotype" of a patient and instruct on accessing missing variables.</p> <p>Each task will be categorised and will allow to use metadata information for better future recommendations.</p>
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Code	ES-14
Title	Automated report/message generator
User Facing	Yes
User Roles	Scientist / Clinician, Patient
Priority	Could have
Description and Rationale	The system shall generate a report either for feedback to the patient or for use by a clinician, based on the data entered in a specific function.

Code	ES-15
Title	Communicate with patients at key times
User Facing	Yes
User Roles	Scientist / Clinician, Patient
Priority	Would be nice
Description and Rationale	The system shall ensure communication with patients at key times.

Code	ES-16
Title	Diagnostic Guidelines Reference Links
User Facing	Yes
User Roles	Scientist / Clinician
Priority	Should have
Description and Rationale	The system shall permit to introduce diagnostic guideline libraries in the Platform for being referenced against by the ES in making possible diagnoses.

Code	ES-17
Title	Therapeutic Guidelines
User Facing	Yes
User Roles	Scientist / Clinician
Priority	Must have
Description and Rationale	The system shall allow to introduce specific recommended therapies according to specific diagnoses / phenotypes, so when using the platform, the user will be informed if a specific

therapy can be considered.

Code	ES-18
Title	Labelling each task
User Facing	No
User Roles	None
Priority	Would be nice
Description and Rationale	Each task will be labelled based of each feature to know how to structure it. This is a support feature to help you run the application better while using a tool of the ES.

Code	ES-19
Title	Create and manage interactive forms
User Facing	Yes
User Roles	Scientist / Clinician
Priority	Should have
Description and Rationale	Build and edit forms that will introduce new ways of data manipulation and provide input on possible missing data.

Code	ES-20
Title	Metadata collection
User Facing	No
User Roles	None
Priority	Must have
Description and Rationale	Each task, process and executable in general should keep metadata for later process use, accordingly, to its type (statistical analysis, evaluation, etc.).

Code	ES-21
Title	Workflow / task duplication
User Facing	Yes
User Roles	Scientist / Clinician, Caregiver
Priority	Could have
Description and Rationale	Each workflow should keep data of every workflow with the same variables when created to duplicate or transfer data.

Code	ES-22
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Title	Unique identification of each process
User Facing	No
User Roles	None
Priority	Would be nice
Description and Rationale	Each task and each process should have a unique id, followed by a folder / DB / storage that allows for a “process workspace” to exchange data globally and/or use specific data as input/output

4.2 QUERY BUILDER

Table 8 - Query Builder Requirement

Code	QRB-1
Title	Query Builder
User Facing	Yes
User Roles	Scientist/ Clinician/
Priority	Must have
Description and Rationale	The system shall allow to create an SQL Query taking as input data in JSON format. The current Query Builder works only with tabular data. It should be heavily extended to support health data for the project.

4.3 DATA ANALYTICS

Table 9 - Data Analytics Requirements

Code	DAN-1
Title	Time-Series Analysis
User Facing	No
User Roles	None
Priority	Must have
Description and Rationale	The DAN Component will retrieve data from the Data Lake via the QRB Component. The purpose of the DAN-1 component is to develop models that best capture or describe an observed time series, in order to understand the underlying causes. To achieve this, the user will be able to select via the UI the algorithms to be applied to the time-series data. Examples include amongst others the short-time Fourier Transform (STFT), Discrete Wavelet Transform, etc. The user may be able to apply ARMA models to the time-series data for predicting future patient data. The system shall be able also to apply algorithms to actigraphy data. Results of the introduced approaches will be

	transferred to the VDS component for visualization or to the ML component for further analysis.
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Code	DAN-2
Title	Posterior probabilities of next steps
User Facing	No
User Roles	None
Priority	Should have
Description and Rationale	The system shall calculate posterior probabilities of proposed next steps.

Code	DAN-3
Title	Option for randomisation of participants into an intervention
User Facing	Yes
User Roles	Scientist/Clinician
Priority	Would be nice
Description and Rationale	Firstly, the DAN Component will retrieve the datasets from the Data Lake via the Query Builder. Then, the DAN-3 Component will apply a function, e.g., random, to the dataset, so that the participants in the datasets be randomised.

Code	DAN-4
Title	Support ES- Guided steps
User Facing	Yes
User Roles	Clinician – Scientist, Patient/Caregiver
Priority	Should have
Description and Rationale	The system shall permit the user to be informed by the ES on the next recommended diagnostic step, so as depending on the data available to the ES at any given time, it can start forming hypotheses based on the "chief complaint" and "deep-phenotype" of a patient and instruct on accessing missing variables.

Code	DAN-5
Title	Recommend analyses' types
User Facing	Yes
User Roles	Scientist/ Clinician
Priority	Must have
Description and Rationale	The Data Analytics Component shall retrieve data from the Data Lake via the QRB Component. Next,

	the user will have the capability via the UI to choose which statistical function should be applied to the data, depending on the available ones based on the input data. This functionality will be provided to the user at the stage of data distribution (DAN-14), analysing the data (DAN-1), and Exploratory Data Analysis (DAN-12).
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Code	DAN-6
Title	Selection of cases based on inclusion and exclusion criteria
User Facing	Yes
User Roles	Scientist/ Clinician
Priority	Must have
Description and Rationale	The system shall allow to select cases based on inclusion and exclusion criteria (upon performing an analysis, select whom you will study based on x, y, z criteria).

Code	DAN-7
Title	Data manipulation plug-ins
User Facing	Yes
User Roles	Scientist/ Clinician
Priority	Would be nice
Description and Rationale	The system shall allow scientists to install plug-ins that would provide black box functionalities offered by the community.

Code	DAN-8
Title	Integrate Opensource modules for EEG/PSG, but also MRI data
User Facing	Yes
User Roles	Scientist/ Clinician
Priority	Should have
Description and Rationale	The Data Analytics Component will retrieve the data from the Data Lake using the QRB Component. Then, for each stage of the analysis, i.e., DAN-1, DAN-14, and more, the Data Analytics Component will include opensource libraries for analysing the data.

Code	DAN-11
Title	Generation of a report as output

User Facing	Yes
User Roles	Scientist/ Clinician
Priority	Must have
Description and Rationale	The Data Analytics Component will retrieve data from the Data Lake via the QRB Component. Next, at each stage of applying algorithms for analysing and processing the data, the Data Analytics Component should be able to save which programming language, i.e., Python, MATLAB, R, etc. and library, i.e., SciPy, Nilearn, MNE, etc. was used for conducting the respective experiments. Finally, after the user has completed all the analyses, the system shall be able to export a file, which will include the programming language and the libraries used for each specific analysis.

Code	DAN-12
Title	Support for Exploratory Data Analysis (EDA)
User Facing	Yes
User Roles	Scientist/Clinician
Priority	Should have
Description and Rationale	The Data Analytics Component will retrieve data from the Data Lake via the QRB component. Next, the DAN will provide to the user the functionality of the Exploratory Data Analysis. Specifically, there will be an option in the User Interface (UI), where the user will be able to apply statistical functions, i.e., maximum, minimum, standard deviation, etc. to a specific column. Also, the DAN shall be able to apply correlations between columns, including the Pearson, Point-Biserial correlation, etc. Results of the EDA will be passed to the VDS component.

Code	DAN-13
Title	MRI Analysis
User Facing	No
User Roles	Scientist/Clinician
Priority	Should have
Description and Rationale	The DAN Component will retrieve data from the Data Lake via the QRB Component. The purpose of the DAN-13 component is to provide algorithms for the MRI analysis. For instance, the user will be able to apply GLM to MRI data. Results of the introduced approaches will be transferred to the VDS component for visualization or to the ML

component for further analysis.

4.4 HYPOTHESIS TESTING INTERFACE

Hypothesis testing is a Data Analytics interface.

Code		DAN-9
Title	Traits for steps in a process - selection of variables by class	
User Facing	Yes	
User Roles	Scientist/ Clinician	
Priority	Must have	
Description and Rationale	The system shall permit while examining if a hypothesis can be rejected, then select one or more sets of variables according to the "class they have.	

Code		DAN-10
Title	Hypothesis development and testing - High level associations	
User Facing	Yes	
User Roles	Scientist/ Clinician	
Priority	Must have	
Description and Rationale	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. DAN shall be able to retrieve data sets through the QRB (which retrieves datasets from the Data Lake. 2. DAN shall, additionally, receive specific input parameters determined by the user (e.g., statistical test selected, test's significance level defined). 3. DAN shall be able to apply a specific statistical test upon the retrieved data and conclude. 4. The data samples retrieved and involved in the test shall be also visualised through the VDS, in a way that the result is visually comprehensible to the user, indicating the critical parameters of the test. 5. All the parameters of the test (including users' parameters) shall be stored back in the data lake. This data will be used as an input to the DAN reporting module (DAN-11). 	

Code	DAN-14
Title	Applying methods that define data distribution
User Facing	Yes
User Roles	Scientist/Clinician
Priority	Should have
Description and Rationale	The Data analytics component will retrieve data from the Data Lake. The purpose of the DAN-14 component is to apply methods, which define the data distribution, i.e., normality, homoscedasticity. The result of each method can be transferred to the VDS component. This component will help the clinician identify the optimal method per hypothesis.

4.5 DATA AND RESULTS VISUALISATION

Table 10 - Data and Results Visualisation requirements

Code	VDS-1
Title	Visualization Dashboards
User Facing	Yes
User Roles	Scientist/ Clinician/ Patient/ Caregiver
Priority	Should have
Description and Rationale	The system shall store data collected from heterogenous outside data sources (RWD) and from outputs of the system in Data Lake solution.

Code	VDS-2
Title	Data visualization - time series
User Facing	Yes
User Roles	Scientist/ Clinician
Priority	Must have
Description and Rationale	The system shall display time series (e.g., actigraphy data, wearable data, eeg) of n number of variables through bars or lines (x axis for time, y for metric)

Code	VDS-3
Title	Data visualization - interface - select data
User Facing	Yes
User Roles	Scientist/ Clinician

Priority	Should have
Description and Rationale	The system shall allow to highlight a part of a graph that it's to be labelled. (Depending on the label data the user may decide what to do with it. This could be for example a period in a time series, a point in a scatterplot.)

Code	VDS-4
Title	Data visualization - interface - label data
User Facing	Yes
User Roles	Scientist/ Clinician
Priority	Should have
Description and Rationale	<p>The system shall allow user after selecting a part of a time series, as described in VDS-3, to be able to label the data, i.e. associate a text to the selection.</p> <p>Steps:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Write text in a field 2. Associate text with selection as it's described in VDS-3

Code	VDS-5
Title	Data visualization - visualize patient data
User Facing	Yes
User Roles	Scientist/ Clinician
Priority	Should have
Description and Rationale	The system shall allow the scientist to query all the data available from the patient in order to view them in dashboard.

Code	VDS-6
Title	Aggregate patient data visualization
User Facing	Yes
User Roles	Scientist/ Clinician
Priority	Must have
Description and Rationale	The system shall permit to visualize aggregates of patient data in the visualization dashboard

Code	VDS-7
Title	Time-Series Analysis output visualization
User Facing	Yes

User Roles	Scientist/ Clinician
Priority	Must have
Description and Rationale	The system shall display the results of time series analysis.

Code	VDS-8
Title	Data manipulation plug-ins
User Facing	Yes
User Roles	Scientist/ Clinician
Priority	Would be nice
Description and Rationale	The system shall allow scientists to install plug-ins that would provide black box functionalities offered by the community.

4.6 ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

Table 11 - Artificial Intelligence requirements

Code	AI-1
Title	Machine Learning based analysis of data lake
User Facing	No
User Roles	None
Priority	Must have
Description and Rationale	The system must use Machine Learning technique for delivering added value and analysis to data from data lake

Code	AI-2
Title	Machine Learning as a service via an open API
User Facing	No
User Roles	None
Priority	Must have
Description and Rationale	The system has to offer Machine learning as a Service capability provided by a dedicated and Open API-based platform.

Code	AI-3
Title	AI based natural language processing
User Facing	No
User Roles	None
Priority	Could have
Description and Rationale	The system shall include an open-source

	algorithm/platform (previously developed on the FITMAN project) which shall analyse natural language (via natural language processing) coming from social media content using techniques/algorithms like machine learning, sentiment analysis, correlation mining.
--	--

Code	AI-4
Title	AI based natural language processing reports
User Facing	Yes
User Roles	Scientist
Priority	Could have
Description and Rationale	The system shall produce customisable / configurable reports, dashboards and visualizations based on NLP analysis

Code	AI-5
Title	AI based process optimisation
User Facing	Yes
User Roles	Scientist / Clinician
Priority	Should have
Description and Rationale	The system shall optimise process steps sequences in Expert System based on prior information about steps effectiveness.

Code	AI-6
Title	Posterior probabilities of next steps
User Facing	No
User Roles	None
Priority	Should have
Description and Rationale	The system shall calculate posterior probabilities of proposed next steps.

Code	AI-7
Title	Support ES - Guided steps
User Facing	Yes
User Roles	Scientist / Clinician, Caregiver, Patient
Priority	Should have
Description and Rationale	The system shall permit the user to be informed by the ES on the next recommended diagnostic step, so as depending on the data available to the ES at any given time, it can start forming hypotheses based on the "chief complaint" and "deep-phenotype" of a patient and instruct on accessing missing variables.

Code	AI-8
Title	Input metadata parsing
User Facing	No
User Roles	None
Priority	Should have
Description and Rationale	The system can provide a parsing mechanism for given user input (e.g. the user, or even a workflow task can provide analysis metadata - if the expected input is CSD).

Code	AI-9
Title	Input data analysis / categorisation
User Facing	No
User Roles	None
Priority	Should have
Description and Rationale	The system shall be able to analyse and categorise input data to Single/Multiple Variable or Complex Data

4.7 INTEGRATION

The integration is an important aspect of the system. For this reason, we have developed in D7.1, as part of the architecture description, the integration View of the system.

Open standards and protocols are used for all components placed in the system both in terms of development and ease of use. The usage of open standards is the main enabler to the integration of all components.

4.7.1 ADVANCED ANALYTICS COMPONENTS' INTEGRATION

The integration of Advanced Analytics components is based on:

The usage of containers to host the components, and the placement of containers in an orchestrated environment run by Kubernetes.

The definition of communication protocols between components using open protocols. REST API and JSON format for data will be used in this perspective.

4.7.2 ADVANCED ANALYTICS AND MES-COBRA D PLATFORM INTEGRATION

All the components of Advanced Analytics will be placed as orchestrated containers in the overall architecture of the system.

Their integration will be considered on several layers of the system:

At the base layer, they will be placed in the same network defined by container orchestration.

At orchestration layer (Kubernetes) they will be part of the same Kubernetes setup.

At persistence layer they will all use the Data Lake.

At communication level, they will follow the same standard protocols to exchange data.

At function level, they will be placed on business flows, in relation with all the other components

At business level, they all will contribute to reach the project objectives.

The components will interact with external components thru Data Sharing Mechanism

5 ADVANCED ANALYTICS ARCHITECTURE

This section provides the overall architecture of the advanced analytics components and workflow management. Different features are presented as: UI Process Designer, Process Executor, Task Optimiser, Process Optimiser. The Query Builder serves as a connecting role in the MES-CoBraD ecosystem. Data Lake Interface specifications and Query Builder Modules providing also visualizations are reported.

5.1 OVERALL ARCHITECTURE

Advanced Analytics components are placed in the overall architecture of the system as containers managed by Kubernetes. The containers will be orchestrated as other containers part of the overall architecture.

The Advanced Analytics has an important place in the whole system, as presented in the next figure

Figure 20 - MES-CoBraD Architecture

5.2 COMPONENTS

5.2.1 EXPERT SYSTEM - PROCESS MODELLING AND MANAGEMENT

Expert System is a set of tools that provide the ability for the end user to execute dynamically created processes and create potentially unlimited workflows.

The Expert System will be executed on a closed dockerised environment (i.e., uses the Docker ²container

² <https://www.docker.com/>

platform), uses the python³ programming language and the Django⁴ web framework.

The Expert system contains a variety of tools and libraries based in python packages, that can manage workflows, workflow designer tools to create BPMN dynamic diagrams and other components that can be implemented via JSON standards.

5.2.1.1 Task Manage

The Task Manager component can create, update, and delete tasks from the data collected. Every task can have multiple instances, including forms, third-party applications, or AI algorithm services.

This function provides different features, such as task creation with the ability for a user to create tasks and the corresponding integration “drivers”. Each task has a predefined structured input received by the previous or the initial step and produces an explicitly defined output for exchange with the following one.

- › As mentioned previously, each task will represent a specific function that will be executed when the workflow gets at that stage and all the available functions will be available for the user to select.
- › If the task executes an AI algorithmic process, then the corresponding Artificial Intelligence module (ref: chapter 5.5.5 Artificial Intelligence) is solely responsible for parsing the data and executes the algorithm.
- › If the task executes an API integration, then the call is made given the data input and the output is parsed to be harmonised.
- › The task executes a form or a data manipulation “engine”.

Furthermore, the capability for task view, task update and task delete is available.

5.2.1.2 Workflow Manager

Workflow Manager is the function that handles all workflow related features. Workflow is a set of tasks that may follow the Business Process Model and Notation (BPMN) specification and provides the end users the capability of executing any process that follows or resembles a protocol streamlines their work.

This function provides different features, such as the UI Process Designer which includes is a Graphical User Interface exposed on web that creates workflows with simple interactive tools.

The Process Executor which is a function tightly connected with a user interface and a backend service that handles the connection between the user and the work process. The created BPMN, or Non-BPMN workflow can be initiated by the user and each task is executed using the logic operators.

The Task Optimiser which is responsible for controlling the metadata of previous and next executed tasks and collect timeseries data that makes statistical analysis on each task and optimise its performance. It will, also, be connected to the therapeutic / diagnostic guideline and rule system to assist and generate next-task recommendations.

Finally, the Process Optimiser function which is responsible for controlling the metadata of executed workflows and collect timeseries data that makes statistical analysis on each task and optimise its performance (accuracy, timings, status, etc.).

³ <https://www.python.org/>

⁴ <https://www.djangoproject.com/>

5.2.2 QUERY BUILDER

5.2.2.1 Design and functionalities

Figure 21 – Query Builder Component diagram

Query Builder Sub-components

This component will provide endpoints for the creation as well as the execution of SQL queries. The component diagram of Query Builder is depicted in Figure 21.

Query Request Ingest

The Query Builder will receive GET HTTP Requests, in which there will be parameters that will define the desired SQL query in JSON format

Query Creator

The body of the request will include information about the table name, the selected column names, the aggregation functions, the limit, etc. The Query Builder will support all the basic SQL commands, such as SELECT, GROUP BY, ORDER BY, JOIN and all the aggregation functions (SUM, AVG, MAX, MIN, COUNT). Given the input, the Query Builder will construct the desired SQL query.

Query Executor

Afterwards, the Query Executor will communicate with the Data Lake, gathering the data from the respective buckets, and will execute the SQL query in order to retrieve/get the wanted data. As a final step, the Query Executor will return the extracted data to the component that made the request.

5.2.2.2 Technologies and Tools

The Query Builder will be developed using the FastAPI (Python-based Framework).

5.2.2.3 Interfaces

The interfaces specified in Figure 21 refer to the communication between the Query Builder component and the rest components in MES-CoBraD. Query Builder shall provide its results to other components (e.g. Data Analytics, Data Results and Visualisation components) but the coordination of such actions shall be done through the workflow manager of the expert system. These indirect communication channels are not included

in this diagram.

The interfaces applicable to the Query Builder component, are:

- **QB.I.01: Data Lake Interface**
This interface allows the Query Builder component a) to retrieve datasets from the Data Lake for further processing and b) to save the results of the dataset processing in order to create a new dataset.
 - **Interface provider:** Data Lake component
 - **Input:** datasets;
 - **Output:** New dataset.
- **QB.I.02: Expert System Interface**
This interface allows the Query Builder component a) to send metadata of a dataset needed by the Task Manager to be used in a step in the BPMN builder or b) to send datasets specified by the metadata during an instance of the BPMN to be further used in other components.
 - **Interface provider:** Query Builder component
 - **Input:** Query request;
 - **Output:** datasets, dataset configuration data, or metadata.
- **QB.I.03: User Access Control System Interface**
This interface allows the Query Builder component to verify the identity of the user and whether they have access to the information they aim to query.
 - **Interface provider:** User Access Control System component
 - **Input:** not applicable;
 - **Output:** Keycloak tool metadata.

5.2.2.4 Performance Indicators

Response time: between the moment a new query is requested and the time when the SQL query is sent to the Data Lake, i.e. the maximum time duration: 1.000 ms.

Parallel Requests: number of parallel query building processes, i.e. the minimum parallel instances: 10

5.2.3 DATA ANALYTICS

5.2.3.1 Design and functionalities

The Data Analytics component will be used to implement statistical data analysis and hypothesis testing, analysis of time-series data, and Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) image analysis. This multi-purpose analytics service will provide the end-users (scientists - clinicians) the ability to analyse patients' data, develop insights about patients' health conditions and implement scientific research formulating hypotheses.

When performing an analysis, it will be possible to select the cases in which the analysis will be performed, based on some inclusion and exclusion criteria. Following the completion of an analysis, the module will be able to generate a detailed report, which shall include a variety of information on how the analysis was performed (e.g., the method that was used, the version of the programming language, the version of the pipeline/package).

Figure 22 – Advanced Analytics Component diagram

Data Analytics Sub-components

The component diagram of the Advanced Analytics component is depicted in , which includes the following sub-components:

Time series pre-processing

The Advanced Analytics module will provide algorithms for processing time series data, i.e., electroencephalogram (EEG), polysomnography (PSG) data, etc.

Depending on the format of the data the appropriate library will be utilised, as it is presented in 3.2.4.

Time series analysis

When it comes to the analysis, time-series analysis and forecasting methods will be provided. Autoregressive integrated moving average model (ARIMA) constitutes an example, which is implemented via the library named *pmdarima* in Python. Also, spectral analysis via Short-Time Fourier Transform (STFT), Discrete Wavelet Decomposition (DWT), etc. are necessary and implemented in most open-source libraries. The Advanced Analytics component will also provide algorithms for actigraphy data analysis, including the detection of rest periods, the implementation of advanced signal processing functions, and many more.

MRI pre-processing

The Advanced Analytics component will provide algorithms for processing MRI data. In case images are in *dicom* format, the component will enable the conversion into *nifty* files, if necessary, since this format is used by most libraries/tools.

MRI Analysis

The general linear model (GLM) can be implemented through the Advanced Analytics component. The GLM is used for making inferences about brain responses in a single subject. Also, the GLM can be used for making inferences about the group (second-level or group analysis). The available algorithms are presented in Section

3.2.4.

Statistical Analysis

The Advanced Analytics module will contain a series of statistical packages, which include functions that can be used in the analysis process. The focus of this component will be to provide interpretability of the data. For this purpose, methods for investigating the data, analysing the relationship between variables (e.g., correlation, regression algorithms) and processing datasets for identifying individual data points associations (e.g., clustering techniques) will be applied.

Hypothesis Testing

A specific Hypothesis Testing module will be created as part of the Advanced Analytics component development. This module will serve the requirements of clinical researchers to examine their research questions and investigate statistical differences in patients' sample data. The end-users will be able to formulate their hypotheses and evaluate them, using several statistical tests, proving if they can be accepted or not. Based on the assumptions and the purpose of each statistical test, several parametric (e.g., t-test, ANOVA, z-test) and non-parametric (e.g., Chi-squared test, Mann-Whitney U test, Wilcoxon signed-rank test) methods will be employed. Also, methods to adjust the p-values for multiple comparisons will be provided. The Hypothesis testing module is powered by the Advanced Analytics module using most of its tools and capabilities.

5.2.3.2 *Technologies and Tools*

The Data Analytics will be also implemented in FastAPI. FastAPI is a modern and fast (high-performance) web framework for building APIs with Python 3.6+

Various Python libraries will be used for the analysis of the data.

5.2.3.3 *Interfaces*

The interfaces specified in

refer to the communication between the Data Analytics component and the rest components in MES-CoBraD. Data Analytics processes depend on other components (e.g. Query Builder, Data Results and Visualisation components) but the coordination of such actions shall be done through the workflow manager of the expert system. These indirect communication channels are not included in this diagram.

The interfaces applicable to the Data Analytics component, are:

- **AA.I.01: Expert System**

This interface allows the Data Analytics component a) to send metadata needed by the Task Manager to specify the details of a single step in the BPMN builder and b) to receive the metadata necessary to execute an action, as specified in the Task Manager of the Expert System. After the completion of the action, the results of the analysis along with any relevant metadata are returned to the Workflow Manager.

- **Interface provider:** Data Analytics component
- **Input:** Task Manager request;
- **Output:** Analysis configuration data, Analytics results, metadata.

- **AA.I.02: User Access Control System Interface**

This interface allows the Data Analytics component to verify the identity, role and access rights of the user that uses the module.

- **Interface provider:** User Access Control System component
- **Input:** Not applicable;
- **Output:** Keycloak tool metadata.

- **AA.I.03: DataLake Interface**

This interface allows the Data Analytics component a) to retrieve datasets/objects from the Data Lake for further processing and b) to save the results of the dataset/objects processing in order to create a new dataset.

- **Interface provider:** Data Lake component
- **Input:** datasets, objects;
- **Output:** New dataset or new objects.

5.2.3.4 Performance Indicators

Response time: between the moment a new analysis is requested and the time when the result is sent to the Expert System, i.e. the maximum time duration: 1.000 ms.

Parallel Requests: number of parallel analysis processes, i.e. the minimum parallel instances: 10

5.2.4 DATA AND RESULTS VISUALISATION

5.2.4.1 Design and functionalities

The Data and Results Visualisation component will provide plots, visualisations and dashboards to facilitate the exploration of the results of the Query Builder and the Advanced Analytics components. It will help clinicians develop insights about patients' condition and based on these, take the appropriate actions.

Figure 23 – Data and Results Visualisation Component diagram

Data and Results Visualisation Sub-components

The modules that formulate the Data and Results Visualisation component and its functionalities are depicted in Figure 23.

Data Parser

The resulting incoming data from the components we mentioned previously, will be available as a dashlet that the user can insert into a customisable dashboard.

Statistical Analysis – MRI – Timeseries Visualisation

The workflow will let the user choose the type of visualisation (simple chart of values, barchart, lineplot, etc) and the settings that will be used for this visualisation (range, axes, etc). Then, there will be an option to add the visualisation to the dashboard where the user can do various other actions (change titles, rearrange dashlets, etc) and another option for saving the visualisation.

5.2.4.2 Technologies and Tools

The Data and Results Visualisation module will be implemented using the FastAPI framework.

AmCharts (JavaScript-based library) will be used for the needs of more general visualisations (e.g. time-series data). It is especially useful as it offers a wide variety of visualisations and provides interactivity out of the box.

React (JavaScript library) is a declarative, efficient, and flexible JavaScript library for building user interfaces. It can compose complex UIs from small and isolated pieces of code called “components”. The design of simple views for each state in MES-CoBraD will enhance application’s responsiveness by letting only the relevant components be efficiently updated and rendered when data changes.

Various Python libraries will also be used for visualising scientific data (EEG, MEG, MRI, etc) and offer statistical analysis visualisations. Some examples of these libraries are Nilearn, Visbrain and MNE-Python.

5.2.4.3 Interfaces

The interfaces specified in Figure 23 refer to the communication between the Data Results and Visualisation component and the rest components in MES-CoBraD. Data Results and Visualisation functionalities depend on other components (e.g. Query Builder, Data Analytics components) but the coordination of such actions shall be done through the workflow manager of the expert system. These indirect communication channels are not included in this diagram.

The interfaces applicable to the Data and Results Visualisation component, are:

- **V.I.01: Expert System**

This interface allows the Data and Results Visualisation component a) to send metadata of visualisations needed by the Task Manager to be used in a step in the BPMN builder and b) to send visualisations to be displayed during an instance of a BPM step.

- **Input:** Task Manager request;
- **Output:** Visualisation configuration data, Visualisations, metadata.

- **AA.I.02: User Access Control System Interface**

This interface allows the Data and Results Visualisation component to verify the identity, role and access rights of the user that uses the module.

- **Interface provider:** User Access Control System component
- **Input:** Not applicable;
- **Output:** Keycloak tool metadata.

5.2.4.4 Performance Indicators

Performance indicators shall be included in the next iteration of D6.1 in order to encapsulate better Users’ preferences on each different case.

5.2.5 ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

The Artificial Intelligence System is an autonomous service which consists of a series of sub-system services for providing data analysis. Analyses the input data, checks for execution options and finally executes the desired algorithm.

The AI System will be executed on a closed containerised environment (i.e. uses the Kubernetes container

platform), uses the python⁵ Django python package.

The Artificial Intelligence system will, also, integrate the following tools which have been reviewed and qualified so far:

- > TensorFlow
- > PyTorch
- > Keras
- > Alibi Explain
- > Captum

All data exchanges between functions and features will be JSON compliant.

5.2.5.1 *Analyse data*

This function, the input data is analysed by type and separated based on Single Variable Data (SVD), Multi Variable Data (MVD) and Complex Structured Data (CSD).

5.2.5.2 *Parse options*

This function checks any parameters given during input initialisation. The parameters will be specified and will delimit the available solutions when selecting an algorithm. All the parameters that is used its, speed / accuracy, prediction / diagnosis / treatment, explainable true / false, a specific algorithm and they will be optional.

5.2.5.3 *Algorithm selection and execution*

In case no algorithm default is given, then it will check the input parameters, and will supply the appropriate algorithm with the data (see Algorithm as a Service).

5.2.5.4 *Algorithm as a Service*

In this function, all available algorithms are standardised to run under a common ecosystem, or a set of services that will host different algorithms, prepare the data to be in a form recognisable by them, and finally collect the information so that to transfer it to the next stage.

Each service will be compliant to REST API practices and will use a queueing mechanism (such as MQTT).

5.2.6 USER INTERFACE

This section provides an overview and snapshot of the current understanding and design of the Graphical User Interface (GUI) of the MES-CoBraD System. The GUI is a work in progress, and it will be detailed (and possibly modified) as our work toward the implementation and integration of the system progresses. Many of the mock-ups of the GUI presented below are still under discussion and will likely go through modifications. The mock-ups may either present schematically the functional elements of pages, or, in some cases, we went a step further providing also suggested graphical implementations.

The MES-CoBraD System will have an integrated common Graphical User Interface. The GUI will follow the logic of the broad process areas which are dealt with by the overall system and not necessarily the logic of component boundaries – since the components often need to work with each other to provide the various services. This means that the components and the switch between them will be broadly seamless for the end users. The main processes identified are:

1. Data (work): this involves processes related to data upload, access, data collection, etc.

⁵ <https://www.docker.com/>

⁶ <https://www.python.org/>

2. (Data) Analysis: this involves data analysis processes and procedures available to end users mainly for research but possibly also for clinical processes.
3. Clinical Processes: these refer to processes referring to clinical trials (for research purposes) or procedures and protocols for diagnosis and treatment.
4. Knowledge Base: providing an organised way to share knowledge.
5. System Administration: various functionalities for use for system administration.

These process areas also become the principal elements of the main menu. Figure 24 below presents schematically the main menu of the GUI. We foresee at this moment that the main menu will have a depth of maximum 3 levels (possibly 2 based on further discussion among partners). The need for further splits may be satisfied by providing further options on actual pages (by means of clickable items, pictures plus text or widgets).

Figure 24 – Main Menu Presentation

In the following we explain the elements of the main menu (except for the primary items already explained). It should be noted that the elements of the main menu like other elements on pages and pages themselves will

be visible depending on the user's role and rights of access. So, for example, regular users will not see the System Administration item.

6. Data

- a. My datasets: allows the user to view a list of datasets and from there execute a series of operations on the dataset.
- b. Data upload: allows the user to upload secondary datasets by following a strict procedure which respects rights of access, data licensing, and data privacy (this procedure is not fully defined yet, but we are working on it).
- c. Data collection: allows the user to collect primary data by means of questionnaires. The user can create questionnaires, apply them online or apply them by printing, on paper completion by respondents and further transcribing them into the system.

7. Analysis

- a. Various statistical analysis procedures (and possible machine learning algorithms) will be made available for data analysis.

8. Clinical processes:

- a. Clinical trials: Allows users to run clinical trials.
- b. Diagnosis and treatment: allow users to run various procedures and protocols for diagnosis and treatment.

9. Knowledge base

- a. Sub items have not been defined yet.

10. System administration

- a. Sub items have not been defined yet.

6 ADVANCED ANALYTICS MOCKUPS

The sections present the analysis of the advanced analytics mockups providing the presentation of user interface, information on the expert system and process modelling and management, query builder and data analytics. Information on the hypothesis testing interface, visualizations and AI are also reported.

6.1 USER INTERFACE

Based on the main menu discussed on 5.2.6 we present Figure 25 below a general mock-up of the main page as it appears after the user is logged in (and assuming for now that the user has broad rights (as a scientist or clinician) but not the rights of a system administrators).

Figure 25 – Home Page Mock-up

The items other than the main menu are largely self-explanatory. The MES-CoBraD logo will appear in the header, a search bar will be available for text content of the site (mainly the knowledge base), an alert bell will be available for alerts (primary on reaching some milestones on clinical processes) and a user icon will appear where, by clicking, the user can access some account management functionalities.

The other content on the main page is under discussion. While we were considering a dashboard like content,

we decided that it may be inappropriate since the System is not based on continuous streams of data coming in. We are considering the content as being static text and pictures.

Prior to the full main page being displayed with an extended main menu, a page 0, or a barebones home page (with only the Knowledge Base and basic information about the MES-CoBraD System and Project) will be shown for non-logged-in users. From there the user can register (sign up) or log in (sign in).

A proposed register form is provided in Figure 26 below. The data fields still need discussion and revisiting, and it is probably not final at this moment.as the overall process of registration of users is defined.

Register

First name

Last name

Adress

ID Number

Medic

Phone

E-mail

I hereby consent to the processing of the personal data that I have provided and declare my agreement with the data protection regulations

Figure 26 – Register Form Mock-up

Figure 27 below displays a mock-up of the login form.

Login

A login form with two input fields: 'Username' and 'Password'. Below the fields are two buttons: 'Login' and 'Register'. A link 'Forgot your password?' is centered below the buttons.

Figure 27 – Login Form Mock-up

In the following we present some pages for various functionalities of the system which are early proposals for discussion.

Figure 28 - Incoming Data Monitoring Page Mock-up

Figure 29 below presents a page where several options are available in continuation of the main menu (to avoid too many levels of depth of the menu). The proposal here is that these options are presented in the form of rectangles with suggestive graphics and text. This example is about diagnostic guidelines, but the style can be applied for any case where further depth of options than the main menu provides is necessary.

Figure 29 – Options Page Mock-up

Figure 30 below presents an example of a presentation of an article type page with text and possible graphics. To make it more readable the article is broken into several sections visible on the left side menu, these sections can be expanded/made visible or contracted/made invisible.

Figure 30 – Article Page Mock-up

A few other full graphics mockup pages are presented bellow as current proposals to facilitate further discussion.

Figure 31 below presents a proposal for a view patient profile page. While the page is fully graphically implemented, the exact details of the page (especially the data fields) need to be worked out. Furthermore, this variant of the page would be implemented in the Edge Module as it presents non-anonymised/pseudonymised

data. An anonymised/ pseudonymised version of the page may be available on the platform.

Figure 31 – Patient Profile Page Mock-up

Figure 32 below presents a view patient list mock-up page. As explained for the previous figure, this page may need to have both anonymised/ pseudonymised and non-anonymised variants.

Figure 32 – View Patient List Mockup Page

6.2 EXPERT SYSTEM - PROCESS MODELLING AND MANAGEMENT

The GUI of Expert System is based on the core interface of MES-CoBraD provided by 6.1 and just as the general GUI, the mockups presented in this chapter, are not in final stage and may change during the project.

Figure 33 shows the site used to create a workflow. The user has the freedom to create tasks, define operators and create connections to the Data Lake. The same image is displayed to the user when he wants to edit an existing workflow.

Figure 33 – Creation of a workflow

Figure 34 shows the list of all workflows that have been created, along with their descriptions, the ability to execute, edit and/or delete it.

Figure 34 – List of all available workflows

Finally, Figure 35 shows the ability of performing a clinical process where the available steps and the information of each step are displayed. Here, the user can interact with workflows and data transferred between steps.

Figure 35 – Clinical process execution

6.3 QUERY BUILDER

A mock-up of the interface of the Query Builder is presented below. A clinician/researcher using this Interface

will be able to request specific data from the DataLake choosing the respective tables, columns and aggregations. For instance, in the Figure 36 below, a user has selected data from Table 2 and Table 4, the grouping of column B and Column D and applies the SUM aggregation function in column A. Also, the user has asked only the first 200 records that equals to “value” in Column A.

The screenshot shows the 'Query Builder' interface with the following configuration:

- Select Tables:** Table 1 (unchecked), Table 2 (checked), Table 3 (unchecked), Table 4 (checked).
- Select Grouping Columns:** Column A (unchecked), Column B (checked), Column C (unchecked), Column D (checked).
- Select Aggregation Column:** Column A (dropdown).
- Select Aggregation:** SUM (dropdown).
- Limit:** 200 (input field).
- Choose column:** Column A (dropdown), followed by an equals sign (=) dropdown, and a 'Value' input field.
- Execute:** A prominent blue button at the bottom.

Figure 36 – Interface of the Query Builder

This mockup constitutes a first version of the Query Builder’s Interface. The next versions will include more functionalities and capabilities for more complex queries.

6.4 DATA ANALYTICS

A mock-up of the interface of the Data Analytics is presented below. In Figure 37 a list of the available analyses related with the electrophysiology signals is presented. In each “Analysis card” a short description is provided along with some basic functionalities (execute, modify and/or delete).

Figure 37 – List of all the available analyses for the electrophysiology signals

Moreover, in Figure 38, in Figure 39, Figure 40, Figure 41, Figure 41, and Figure 42 six representative instances of analysis are presented. In general, prior to performing each analysis several parameters must be provided to capture users' preferences.

More specifically, Figure 38 defines the list of the parameters that will be passed to the algorithm for the detection of spindles. The user has to define the spindles' frequency range, the broad band frequency range, and the duration of spindles. Next, the user clicks the "Execute" button for performing the analysis.

The screenshot shows the 'Detection of Spindles' configuration form. It features the MES-CoBraD logo at the top left. The title 'Detection of Spindles' is centered at the top. Below the title, there are three rows of input fields. Each row starts with the text 'Please fill in', followed by a parameter name, and then a text input box. The parameters are: 'Spindles Frequency range' with input 'range_min, range_max'; 'Broad Band Frequency range' with input 'range_min, range_max'; and 'Duration of the spindles' with input 'minimum duration, maximum duration'. At the bottom center, there is a dark blue 'Execute' button.

Figure 38 – List of parameters for the detection of spindles

In Figure 39, the user must select and fill in the parameters, which are required for the computation of the Short-Time Fourier Transform (STFT). Specifically, the user has to choose the type of the window, which is available in the drop-down list. Also, the user must fill in the number of points to overlap between segments,

the length of each segment, as well as the length of the FFT used. Finally, the user clicks the “Execute” button for performing the analysis.

Short-Time Fourier Transform		
Please select	window	<input type="text" value="Hann"/> Hamming etc.
Please fill in	Number of points to overlap between segments	<input type="text" value="int"/>
Please fill in	length of each segment	<input type="text" value="int"/>
Please fill in	length of the FFT used	<input type="text" value="int"/>
<input type="button" value="Execute"/>		

Figure 39 – List of parameters for the computation of the STFT

In Figure 40, the user chooses the parameters required for the ARIMA model. Specifically, the user is able to define the test size, in order that the ARIMA model is trained using the train set. Thus, the error in the test set can be calculated. At the same time, the user is capable of choosing the future patient data in seconds (or samples). Next, the user is able to define the method and the information criterion, which is used to select the best ARIMA model. Finally, the user clicks the “Execute” button for starting the analysis.

The screenshot shows a web interface for configuring an ARIMA model. At the top left is the MES-CoBraD logo. The main heading is "Time-series Forecasting using an ARIMA model". Below this, there are four input fields:

- test_size**: A text input field with the placeholder "int".
- future patient data (in seconds)**: A text input field with the placeholder "int".
- method**: A dropdown menu with "lbfgs" selected, and "Newton-Raphson" and "etc." visible in the list.
- information_criterion**: A dropdown menu with "aic" selected, and "bic" and "etc." visible in the list.

At the bottom center is a dark blue button labeled "Execute".

Figure 40 – List of parameters given to an ARIMA model

In Figure 41, the user defines the parameters for the calculation of the power spectral density using the Welch's method. Specifically, the user is able to choose the window from a drop-down list, which includes all the available windows. Also, the user is capable of filling in the number of points to overlap between segments, the length of each segment, and the length of the FFT used. Finally, the user clicks the "Execute" button in order the analysis to be started.

The screenshot shows a web interface for configuring the Power Spectral Density (Welch's Method). At the top left is the MES-CoBraD logo. The main heading is "Power Spectral Density (Welch's Method)". Below this, there are four input fields:

- window**: A dropdown menu with "Hann" selected, and "Hamming" and "etc." visible in the list.
- Number of points to overlap between segments**: A text input field with the placeholder "int".
- length of each segment**: A text input field with the placeholder "int".
- length of the FFT used**: A text input field with the placeholder "int".

At the bottom center is a dark blue button labeled "Execute".

Figure 41 – List of parameters for the computation of the Power Spectral Density using the Welch's method

Figure 42 illustrates the interface for the autocorrelation function. More specifically, the user is able to define

the alpha value, so that the confidence intervals be returned. Also, the user is able to select whether the autocorrelation function will be computed via FFT or not. At the same time, the user will be able to choose if the Ljung-Box q statistic will be returned for each autocorrelation coefficient. Finally, the user clicks the “Execute” button for conducting the analysis.

The screenshot shows a form titled "Autocorrelation" with the MES-CoBraD logo in the top left. The form contains three rows of input fields:

- Row 1: "Please fill in" label, "alpha" parameter, and a text input field containing "scalar".
- Row 2: "Please select" label, "fft" parameter, and a dropdown menu showing "True or False".
- Row 3: "Please select" label, "Ljung-Box q statistic for each autocorrelation coefficient" parameter, and a dropdown menu showing "True or False".

At the bottom center of the form is a dark blue button labeled "Execute".

Figure 42 – List of parameters for the computation of the autocorrelation function

6.5 HYPOTHESIS TESTING INTERFACE

A mock-up of the interface of the Hypothesis Testing is presented below. In Figure 43 a list of the hypothesis scenarios, created by the user, is presented. In each “Hypothesis card” a short description is provided along with some basic functionalities (present the result, modify/create a new instance, and/or delete).

The screenshot shows the "Hypothesis Testing" interface. At the top left is the MES-CoBraD logo and a hamburger menu icon. The title "Hypothesis Testing" is displayed. On the top right, there is a search bar with the placeholder "Search portal...", a magnifying glass icon, a user profile icon, and a blue "Create" button. Below the title, there is a filter button labeled "All". The main area contains six "Hypothesis cards" arranged in a 2x3 grid. Each card has a blue header with the title "Hypothesis 1" through "Hypothesis 6", a white body with the text "Short Description.", and a footer with three icons: a right-pointing chevron, a pencil, and a trash can. A "Results" tooltip is visible over the chevron icon of the first card. At the bottom center, there is a pagination control with a left arrow, the number "1", an ellipsis "...", the letter "n", and a right arrow.

Figure 43 – List of all the created hypothesis scenarios

The user selects the hypothesis that he/she wants to test. Then, as illustrated in Figure 44, the user selects

samples from the Data Lake via the Query Builder Component. After that, the user is able to choose one of the following:

- > Correlations
- > Data Distribution
- > Homoscedasticity
- > Statistical Tests for Hypothesis Testing

Figure 44 – Initial Interface

In case that the user clicks the option “Data Distribution”, the user is transferred to another interface, which is shown in Figure 45, where there are available many techniques, which let the user check if the data sample deviates from a Gaussian distribution. This is a very important step before conducting a statistical test. As mentioned in Section 2.2.5, one assumption of t-test is the normality, which indicates that both samples are approximately normally distributed. As one can easily observe in Figure 45, the user chooses first the sample, which will be used for checking if it follows a normal distribution. Next, for checking the assumption of normality, the user is able to choose one of the following methods:

- > Visual Normality Checks
 - Quantile – Quantile (Q-Q) plot
 - Histogram
- > Statistical Normality Tests
 - Shapiro Wilk Test, which tests the null hypothesis that the data was drawn from a normal distribution. It returns the test statistic along with the p-value for the hypothesis test.
 - D’ Agostino’s K-squared test, which tests the null hypothesis that a sample comes from a normal distribution. It is based on D’Agostino and Pearson’s test [137][138] that combines skew and kurtosis to produce an omnibus test of normality. It returns the statistic and the p-value.

- Anderson – Darling test, which tests the null hypothesis that a sample is drawn from a population that follows a normal distribution. It must be also noted that the function implemented in SciPy library in Python works for normal, exponential, logistic, or Gumber distributions.

Figure 45 – Methods for checking whether the data samples follow a normal distribution

In case that the user clicks the option “Q-Q plot”, as shown in Figure 45, the user is transferred to another interface, which is illustrated in Figure 46. This interface shows a Q-Q plot of the quantiles of the data sample versus the quantiles of a normal distribution.

In case that the user clicks the option “Histogram”, as shown in Figure 45, the user is transferred to another interface, which is shown in Figure 47. In Figure 47, we can see a Gaussian-like shape to the data.

In case that the user clicks the other options, i.e., “Shapiro-Wilk test”, “D’ Agostino’s K-squared test”, and “Anderson-Darling test”, as shown in Figure 45, the user is transferred to another interface, which is shown in Figure 48, where the user can see the test statistic and the p-value.

Figure 46 – Q-Q plot

Figure 47 – Histogram

Hypothesis 1	
Test statistic	<input type="text" value="Number"/>
p-value	<input type="text" value="Number"/>

Figure 48 – Test statistic and p-value

In case that the user clicks the option “Homoscedasticity”, as shown in Figure 44, the user is transferred to another interface, which is illustrated in Figure 49. It is known that the assumption of homoscedasticity must be satisfied, in order for the associated p-value to be valid. For example, the ANOVA test includes the assumption of homoscedasticity, meaning that the population standard deviations of the groups are all equal. As shown in Figure 49, the user is able to choose two techniques for checking whether the population standard deviations of the groups are all equal. First, the user chooses the samples, which will be checked and then the user chooses one of the following techniques for checking the property of homoscedasticity:

- › Bartlett’s test. It must be noted that for samples from significantly non-normal populations, Levene’s test is more robust.
- › Levene test, which is an alternative to Bartlett’s test in the case where there are significant deviations from normality.

In case that the user clicks the option “Levene Test”, as shown in Figure 49, the user is transferred to another interface, which is illustrated in Figure 50, in order to choose one of the following parameters:

- › “mean”: Recommended for symmetric, moderate-tailed distributions [139]
- › “median”: Recommended for skewed (non-normal) distributions
- › “trimmed”: Recommended for heavy-tailed distributions

The options for “median” and “trimmed” refer to [140]. The test is known as Brown-Forsythe test.

Finally, after selecting the Levene test or the Bartlett’s test, the user is transferred to another interface, which is illustrated in Figure 48, where the user can see the test statistic and the p-value.

Figure 49 – Methods for checking the assumption of homoscedasticity

Figure 50 – Levene Test

In case that the user checks the option “Correlations”, as shown in Figure 44, the user is transferred to another interface, which is illustrated in Figure 51. Specifically, after selecting the samples, the user is able to choose one of the following methods for computing the correlations:

- Pearson Correlation, which measures the linear relationship between two datasets

- › Spearman Correlation, which is a nonparametric measure of the monotonicity of the relationship between two datasets.
- › Kendall's Tau, which is a measure of the correspondence between two rankings.
- › Point biserial correlation, which is used to measure the relationship between a binary variable, x , and a continuous variable, y .

By clicking one of these options, the user is transferred to an interface as illustrated in Figure 48, where the user sees the test statistic (correlation coefficient) and the p-value.

Figure 51 – Methods for calculating the correlations

In case that the user checks the option “Statistical Tests for Hypothesis Testing”, as shown in Figure 44, the user is transferred in another interface, which is shown in Figure 52. The user is able to choose which statistical test fits best the assumptions of normality, homoscedasticity, etc. Specifically, as one can easily observe, there are both parametric and non-parametric statistical tests. For instance, the ANOVA test has important assumptions, including (i) the samples are independent, (ii) each sample is from a normally distributed population, and (iii) homoscedasticity. If these assumptions are not true, then the user is able to exploit either the Kruskal-Wallis H-test or the Alexander-Govern test. To be more precise, the Alexander-Govern test does not assume on homoscedasticity.

In addition, the Mann-Whitney U rank test is for independent samples. For related/paired samples, one could use the Wilcoxon signed-rank test.

Figure 52 – Options for parametric and non-parametric statistical tests

After selecting the statistical test, the user is transferred in another interface, which is illustrated in Figure 53. More specifically, Figure 53 illustrates the interface for performing a specific statistical hypothesis test. In this case, the user performs an independent t-test. In this interface, the user is able to define some additional parameters for conducting the statistical test. For this purpose:

- › the user needs to choose the data samples to be compared.
- › enter some critical parameters for conducting the test, using a drop-down menu or a numeric input field. The “alternative” parameter defines the alternative hypothesis. The following options are available:
 - ‘two-sided’: the means of the distributions underlying the samples are unequal
 - ‘less’: the mean of the distribution underlying the first sample is less than the mean of the distribution underlying the second sample
 - ‘greater’: the mean of the distribution underlying the first sample is greater than the mean of the distribution underlying the second sample.

The ‘trim’ parameter defines the fraction of elements to be trimmed from each end of the input samples. If 0, no elements will be trimmed from either side.

After performing the test (by clicking “calculate”), the user can see the calculated test statistic and p-value.

Figure 53 – Independent t-test

These mockups constitute a preliminary version of the hypothesis testing interface. In the next versions the parameters required by the user will be enriched and redefined. Also, in case of multiple tests, the user will be able to exploit some methods for testing and adjustment of p-values, including the Bonferroni correction, the Benjamini-Hochberg correction, and many more.

6.6 DATA AND RESULTS VISUALISATION

The results of the analyses, which are illustrated in Figure 37-Figure 42, are shown in Figure 54, Figure 55, Figure 56, Figure 57, and Figure 58.

More specifically, Figure 54 illustrates the visualization dashboard for the results obtained by the ARIMA model. The user is able to get a summary of the ARIMA model, see the future values of an electrophysiology signal, i.e., EEG, and get the diagnostic plots. To be more precise, the function `plot.diagnostics` produces a 2x2 plot grid with the following plots (ordered clockwise from top left):

- › Standardised residuals over time
- › Histogram plus estimated density of standardised residuals, along with a Normal(0,1) density plotted for reference.
- › Normal Q-Q plot, with Normal reference line.
- › Correlogram

Figure 54 – Visualization Output of the ARIMA model

In addition, Figure 55 illustrates the results of the analysis shown in Figure 42.

Figure 55 – Autocorrelation

In Figure 56, the results of the analysis illustrated in Figure 38 are presented.

Figure 56 – Detection of spindles

Figure 57 illustrates the results of the STFT algorithm shown in Figure 39.

Figure 57 – Short-Time Fourier Transform

Finally, Figure 58 illustrates the results of the analysis shown in Figure 41.

Figure 58 – Power Spectral Density using the Welch's method

7 APIS' SPECIFICATION

The sections present the APIs and their specifications that are available through the MES-CoBraD platform. These include the Query Builder, the Expert System, the Data Analytics, the Data Lake, the Data Visualization and the Artificial Intelligence. Each chapter consists of two parts, the “Overview Paths” and the “Component - Schemas”.

The first one provides all the information the API’s endpoints provide. Each path displays the API call method, the URI request path, and a small description. Additionally, they provide the different responses that we might get during the different use cases and the requirements needed to successfully execute each API call.

The “Component - Schemas” provide the definitions of an API model entity. These entities are the objects that are expected to be retrieved at a successful API call response.

7.1 QUERY BUILDER AND MES-COBRAD DATA LAKE

7.1.1 QUERY BUILDER APIS

7.1.1.1 POST /complex/select/query Complex Select Query

Build a Select SQL query

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Successful Response <i>Content</i> application/json	No Links
422	Validation Error <i>Content</i> application/json	No Links

7.1.1.2 POST /complex/group/query Complex Group Query

Build a Group by SQL query

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Successful Response <i>Content</i> application/json	No Links
422	Validation Error <i>Content</i> application/json	No Links

7.1.1.3 POST /complex/join/query Complex Join Query

Build a Join query

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Successful Response <i>Content</i> application/json	No Links

Code	Description	Links
422	Validation Error <i>Content</i> application/json	No Links

7.1.1.4 [POST /execute_query](#) Execute Query

Execute query

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Successful Response <i>Content</i> application/json	No Links

422	Validation Error <i>Content</i> application/json	No Links
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7.1.1.5 [GET /tables](#) Get Tables

Get all the available tables

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Successful Response <i>Content</i> application/json	No Links

7.1.1.6 [GET /tables/{table}](#) Get Columns of Table

Get all the columns of a table

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
path	<i>table</i> <i>required</i>		string

Responses

Code	Description	Links
------	-------------	-------

Successful Response

200	<i>Content</i> application/json	No Links
422	Validation Error <i>Content</i> application/json	No Links

7.1.1.7 [GET /buckets](#) Get List of Buckets

Get all the available buckets

Responses

Code	Description	Links
	Successful Response	
200	<i>Content</i> application/json	No Links

7.1.1.8 [GET /buckets/{bucket}](#) Get objects of a bucket

Get the objects of a bucket

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
path	<i>bucket</i> <i>required</i>		string

Responses

Code	Description	Links
	Successful Response	
200	<i>Content</i> application/json	No Links
	Validation Error	
422	<i>Content</i> application/json	No Links

7.1.1.9 [POST /buckets/{bucket}/save](#) Save Object as Csv in a bucket

Save the output after the execution of a query in a bucket

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
path	bucket <i>required</i>		string

Responses

Code	Description	Links
	Successful Response	
200	<i>Content</i> application/json	No Links
	Validation Error	
422	<i>Content</i> application/json	No Links

7.1.1.10 Data Lake APIs

7.1.1.10.1 Metadata Manager APIs

The Metadata Manager is the component in charge of dealing with the questionnaires and variables metadata.

The APIs are totally RESTful and provide both GET, POST, DELETE and PATCH verbs over the following resources:

- Concepts
- Variables
- Languages
- Questionnaires
- Questions
- STS Categories

Moreover, it allows to manage the following relations:

- Concepts – Variables
- Questions – Variables
- STS Categories – Variables

The complete specification is available in OpenAPI v3 format in the Annex II.

7.1.1.10.2 Object Storage APIs

The MES-CoBraD Object Storage is entirely provided by the Digital Enabler platform. It exposes a set of

APIs that are totally compliant with the AWS S3 APIs specifications.

For this reason, all the APIs exposed are compliant with the specification available in the [Amazon S3 API Reference](#).

7.1.2 COMPONENTS – SCHEMAS

7.1.2.1 GroupItem

Properties

Name	Description	Schema
aggregation_metrics <i>required</i>	Aggregation metric to be used as aggregation metric in GROUPS Title: Aggregation Metrics	< > array
aggregation_columns <i>required</i>	Column to apply aggregations Title: Aggregation Columns	< > array
grouping_columns <i>required</i>	List for declaring columns to be used in GROUP BY statement Title: Grouping Columns	< > array
table <i>required</i>	table to get data Title: Table	string
connection_name <i>optional</i>	connection from Presto Title: Connection Name Default: connection_name	string
schema_name <i>optional</i>	Connection schema from Presto Title: Schema Name Default: schema	string
where_column <i>optional</i>	column to use for filtering results Title: Where Column	string
where_clause_term <i>optional</i>	term to use for where condition value Title: Where Clause Term	string

<i>limit optional</i>	LIMIT parameter Title: Limit	integer
<i>aggregation_metrics_alias_list optional</i>	alias for aggregation output Title: Aggregation Metrics Alias List	< > array
<i>not_condition optional</i>	if True enable NOT condition Title: Not Condition Default: false	boolean
<i>in_values optional</i>	values for conditional WHERE IN statement Title: In Values	< > array
<i>between_values optional</i>	list with 2 values for BETWEEN statement Title: Between Values	< > array
<i>like_pattern optional</i>	string to use in LIKE pattern Title: Like Pattern	string
<i>where_symbol optional</i>	symbol to use checking where condition Title: Where Symbol	string
<i>order_by_column optional</i>	column to use for results ordering Title: Order By Column	string
<i>order optional</i>	ASC/DESC order Title: Order	string
<i>return_dict optional</i>	Return output as dictionary Title: Return Dict Default: true	boolean
<i>if_pandas optional</i>	Return output as pd.DataFrame Title: If Pandas Default: false	boolean

Return output suitable for column chart

<i>if_column_chart optional</i>	Title: If Column Chart Default: false	boolean
<i>AND_optional</i>	AND statement for having multiple WHERE clauses Title: And	< > array
<i>OR_optional</i>	OR statement for having multiple WHERE clauses Title: Or	< > array
<i>username optional</i>	user that performs the query Title: Username	string

7.1.2.2 JoinItem

Properties

Name	Description	Schema
<i>join_tables required</i>	tables to join Title: Join Tables	< > array
<i>connection_name optional</i>	connection from Presto Title: Connection Name Default: connection_name	string
<i>schema_name optional</i>	Connection schema from Presto Title: Schema Name Default: schema	string
<i>columns_table 1 optional</i>	columns from table 1 Title: Columns Table1	< > array
<i>columns_table 2 optional</i>	columns from table 2 Title: Columns Table2	< > array
<i>columns_table 3 optional</i>	columns from table 3 Title: Columns Table3	< > array

columns_table_list <i>optional</i>	list columns from all tables Title: Columns Table List	< > array
aggregation_metrics_table1 <i>optional</i>	aggregation metrics to use AVG/SUM/COUNT for columns in table 1 Title: Aggregation Metrics Table1	< > array
aggregation_metrics_table2 <i>optional</i>	aggregation metrics to use AVG/SUM/COUNT for columns in table 2 Title: Aggregation Metrics Table2	< > array
aggregation_metrics_table3 <i>optional</i>	aggregation metrics to use AVG/SUM/COUNT for columns in table 3 Title: Aggregation Metrics Table3	< > array
aggregation_metrics_table_list <i>optional</i>	aggregation metrics list to use AVG/SUM/COUNT for all columns Title: Aggregation Metrics Table List	< > array
aggregation_metrics_alias_list_table1 <i>optional</i>	alias for aggregation output for columns in table 1 Title: Aggregation Metrics Alias List Table1	< > array
aggregation_metrics_alias_list_table2 <i>optional</i>	alias for aggregation output for columns in table 2 Title: Aggregation Metrics Alias List Table2	< > array
aggregation_metrics_alias_list_table3 <i>optional</i>	alias for aggregation output for columns in table 3 Title: Aggregation Metrics Alias List Table3	< > array
aggregation_metrics_alias_list <i>optional</i>	alias for aggregation output for all columns Title: Aggregation Metrics Alias List	< > array

<code>grouping_columns</code> <i>optional</i>	list of dicts of grouping columns Title: Grouping Columns	< > array
<code>join_types</code> <i>required</i>	list of dicts that describe the join Title: Join Types	< > array
<code>order_by_column</code> <i>optional</i>	column to use for results ordering Title: Order By Column	< > array
<code>where_column</code> <i>optional</i>	column to use for filtering results Title: Where Column	string
<code>where_table</code> <i>optional</i>	table to use for filtering results Title: Where Table	string
<code>where_symbol</code> <i>optional</i>	symbol to use checking where condition Title: Where Symbol	string
<code>where_clause_term</code> <i>optional</i>	term to use for where condition value Title: Where Clause Term	string
<code>in_values</code> <i>optional</i>	values for conditional WHERE IN statement Title: In Values	< > array
<code>not_condition</code> <i>optional</i>	if True enable NOT condition Title: Not Condition Default: false	boolean
<code>between_values</code> <i>optional</i>	list with 2 values for BETWEEN statement Title: Between Values	< > array
<code>like_pattern</code> <i>optional</i>	string to use in LIKE pattern Title: Like Pattern	string
<code>limit</code> <i>optional</i>	LIMIT parameter Title: Limit	integer

<i>AND_optional</i>	AND statement for having multiple WHERE clauses Title: And	< > array
<i>OR_optional</i>	OR statement for having multiple WHERE clauses Title: Or	< > array

7.1.2.3 SelectItem

Properties

Name	Description	Schema
<i>table_required</i>	table to get data Title: Table	string
<i>connection_name_optional</i>	connection from Presto Title: Connection Name Default: connection_name	string
<i>schema_name_optional</i>	Connection schema from Presto Title: Schema Name Default: schema	string
<i>columns_optional</i>	columns to get from table Title: Columns	< > array
<i>all_optional</i>	select all columns for table if True Title: All Default: false	boolean
<i>aggregation_metrics_optional</i>	aggregation metrics to use AVG/SUM/COUNT Title: Aggregation Metrics	< > array
<i>aggregation_columns_optional</i>	aggregation columns to use for applying metrics Title: Aggregation Columns	< > array
<i>aggregation_metrics_alias_list_optional</i>	alias for aggregation output Title: Aggregation Metrics Alias List	< > array

<code>where_clause_term</code> <i>optional</i>	term to use for where condition value Title: Where Clause Term	string
<code>in_values</code> <i>optional</i>	values for conditional WHERE IN statement Title: In Values	< > array
<code>not_condition</code> <i>optional</i>	if True enable NOT condition Title: Not Condition Default: false	boolean
<code>between_values</code> <i>optional</i>	list with 2 values for BETWEEN statement Title: Between Values	< > array
<code>like_pattern</code> <i>optional</i>	string to use in LIKE pattern Title: Like Pattern	string
<code>order</code> <i>optional</i>	ASC/DESC order Title: Order	string
<code>order_by_column</code> <i>optional</i>	column to use for results ordering Title: Order By Column	string
<code>limit</code> <i>optional</i>	LIMIT parameter Title: Limit	integer
<code>where_symbol</code> <i>optional</i>	symbol to use checking where condition Title: Where Symbol	string
<code>return_dict</code> <i>optional</i>	Return output as dictionary Title: Return Dict Default: true	boolean
<code>if_pandas</code> <i>optional</i>	Return output as pd.DataFrame Title: If Pandas Default: false	boolean

<code>many_aggregations</code> <i>optional</i>	Many aggregations to apply: <code>{ ' AGG (COLUMN_NAME)' : ' ALIAS' }</code>	object
	Title: Many Aggregations	
<code>AND_</code> <i>optional</i>	AND statement for having multiple WHERE clauses	< > array
	Title: And	
<code>where_column</code> <i>optional</i>	column to use for filtering results	string
	Title: Where Column	
<code>OR_</code> <i>optional</i>	OR statement for having multiple WHERE clauses	< > array
	Title: Or	

7.2 EXPERT SYSTEM - PROCESS MODELLING AND MANAGEMENT

7.2.1 OVERVIEW PATHS

7.2.1.1 GET /run/ Read Runs

Retrieve workflows with their metadata.

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	limit optional		integer
query	skip optional		integer

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Successful Response Content application/json Title: Response Read Runs Run Get	No Links

404	Not Found	No Links
422	Validation Error Content application/json	No Links

7.2.1.2 GET /run/{run_id} Read Run

Get specific workflow run by ID.

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
path	run_id required		string (uuid)

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Successful Response Content application/json	No Links
404	Not Found	No Links
422	Validation Error Content application/json	No Links

7.2.1.3 GET /run/{run_id}/next Show Next Task

Retrieve running instance and return next task(s).

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
path	run_id required		string (uuid)

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Successful Response Content application/json	No Links
404	Not Found	No Links
422	Validation Error Content application/json	No Links

7.2.1.4 GET /run/{run_id}/step/{step_id} Run Specific Task

Initiate next step (specific task).

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
path	run_id required		string (uuid)
path	step_id required		string (uuid)

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Successful Response Content application/json	No Links
404	Not Found	No Links
422	Validation Error Content application/json	No Links

7.2.1.5 PUT /run/{run_id}/step/{step_id} Exec Specific Task Actions

Perform actions for a given execution step. The parameters needed in body depend on the step/task type.

The MES-CoBraD project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No 965422

If you want to execute a "Gateway", then {"step_id": <uuid>} is needed. If you want to execute a "Task", then {"action": "exec"/"complete"} is needed. If you want to execute anything else, pass an empty body.

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
path	run_id required		string (uuid)
path	step_id required		string (uuid)

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Successful Response Content application/json	No Links
404	Not Found	No Links
422	Validation Error Content application/json	No Links

7.2.1.6 GET /run/{run_id}/step/{step_id}/ping Ping Task Status

Get the status of specific task.

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
path	run_id required		string (uuid)
path	step_id required		string (uuid)

Responses

Code	Description	Links
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200	Successful Response Content application/json	No Links
404	Not Found	No Links
422	Validation Error Content application/json	No Links

7.2.1.7 GET /workflow/ Read Workflows

Retrieve workflows with their metadata.

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	limit optional		integer
query	skip optional		integer

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Successful Response Content application/json Title: Response Read Workflows Workflow Get	No Links
404	Not Found	No Links
Code	Description	Links
422	Validation Error Content application/json	No Links

7.2.1.8 [POST /workflow/ Create Workflow](#)

Create new workflow.

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Successful Response Content application/json	No Links
404	Not Found	No Links
422	Validation Error Content application/json	No Links

7.2.1.9 [GET /workflow/entity_types Read Entity Types](#)

Get all available workflow entity types.

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Successful Response Content application/json	No Links
404	Not Found	No Links

7.2.1.10 [GET /workflow/{workflow_id} Read Workflow](#)

Get workflow by ID.

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
path	workflow_id required		string (uuid)

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Successful Response Content application/json	No Links
404	Not Found	No Links
422	Validation Error Content application/json	No Links

7.2.1.11 PUT /workflow/{workflow_id} Update Workflow

Update a workflow.

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
path	workflow_id required		string (uuid)

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Successful Response Content application/json	No Links
404	Not Found	No Links
422	Validation Error Content application/json	No Links

7.2.1.12 DELETE /workflow/{workflow_id} Destroy Workflow

Delete a workflow.

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
path	workflow_id required		string (uuid)

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Successful Response Content application/json	No Links
404	Not Found	No Links
422	Validation Error Content application/json	No Links

7.2.1.13 DELETE /workflow/{workflow_id}/revert Revert Workflow

Revert the deletion of a workflow.

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
path	workflow_id required		string (uuid)

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Successful Response Content application/json	No Links
404	Not Found	No Links
422	Validation Error Content application/json	No Links

7.2.1.14 GET /workflow/{workflow_id}/run Run Workflow

Initiate a workflow process

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
path	workflow_id required		string (uuid)

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Successful Response Content application/json	No Links
404	Not Found	No Links
422	Validation Error Content application/json	No Links

7.2.1.15 GET /workflow/{workflow_id}/task/{task_name} Read Task Details

Get task details given its name and workflow ID.

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
path	task_name required		string
path	workflow_id required		string (uuid)

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Successful Response Content application/json	No Links

404	Not Found	No Links
422	Validation Error Content application/json	No Links

7.2.2 COMPONENTS - SCHEMAS

7.2.2.1 Run

Properties

Name	Description	Schema
created_at optional	Title: Created At	String (date-time)
updated_at optional	Title: Updated At	String (date-time)
deleted_at optional	Title: Deleted At	String (date-time)
id optional	Title: Id	string (uuid)
workflow_id required	Title: Workflow Id	string (uuid)
state required	Title: State	Object
steps required	Title: Steps	< > array
queue required	Title: Queue	< > array

7.2.2.2 Workflow

Properties

Name	Description	Schema
created_at optional	Title: Created At	String (date-time)
updated_at optional	Title: Updated At	String (date-time)

deleted_at optional	Title: Deleted At	String (date-time)
id optional	Title: Id	string (uuid)
name required	Title: Name	String
description optional	Title: Description	String
tasks optional	Title: Tasks	Object
raw_diagram_data optional	Title: Raw Diagram Data	Object

7.2.2.3 WorkflowCreate

Properties

Name	Description	Schema
created_at optional	Title: Created At	String (date-time)
updated_at optional	Title: Updated At	String (date-time)
deleted_at optional	Title: Deleted At	String (date-time)
description optional	Title: Description	String
tasks optional	Title: Tasks	Object
raw_diagram_data optional	Title: Raw Diagram Data	Object
name required	Title: Name	String

7.2.2.4 WorkflowUpdate

Properties

Name	Description	Schema
created_at optional	Title: Created At	String (date-time)

updated_at optional	Title: Updated At	String (date-time)
deleted_at optional	Title: Deleted At	String (date-time)
description optional	Title: Description	String
tasks optional	Title: Tasks	Object
raw_diagram_data optional	Title: Raw Diagram Data	Object

7.3 DATA ANALYTICS

The data analytics and data and results visualisation modules as mentioned already use FASTAPI for the backend and react for the frontend. The API endpoints of FASTAPI are indicated by the type of request, get, post, etc. The react frontend utilises client side routing and are indicated accordingly. At those therefore we only describe the endpoint and query parameters, they always return the html and javascript that form the page itself.

GET /

A fallback root page in case of an error, not meant to be used normally

Responses	
Code	Description
	Successful Response
200	<i>Content</i> application/json

GET /read/users

Endpoint to get user used in Neurodesk application automatic sign in.

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	name required	Username provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
200	Successful Response <i>Content</i> application/json

GET /add/user

Endpoint to write new user used in Neurodesk automatic sign in.

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	password required	Automatic created password	string
query	name required	Username provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
200	Successful Response <i>Content</i> application/json

GET /list/channels

Endpoint that returns channels

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
200	Successful Response Content application/json

GET /return_autocorrelation

Endpoint that returns correlation of signal with delayed copy of itself.

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	input_qstat <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	boolean
query	input_missing <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	input_name <i>required</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	input_alpha <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	number

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	input_adjusted <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	boolean
query	input_fft <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	boolean
query	input_bartlett_confint <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	boolean
query	input_nlags <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
	Successful Response
200	<i>Content</i> application/json
	Validation Error
422	<i>Content</i> application/json

GET /return_partial_autocorrelation

Partially correlates signal with delayed copy of itself.

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	input_method <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	input_name <i>required</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	input_alpha <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	number
query	input_nlags <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	run_id <i>required</i>	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id <i>required</i>	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
	Successful Response
200	<i>Content</i> application/json
	Validation Error
422	<i>Content</i> application/json

GET /return_welch

Computes estimate of power spectral density.

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	input_name <i>required</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	input_npers eg <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	tmax <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	number
query	input_return_onesided <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	boolean
query	tmin <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	number
query	input_axis <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	input_average <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	input_noverlap <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	input_window <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	input_scaling <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	input_nfft <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	run_id <i>required</i>	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id <i>required</i>	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
	Successful Response
200	<i>Content</i> application/json
	Validation Error
422	<i>Content</i> application/json

GET /return_stft

Calculates short term fourier function of signal

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	input_padded <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	boolean
query	input_name <i>required</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	input_nperseg <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	tmax <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	number
query	input_return_onesided <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	boolean
query	input_boundary <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	tmin <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	number
query	input_axis <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	input_noverlap <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	input_window <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	input_nfft <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
Successful Response	
200	<i>Content</i> application/json
Validation Error	
422	<i>Content</i> application/json

GET /return_peaks

Finds local maxima of neighbouring values of signal.

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	input_width <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	input_name <i>required</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	input_threshold <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	
query	input_plateau_size <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	
query	input_height <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	
query	input_prominence <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	
query	input_distance <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	input_wlen <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	input_rel_height <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	number
query	input_width <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	
query	input_name <i>required</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	run_id <i>required</i>	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id <i>required</i>	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
	Successful Response
200	Content application/json

Responses	
Code	Description
	Validation Error
422	<i>Content</i> application/json

GET /return_periodogram

Computes a periodogram of the EEG signal.

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	input_name <i>required</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	tmax <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	number
query	input_return_onesided <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	boolean
query	tmin <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	number
query	input_axis <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	input_window <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	input_scaling <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	input_nfft <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	run_id <i>required</i>	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id <i>required</i>	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
	Successful Response
200	<i>Content</i> application/json
	Validation Error
422	<i>Content</i> application/json

GET /return_power_spectral_density

Calculates the power spectral density of a given signal with the multi-taper methods.

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	input_fmin <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	number
query	input_low_bias <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	boolean
query	input_fmax <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	number
query	input_name <i>required</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	input_output <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	tmax <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	number
query	input_norm alization <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	tmin <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	number

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	input_band width <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	number
query	input_verbo se <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	input_adapti ve <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	boolean
query	input_n_jobs <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
	Successful Response
200	<i>Content</i> application/json
	Validation Error
422	<i>Content</i> application/json

GET /return_alpha_delta_ratio

Estimates power spectral density using welch.

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	input_name <i>required</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	input_nperseg <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	tmax <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	number
query	input_return_onesided <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	boolean
query	tmin <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	number
query	input_axis <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	input_average <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	input_noverlap <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	input_window <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	input_scaling <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	input_nfft <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	run_id <i>required</i>	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id <i>required</i>	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
Successful Response	
200	<i>Content</i> application/json
Validation Error	
422	<i>Content</i> application/json

GET /return_asymmetry_indices

Calculates the asymmetry indices values of a signal.

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	input_name_2 <i>required</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	input_name_1 <i>required</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	input_nperseg <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	input_return_onesided <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	boolean
query	input_axis <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	input_average <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	input_noverlap <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	input_window <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	input_scaling <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	input_nfft <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
	Successful Response
200	<i>Content</i> application/json
	Validation Error
422	<i>Content</i> application/json

GET /return_alpha_variability

Estimates the alpha variability of a channel in a specific timeframe.

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	input_name <i>required</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	input_nperseg <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	tmax <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	number

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	input_return_onesided <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	boolean
query	tmin <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	number
query	input_axis <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	input_average <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	input_noverlap <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	input_window <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	input_scaling <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	input_nfft <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
	Successful Response
200	<i>Content</i> application/json
	Validation Error
422	<i>Content</i> application/json

GET /return_predictions

Predicts values of timeseries in specific timeframe.

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	method <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	future_seconds <i>required</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	test_size <i>required</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	information _criterion <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	name <i>required</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	start_p <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	max_p <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	max_q <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	start_q <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	run_id <i>required</i>	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id <i>required</i>	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
	Successful Response
200	<i>Content</i> application/json
	Validation Error
422	<i>Content</i> application/json

GET /spindles_detection

Detects sleep spindles.

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	input_name <i>required</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	freq_sp_low <i>required</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	freq_sp_high <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	freq_broad_low <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	freq_broad_high <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	duration_low <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	duration_high <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	min_distance <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	thresh_rel_pow <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	thresh_cor <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	thresh_rms <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	multi_only <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	boolean
query	remove_outliers <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	boolean
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
	Successful Response
200	<i>Content</i> application/json
	Validation Error
422	<i>Content</i> application/json

GET /slow_waves_detection

Detects sleep slow waves.

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	input_name <i>required</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	freq_sw_low <i>required</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	number
query	freq_sw_high <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	number
query	duration_neg_low <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	number
query	duration_neg_high <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	number
query	duration_pos_low <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	number
query	duration_pos_high <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	number
query	amp_neg_low <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	amp_neg_high <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	amp_pos_low <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	amp_pos_high <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	amp_peak_low <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	amp_peak_high <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	coupling <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	boolean
query	run_id <i>required</i>	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
	Successful Response
200	<i>Content</i> application/json
	Validation Error
422	<i>Content</i> application/json

GET /mne/open/eeg

This function starts or restarts part of the EEG Visualisation UI

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
	Successful Response
200	<i>Content</i> application/json
	Validation Error
422	<i>Content</i> application/json

GET /return_signal

This function returns a channel from an EEG file, to be used in various functions and visualisations

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	input_channel_name <i>required</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	run_id <i>required</i>	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id <i>required</i>	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
	Successful Response
200	<i>Content</i> application/json
	Validation Error
422	<i>Content</i> application/json

GET /mne/return_annotations

This function returns the annotations saved by the user whenever he edits or views them

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	file_name <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
200	Successful Response <i>Content</i> application/json
422	Validation Error <i>Content</i> application/json

POST /receive_notebook_and_selection_configuration

Receive notebook and selection configuration

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
body	input required	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	json { "bipolar_references": ["string"], "type_of_reference": "string", "channels_reference":

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
			<pre> ["string"], "notches_enabled": boolean, "notches_length": "string", "selection_channel": "string", "selection_start_time": "string", "selection_end_time": "string", "channel_list": ["string"], "filtering_low": "string", "filtering_high": "string" } </pre>
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
	Successful Response
200	<p><i>Content</i> application/json</p>
	Validation Error
422	<p><i>Content</i> application/json</p>

POST /montage/save

This endpoint saves a montage and its configuration.

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
body	input required	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	<pre> json { "bipolar_references": ["string"], "type_of_reference": "string", "channels_reference": ["string"], "notches_enabled": boolean, "notches_length": "string", "channel_list": ["string"] } </pre>
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
200	<p>Successful Response</p> <p><i>Content</i> application/json</p>

GET /montage/list

This endpoint retrieves a list of the saved montages

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
200	Successful Response <i>Content</i> application/json

GET /montage/load

This endpoint returns the information of a selected montage

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	montage_id required	Id of the selected montage	string
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
	Successful Response
200	<i>Content</i> application/json

GET /task/complete

This endpoint is activated when a function has been completed and communicates this to the workflow manager

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
	Successful Response
200	<i>Content</i> application/json

PUT /function/navigation

This endpoint serves as the main communication point with the workflow manager. When the users need to access any function of either the data analytics or Data and Results Visualisation modules, the request is first forwarded to this endpoint so the user is redirected to the correct page and any additional data is loaded and setup before any other action is taken.

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
body	navigation_item <i>required</i>	Json object containing all information about the run of a function	<pre> json { "run_id": "string", "step_id": "string", "metadata": ["string": "string"] } </pre>

Responses	
Code	Description
200	Successful Response <i>Content</i> application/json
422	Validation Error <i>Content</i> application/json

GET /function/existing

This endpoint returns a list of existing functions currently existing in the modules.

Responses	
Code	Description
200	Successful Response <i>Content</i> application/json

GET /freesurfer/status

This endpoint returns the logs for the recon-all and SAMSEG functions during the time they run in the backend.

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
200	Successful Response <i>Content</i> application/json

GET /free_surfer/samseg

This endpoint initiates the SAMSEG MRI function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
200	Successful Response <i>Content</i> application/json

Responses	
Code	Description
	Validation Error
422	<i>Content</i> application/json

GET /free_surfer/recon

This endpoint initiates the recon-all MRI function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
	Successful Response
200	<i>Content</i> application/json
	Validation Error
422	<i>Content</i> application/json

GET /return_columns

This endpoint returns the columns of a dataset

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
	Successful Response
200	<i>Content</i> application/json

GET /normality_tests

This endpoint executes the normality test function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	column <i>required</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	name_test <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
	Successful Response
200	<i>Content</i> application/json
	Validation Error
422	<i>Content</i> application/json

GET /transform_data

This endpoint executes the transform data function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	Imbd <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	number
query	name_tran sform <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	alpha <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	number
query	column <i>required</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	run_id <i>required</i>	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id <i>required</i>	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
	Successful Response
200	<i>Content</i> application/json
	Validation Error
422	<i>Content</i> application/json

GET /compute_pearson_correlation

Compute pearson correlation

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	column_2 <i>required</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	column_1 <i>required</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	run_id <i>required</i>	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id <i>required</i>	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
	Successful Response
200	<i>Content</i> application/json

Responses	
Code	Description
	Validation Error
422	<i>Content</i> application/json

GET /compute_spearman_correlation

Compute spearman correlation

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	column_2 <i>required</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	column_1 <i>required</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	run_id <i>required</i>	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id <i>required</i>	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
	Successful Response
200	<i>Content</i> application/json
	Validation Error
422	<i>Content</i> application/json

GET /compute_kendalltau_correlation

Compute kendall tau correlation

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	method <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	alternative <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	variant <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	nan_policy <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	column_2 <i>required</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	column_1 <i>required</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	run_id <i>required</i>	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id <i>required</i>	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
	Successful Response
200	<i>Content</i> application/json
	Validation Error
422	<i>Content</i> application/json

GET /compute_point_biserial_correlation

Compute point biserial correlation

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	column_2 <i>required</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	column_1 <i>required</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	run_id <i>required</i>	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id <i>required</i>	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
	Successful Response
200	<i>Content</i> application/json
	Validation Error
422	<i>Content</i> application/json

GET /check_homoscedasticity

Check homoscedasticity

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	name_of_test <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	center <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	column_2 <i>required</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	column_1 <i>required</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	run_id <i>required</i>	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id <i>required</i>	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
	Successful Response
200	<i>Content</i> application/json
	Validation Error
422	<i>Content</i> application/json

GET /transformed_data_for_use_in_an_ANOVA

Get transformed data to be used in ANOVA

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	column_2 <i>required</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	column_1 <i>required</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	run_id <i>required</i>	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
Successful Response	
200	<i>Content</i> application/json
Validation Error	
422	<i>Content</i> application/json

GET /statistical_tests

This endpoint handles the initialisation of many statistical functions

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	mode <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	zero_method <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	method <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	alternative <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	correction <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	boolean

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	statistical_test <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	nan_policy <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	column_2 <i>required</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	column_1 <i>required</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	run_id <i>required</i>	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id <i>required</i>	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
	Successful Response
200	<i>Content</i> application/json
	Validation Error
422	<i>Content</i> application/json

GET /multiple_comparisons

This endpoint handles the initialisation of many statistical functions

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	p_value <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	< number > array
query	method <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	alpha <i>required</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	number
query	run_id <i>required</i>	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id <i>required</i>	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
Successful Response	
200	<i>Content</i> application/json
Validation Error	
422	<i>Content</i> application/json

GET /return_reconall_stats/whole_brain_measurements

Return recon all results measurements

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	hemisphere _requested <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	fs_dir <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
	Successful Response
200	<i>Content</i> application/json
	Validation Error
422	<i>Content</i> application/json

GET /return_reconall_stats/structural_measurements

Return structural measurements

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	fs_dir <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
	Successful Response
200	<i>Content</i> application/json
	Validation Error
422	<i>Content</i> application/json

GET /return_samseg_result

Return samseg results

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	fs_dir <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
	Successful Response
200	<i>Content</i> application/json
	Validation Error
422	<i>Content</i> application/json

GET /return_actigraphy_data

Return actigraphy data

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
200	Successful Response <i>Content</i> application/json

GET /classification_for_cutoff_determination

Return classification for cutoff determination

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string
query	dependent_ variable required	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	independen t_variable required	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	algorithm required	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string

Responses	
Code	Description
	Successful Response
200	<i>Content</i> application/json

GET /principal_component_analysis

Return principal component analysis

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string
query	n_compone nts required	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	independen t_variables required	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string

Responses	
Code	Description
	Successful Response
200	<i>Content</i> application/json

GET /kmeans_clustering

The MES-CoBraD project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No 965422

Return principal component analysis

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string
query	n_clusters required	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	independent_variables required	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string

Responses	
Code	Description
200	Successful Response <i>Content</i> application/json

7.4 DATA AND RESULTS VISUALISATION

(React) Get /

Fallback page, used if there is an error in the application

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

(React) Get /auto_correlation

Page containing the form and output of the auto correlation EEG function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

(React) Get /partial_auto_correlation

Page containing the form and output of the partial auto correlation EEG function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

(React) Get /filters

Page containing the form and output of the filters EEG function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

(React) Get /welch

Page containing the form and output of the welch EEG function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

(React) Get /stft

Page containing the form and output of the stft EEG function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

(React) Get /find_peaks

Page containing the form and output of the find_peaks EEG function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

(React) Get /periodogram

Page containing the form and output of the function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

(React) Get /power_spectral_density

Page containing the form and output of the power spectral density EEG function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

(React) Get /freesurfer

Page containing the form and output of the MRI functions, recon-all and SAMSEG

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

(React) Get /eeg

Page containing the form and output of the EEG Visualisation function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

(React) Get /eeg/pre

Page containing the form and output of the EEG Visualisation and preprocessing function that precedes most eeg functions

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string
query	type required	Type of function provided by workflow manager	string

(React) Get /spindles

Page containing the form and output of the spindles EEG function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

(React) Get /slowwaves

Page containing the form and output of the slowwaves EEG function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

(React) Get /freesurfer_reconall_results

Page containing the output of the recon all MRI function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

(React) Get /freesurfer_samseg_results

Page containing the form and output of the SAMSEG MRI function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

(React) Get normality_Tests

Page containing the form and output of the normality tests function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

(React) Get /transform_data

Page containing the form and output of the transform data function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

(React) Get /pearson_correlation

Page containing the form and output of the Pearson correlation function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

(React) Get /spearman_correlation

Page containing the form and output of the Spearman correlation function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

(React) Get /point_biserial_correlation

Page containing the form and output of the Point Biserial Correlation function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

(React) Get /kendalltau_correlation

Page containing the form and output of the Kendalltau correlation function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

(React) Get /welch t test

Page containing the form and output of the Welch t test function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

(React) Get /independent_t_test

Page containing the form and output of the Independent t test function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

(React) Get /two_related_samples_t_test

Page containing the form and output of the two related samples t test function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

(React) Get /mann_whitney

Page containing the form and output of the Mann Whitney function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

(React) Get /wilcoxon_signed_rank_test

Page containing the form and output of the wilcoxon_signed_rank_test function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

(React) Get /alexander_govern_test

Page containing the form and output of the Alexander Govern test function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

(React) Get /kruskal_wallis_h_test

Page containing the form and output of the Kruskal Wallis H test function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

(React) Get /one_way_ANOVA

Page containing the form and output of the one way ANOVA function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

(React) Get /wilcoxon_rank_sum_statistic

Page containing the form and output of the Wilcoxon rank sum statistic function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

(React) Get /one_way_chi_square_test

Page containing the form and output of the One way chi square test function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

(React) Get /Homoscedasticity

Page containing the form and output of the homoscedasticity function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

(React) Get /alpha_delta_ratio

Page containing the form and output of the alpha delta ratio eeg function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

(React) Get /alpha_variability

Page containing the form and output of the alpha variability EEG function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

(React) Get /asymmetry_indices

Page containing the form and output of the asymmetry indices EEG function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

(React) Get /dashboard

Page containing the form and output of the Dashboard function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

(React) Get /level

Page containing the form and output of the level function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

(React) Get /actigraphy

Page containing the form and output of the actigraphy function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

(React) Get /actigraphy/general

Page containing the form and output of the actigraphy general data function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

GET /free_view

This endpoint initiates the backend part of the MRI Visualisaiton function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
200	Successful Response <i>Content</i> application/json
422	Validation Error <i>Content</i> application/json

(React) Get /mri

Page containing the MRI visualisation function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

7.5 ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

7.5.1 OVERVIEW PATHS

7.5.1.1 GET /run/{run_id}/predict Predict Next Task based on current status

Predict next steps given the current state of the running workflow.

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
path	run_id required		string (uuid)

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Successful Response Content application/json	No Links
404	Not Found	No Links
422	Validation Error Content application/json	No Links

7.5.1.2 GET /run/{run_id}/step/{step_id}/predict Predict next given Specific Task

Predict next steps given the current step of a running workflow.

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
------	------	-------------	--------

path	run_id required	string (uuid)
path	step_id required	string (uuid)

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Successful Response Content application/json	No Links
404	Not Found	No Links
422	Validation Error Content application/json	No Links

8 IMPLEMENTATION

8.1 OVERVIEW

The present chapter will show how Advanced Analytics functionalities are placed in specific modules integrated in the MES-CoBraD platform. We'll start by displaying the place in the overall architecture, then discuss hardware and software components. Finally, the Development of specific elements are considered.

8.1.1 PLACEMENT IN THE OVERALL ARCHITECTURE

The place in the overall architecture of the system is marked in the next figure (Figure 59). Advanced Analytics elements are the result of task T6.2 - data Analytics. They are implemented as containers (Docker containers), then they are placed under the container management system orchestrated by Kubernetes.

Data are exchanged with the Data Lake component through the sharing and reuse layer, implemented as result of task T5.3.

Data presentation is placed in the main portal of MES-CoBraD.

Figure 59 - Expert System, Data Analytics and AI in the overall architecture

8.1.2 HARDWARE INFRASTRUCTURE

Data Analytics modules are placed in Docker containers. They are deployed in several nodes orchestrated

by Kubernetes. In the development and test environment, there is one master node and three worker nodes.

The specifications for nodes are:

Master node:

- > 2 CPU
- > 16 G RAM
- > 256 G SSD
- > 1 Gb Network

Worker nodes:

- > 6 CPU
- > 16 G RAM
- > 256 G SSD
- > 1 Gb Network

8.1.3 SOFTWARE INFRASTRUCTURE

The modules are placed in a Kubernetes managed cluster. The software infrastructure used is composed of

- > Operating System: Linux UBUNTU
- > Containers: Docker
- > Container management: Kubernetes
- > Java
- > Python

The version used are:

Linux:

- > Distributor ID: Ubuntu
- > Description: Ubuntu 20.04.3 LTS
- > Release: 20.04
- > Codename: focal

Docker:

- › Docker version 20.10.11, build dea9396

Kubernetes:

- › kubeadm version: &version.Info{Major:"1", Minor:"23", GitVersion:"v1.23.3", GitCommit:"816c97ab8cff8a1c72eccca1026f7820e93e0d25", BuildDate:"2022-01-25T21:24:08Z", GoVersion:"go1.17.6", Compiler:"gc", Platform:"linux/amd64"}
- › Client Version: version.Info{Major:"1", Minor:"23", GitVersion:"v1.23.3", GitCommit:"816c97ab8cff8a1c72eccca1026f7820e93e0d25", BuildDate:"2022-01-25T21:25:17Z", GoVersion:"go1.17.6", Compiler:"gc", Platform:"linux/amd64"}

Java:

- › openjdk version "11.0.16" 2022-07-19
- › OpenJDK Runtime Environment (build 11.0.16+8-post-Ubuntu-0ubuntu120.04)
- › OpenJDK 64-Bit Server VM (build 11.0.16+8-post-Ubuntu-0ubuntu120.04, mixed mode, sharing)

Python:

- › Python versions 3.9 and 3.10

8.2 EXPERT SYSTEM - PROCESS MODELLING AND MANAGEMENT

8.2.1 OVERVIEW

The Expert System is a web application that uses multiple sources to reproduce and solve problems which are usually done by the scientists. The main purpose of the MES-CoBraD Expert System is to support diagnosis and therapeutic processes with the use of Artificial intelligence and other modules that are integrated with it.

This module consists of a back-end service developed with FastAPI, a front-end developed in ReactJS and multiple libraries used.

The back-end services application has the endpoints needed to successfully execute a given workflow and manage the connection between the various components available in the MES-CoBraD platform (data analytics, Data Lake, visualizations, etc.). The ES-1 requirement, presented in section 4.1, is addressed successfully by the described architecture since the Expert System exposes the steps needed in the most describable way to make the necessary decisions to reach the desired outcome of a given workflow.

The front-end module of the application is a single page application in which the user can create a process using the BPMN creator with diagram representation, which is called a workflow. The user fills in a form all the required data of a workflow and then creates the diagram BPMN for the process that must be followed.

- › Fill the form and create a BPMN diagram of the process
 - Create a workflow using a workflow name, a small description and diagram that describes the route that will be followed step by step to achieve an end state. Each task that will be created using the diagram that was designed, can use an external module like, the Data Lake, the Data Analytics or the Questionnaire module to analyse data or create multiple algorithm results.

Figure 60 Create a workflow

- › View the XML of the BPMN diagram and save it
 - There is an option to use the Diagram XML for other 3rd party applications to create a workflow representation or use.

Figure 63 Edit a workflow

› Delete a workflow

- There is a on option to delete a workflow that you have created.

Figure 64 Delete a workflow

› View the Tasks that should be followed

- There is an option to view Workflow's tasks with the characteristics that describe it, like the task's type, the input of the task, the output, if it's a manual task or if it uses an external module to be completed.

1.Create new Task here
[Create new Task](#)

2.Workflow "Neurological Diagnosis" Tasks

Task Name: Medical History
type: Manual task
input: Start
Clinical examination
Manual task:
Yes

Task Name: clinical examination
type: Manual task
input: medical history
output: movement disorder
Manual task:
Yes

Task Name: movement disorder
type: ExclusiveGateway
input: clinical examination
output: X_Questionnaire, MRI
Manual task:
No
Analytic module:
Yes

Figure 65 Tasks of the workflow

> Run a Workflow

- The main feature of the system is the process Run Workflow. That means that a workflow that it is based on a BPMN diagram from the creation section, can be run step by step, using the tasks that are described on the diagram. On this process there is an option to run a step manually, automatically based on Artificial Intelligence algorithms, or use another module of the Expert System to achieve a result and proceed to the next step.

Figure 66 Run a workflow

> Step of a workflow Run

- Each step is running a specific task of the workflow using the available methods.

Figure 67 Step of a workflow

> Step with redirect to external module

Figure 68 Step with redirect to external module

> Choose the next Step of the Run

- There is the option to choose between the next step, based on the diagram. If there is no condition to choose the next path, you are obliged to follow the next step accordingly.

Figure 69 Choose the next step of a workflow

> Prediction result

- The module can provide a prediction based on the data provided including the redirects and the other modules that got involved.

Figure 70 Prediction

8.3 QUERY BUILDER

8.3.1 OVERVIEW

Query Builder is a complex component that is used for building and executing SQL queries over the stored data as well as selecting objects/files from the DataLake. This component consists of a back-end service, developed in FastAPI, and a front-service, developed in ReactJS.

The back-end service provides a large variety of endpoints for building basic SQL queries (SELECT, GROUP BY, JOIN), for getting the available tables and columns names, for executing the query and saving this output. The QRB-1 requirement, which is presented in section **Error! Reference source not found.**, is addressed successfully by the described architecture, since Query Builder builds SQL queries receiving as input data in JSON format and the Query Builder is able to read tabular data as well as in csv format.

The front-end service is a single-page application in which the user selects the respective tab for building selection queries or join queries and for selecting objects from the Object Storage. The user fills in a form, which is converted in JSON format and acts as input in the back-end service. Then, the user is able to preview the data produced by the execution of the SQL query as well as to save the desired data (as a csv file in the Object Storage). When the user saves the data, Query Builder exits and Workflow Manager is informed about the completion of the step and the location of the saved data.

8.3.2 FUNCTIONALITIES

In a nutshell, the main functionalities of Query Builder are the following:

- › Build Select SQL query

Figure 71 Build Select SQL query

› Build Select SQL query with filtering

Figure 72 Build Select SQL query with filtering

› Preview the output of an executed Select SQL Query

country_id	pr_id
1	1
2	2

Figure 73 Preview the output of an executed Select SQL Query

- › Save the output in the Object Storage
- › Build Group by SQL query from one table

Figure 74 Build Group by SQL query from one table

- › Build Group by SQL query from one table with filtering

Figure 75 Build Group by SQL query from one table with filtering

› Build Join SQL query

Figure 76 Build Join SQL query

› Build Join SQL query with filtering

The screenshot shows the 'JOIN QUERIES' section of the SQL query builder. It features a 'Join Tables' dropdown with the value 'postgresql.public.ntua_tb01_test_relational, postgresql.public.ntua_tb02_test_relational'. An 'Aggregations' checkbox is present and unchecked. Below this is a 'Select Columns' section with two input fields: 'postgresql.public.ntua_tb01_test_relational' containing 'country_id_param01' and 'postgresql.public.ntua_tb02_test_relational' containing 'country_name'. The 'Joins' section has two rows: 'Table 1' (postgresql.public.ntua_tb01_test_relational) with 'Join Column 1' (pr_id), and 'Table 2' (postgresql.public.ntua_tb02_test_relational) with 'Join Column 2' (pr_id). The 'Filters' section includes a 'Table' dropdown (postgresql.public.ntua...), a 'Column' dropdown (country_name), a 'Condition' dropdown (Equal to), and a 'Value' input field (Greece). At the bottom are '+ADD FILTER', 'CLEAR FILTERS', and 'SUBMIT' buttons.

Figure 77 Build Join SQL query with filtering

› Build Group by SQL query from multiple tables

The screenshot shows the 'JOIN QUERIES' section of the SQL query builder. The 'Join Tables' dropdown is set to 'postgresql.public.ntua_tb01_test_relational, postgresql.public.ntua_tb02_test_relational'. The 'Aggregations' checkbox is checked. There are two main sections: 'Grouping Columns' and 'Aggregation Columns'. 'Grouping Columns' has two input fields: 'postgresql.public.ntua_tb01_test_relational' containing 'column1, column2' and 'postgresql.public.ntua_tb02_test_relational'. 'Aggregation Columns' has a 'Table' dropdown (postgresql.public.n...), a 'Column' dropdown (param01), and an 'Aggregation' dropdown (MAX). Below these are '+ADD AGGREGATION' and 'CLEAR AGGREGATIONS' buttons. The 'Joins' section is identical to Figure 77. The 'Filters' section has '+ADD FILTER' and 'CLEAR FILTERS' buttons.

Figure 78 Build Group by SQL query from multiple tables

› Build Group by SQL query from multiple tables with filtering

Figure 79 Build Group by SQL query from multiple tables with filtering

› Select file(s) from the Object Storage

Figure 80 Select file(s) from the Object Storage

› Query Builder completes the step, and the Workflow Manager receives a message about the completion of the task and the location of the saved data

Figure 81 Query Builder completes the step, and the Workflow Manager receives a message about the completion of the task and the location of the saved data

8.4 DATA AND RESULTS VISUALISATION

The data and results visualisation module creates different visualisations according to the data that need to be visualised in each case. During the development of the module, it became apparent that not a single library can cover all our needs for different visualisations. In this iteration of the module visualisations are handled mostly by:

› Amcharts5

- Amcharts5 is the main library that handles most our simple plots. These plots

The MES-CoBraD project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No 965422

include simple column, lollipop and line charts.

> Amcharts4

- Amcharts4 is used in several graphs, due to its ability to better handle a large quantity of data, which amcharts5 can't support currently. Specifically Amcharts4 is used to create plots of EEG signals without the use of MNE library wherever needed.

› Matplotlib

- In cases where amcharts cannot easily and effectively display the necessary plots, they are created using the matplotlib library and translated through a supporting library to html.

› Neurodesk-MNE

- Some data require specialised libraries to display them. In this specific case, to display the eeg signals, we use the MNE library to create visualisations. Because the visualisations need to be supplied to the user through a browser, and the MNE library leverages libraries that aren't present in our react front end application. In order to address this restriction, we also use the Neurodesk open-source application which creates a virtual desktop environment through LXpanel. The use of this virtual desktop environment has been mostly automated and requires minimal input from the user to operate. It is shown through iframes whenever needed.

› Neurodesk-Freeview

- Similarly, to display MRI data, we have chosen the Freeview open-source application. It has the same limitation with the MNE library, which requires the existence of a virtual desktop environment. The neurodesk application also includes by default Freeview, which we use similarly, having automated most of the basic functions while allowing the user full access of the Freeview application.

All in all, Data and Results Visualisation functionality is mainly provided by three different types of visualisation.

1. First visualisations are delivered alongside the results of other modules. For example, in the data analytics module, when a function is completed, its results are returned and accompanied by a visualisation or the application to further explore it.
2. Second, there are two specific functions whose main purpose is the visualisation of EEG signals and MRI visualisations respectively which allow the user to explore the data without having a specific purpose or output expected by the system itself.

a. EEG Visualisation

The page EEG Visualisation function allows the user to tweak parameters and change the view of the EEG signal. The EEG Visualisation is also used before every function of the Data Analytics module because EEG signals might need parameterisation themselves before the function is applied. Its various functions and capabilities are listed in the next section.

b. MRI Visualisation

The page MRI Visualisation page gives access to the user, to the freeview tool. The data is automatically loaded to the tool and the user can access it freely using its functionality

- Finally through the workflow dashboard which displays all the relevant visualisations produced in previously executed functions of a workflow. Each element of the dashboard can be moved and resized freely by the user giving him control over the display of information. The visualisation in the dashboard are the same as those presented in each different functions most of the time.

8.5 DATA ANALYTICS

8.5.1 OVERVIEW

The data analytics component provides the capability to process, analyse and transform data from different data sources. The libraries and applications used to provide the functionality are the following:

- › MNE & Neurodesk MNE
 - MNE is used in Fast API backend and provides most of the functionality relating to the handling and processing of EEG signals. The MNE library in neurodesk is mostly used for visualisation and functionality relating to it, like annotating.
- › Neurodesk Freesurfer
 - Freesurfer is used for the processing of MRI data. While a standalone implementation of it can be used, it is already included in the neurodesk application itself, so we use the implementation in it.
- › Scipy & Statsmodel & YASA
 - These libraries are used to provide various statistic related functions.
- › Freesurfer Stats
 - Used to handle output from Freesurfer functions.

It provides different functionality tailored to each different type of input data. These functions have been categorised to each different major type of input information sent by the rest of MES-CoBraD platform. Each function is accessed separately from the workflow manager which provides all the additional necessary information such as input data and location of files to the data analytics component. After the user provides any necessary parameterisation and completes any part of the functions that require manual input, each functions relevant output will be stored in the DataLake and the workflow manager.

8.5.2 EEG FUNCTIONS

EEG functions contain any functionality relevant to the results of electroencephalograms.

8.5.2.1 The EEG Signal Pre-processing and Presentation

Before proceeding with the actual functions researchers usually need to be able to view and examine the EEG signal themselves. The EEG Signal Pre-processing and Presentation function gives the option to interact and tinker with the presentation of the EEG data. The parametrisation is completed by the user through a form in the page itself whose output is saved and converted to a Jupyter notebook file which is then forwarded to the neurodesk environment automatically and opened with its MNE application. Next through an iframe which points to the neurodesk environment the user can either check the created file if he wants or immediately execute it displaying the new parametrised signals. The user is given the following functionality:

- › Notch Filter
 - The notch filter is used to filter out the noise from the power grid that can be found in

eeg signals.

Notch Filter

Enable Notches Filter

Notch Hz
50Hz

> Reference Channels

- The user can choose to not assign a reference for the EEG signal or assign either an average reference from all the channels or assign specific channels as reference.

Reference Channels

Reference Type
Channels

Select type of reference:

Channels Reference Selector

Channel
Cz-AV

Cz-AV

Select reference channel

ADD REFERENCE CHANNEL >

> Bipolar References

- The user can add new virtual channels which takes the difference between the specified anode and cathode channels.

> Filtering

- The user can apply either a highpass, a lowpass, a bandpass or a bandstop filter to the signal. To apply a bandpass filter the user needs to pass a value to both fields with the lowpass value higher than the highpass value. If the highpass value is higher than the lowpass the filter applied is instead a bandstop filter.

> Signal Cropping

- The user can crop the signal and only display a specified timeframe. To do that first, the user selects a specific channel to preview in the appearing modal and then selects the time he wants.

› Showing specific channels and ordering them

› Displaying and saving annotations

- The user can create and edit annotations through the MNE module of neurodesk. The annotations are automatically transferred and saved to the Data Analytics component where the username of the created or last editor of an annotation is appended and saved alongside the rest of the information.

Annotations in File			
Creator	Description	Onset	Duration
user	Prune	2019-02-10 16:09:52.583300	82.6111
user	Movement	2019-02-10 16:09:53.570455	2.704131311726248

› Saving/Loading Montage

- Finally the user can save all the relevant configurations we mentioned previously in a montage. The configuration is saved in a json file with the following format. The user can always load a previously saved montage if he wants.

The screenshot shows the 'Montage' configuration interface on the left and its JSON output on the right. The interface includes a 'Load Montage' dropdown menu with 'Montage - 1' selected, a 'LOAD MONTAGE' button, a 'Save New Montage' section with a 'Montage Name' input field and a 'SAVE CONFIGURATION AS NEW MONTAGE' button. The JSON output is as follows:

```

{
  "bipolar_references": [
    {
      "anode": "channel_name_string",
      "cathode": "channel_name_string"
    }
  ],
  "type_of_reference": "channels|average|none",
  "channels_reference": [
    "channel_name_string",
    "channel_name_string",
    "channel_name_string"
  ],
  "notches_enabled": true|false,
  "notches_value": float,
  "lowpass": float,
  "highpass": float,
  "montage": "montage_name_string",
  "channels_order": ["channel_name_string", "channel_name_string"]
}
    
```

After finishing the parameterisation and the application of the montage, the users can proceed with any other EEG function they select. Obviously, the users can skip any parameterisation and immediately proceed with the initially selected function especially if they have already processed a specific file.

In many cases the users might only need the functionality provided by the EEG Signal Pre-processing and Presentation function and as such it can be accessed as its own distinct function instead of being just a pre-processing step for other functions.

The screenshot displays the 'Analytics Engine' interface. On the left, the 'EEG Display Settings' panel is visible, including 'Notch Filter' (50Hz), 'Reference Channels' (Cz-AV), and 'Bipolar Reference' (T6-AV|C3-AV, C4-AV|Pz-AV). The 'Annotations in File' table shows a single entry for 'user' at '2019-02-10 16:09:52.583300'. On the right, a Jupyter Notebook is open, showing Python code for loading EEG data and applying bipolar references:

```

import mne
import time
import threading
%matplotlib qt5
data = mne.io.read_raw_edf('trial_av.edf', infer_types=True, preload = True)

def autosave_annotations():
    data.annotations.save(filename='annotation_test.csv', overwrite=True)
    threading.Timer(5.0, autosave_annotations).start()

data = mne.set_bipolar_reference(data, anode=['T6-AV'], cathode=['C3-AV'])
    
```


8.5.2.2 Methods

› Auto Correlation

- The auto-correlation function correlates the signal with a delayed copy of itself. The parameters expected from the user are the following:
 - Channel: Selected channel to use as time series data
 - Adjusted: If True, then denominators for autocovariance are $n-k$, otherwise n .
 - Qstat: If True, returns the Ljung-Box q statistic for each autocorrelation coefficient
 - FFT: If True, fast fourier transform is used to compute the autocorellation
 - Bartlet: If true, bartletts' formula is used
 - Missing: specifying how missing values are to be treated. "None": "No checks", "Raise" : "Raises error" , "Drop" : "Remove missing observations"
 - Alpha: The confidence intervals for the given level are returned
 - Nlags: Number of lags to return autocorrelation for
- The functions returns the following:
 - Visualisations
 - A plot with the calculated lags
 - (Optionally: Only if the alpha parameter has a value) A plot of the confidence interval for each
 - Raw data
 - Calculated lags
 - (Optional) confidence intervals

Partial Auto Correlation

- The partial auto-correlation function partially correlates the signal with a delayed copy of itself without taking into account. The parameters expected from the user are the following:
 - Channel: Selected channel to use as time series data
 - Methods: Specifying method to be used for the calculations. The methods are:
 - Yule-Walker with sample-size adjustment
 - Yule-Walker without adjustment
 - Regression of time series on lags of it and on constant
 - Regression of time series on lags using a single common sample to estimate all pacf coefficients
 - Regression of time series on lags with a bias adjustment.
 - Levinson-Durbin recursion with bias correction
 - Levinson-Durbin recursion without bias correction
 - Burg's partial autocorrelation estimator
 - Alpha: The confidence intervals for the given level are returned
 - Nlags: Number of lags to return autocorrelation for
- The function returns the following:
 - Visualisations:
 - A plot with the calculated lags
 - (Optional: Only if the alpha parameter has a value) A plot of the confidence interval for each
 - Raw data:
 - Calculated lags
 - (Optional) confidence intervals

> Welch

- The welch function takes as input a channel of an EEG signal and computes an estimate of the power spectral density. The parameters expected from the user are the following:
 - Channel: Selected channel to use as time series data
 - Nperseg: Length if each segment.
 - Window: Selects the window function that will taper the signal. The options are:
 - Hann
 - Boxcar
 - Triang
 - Blackman
 - Bartlett
 - Flattop
 - Parzen
 - Bohman
 - Blackmanharris
 - Nuttal
 - Barthann
 - Exponential
 - Tukey
 - Taylor
 - Fs: Sampling frequency of the signal, automatically detected if possible
 - Noverlap: Number of points to overlap between segments.
 - Nfft: Length of the fast fourier transform used if zero padded is desired, otherwise the length is the same as nperseg
 - Onesided: If enabled returns one sided spectrum of real data other returns two sided.
 - Scaling: Selects between computing the power spectral density or the power

- Visualisations:
 - A plot showing the whole channel of the signal with highlighted red dot in every detected maxima. Due to technical limitations of the plotting library the peaks aren't shown at all levels of magnification when they exceed a certain number causing low performance. The user can always magnify the view of the plot to see them all. To avoid confusion the user is notified for the total number of detected maxima.
- Raw data:
 - Calculated local peaks

> Periodogram

- The periodogram function takes as input a channel of an EEG signal and computes a periodogram of the signal. The parameters expected from the user are the following:
 - Channel: Selected channel to use as time series data
 - Window: Selects the window function that will taper the signal. The options are: the same as the Welch function refer to that function for a full list.
 - Fs: Sampling frequency of the signal, automatically detected if possible
 - Nfft: Length of the fast fourier transform used if zero padded is desired, otherwise the length is the same as nperseg
 - Scaling: Selects between computing the power spectral density or the power spectrum
 - Density
 - Spectrum
 - Axis: The axis along which the periodogram is computed
- The function returns the following:
 - Visualisations:
 - A plot of the calculated periodogram
 - Raw data:

- The periodogram

› Short time Fourier Transform

- The parameters expected from the user are the following:
 - Channel: Selected channel to use as time series data
 - Window: : Selects the window function that will taper the signal. The options are: the same as the Welch function refer to that function for a full list.
 - Nperseg: Length of each segment.
 - Noverlap: Number of points to overlap between segments.
 - Nfft: Length of the fast fourier transform used if zero padded is desired, otherwise the length is the same as nperseg
 - Onesided: If enabled returns one sided spectrum of real data other returns two sided.
 - Boundary: Specifies whether the input signal is extended at both ends
 - Padded: Specifies whether the input signal is zero-padded at the end
 - Axis: The axis along which the periodogram is computed
- The function returns the following:
 - Visualisations:

> Power Spectral Density

- The power spectral density function calculates the power spectral density of a given signal with the multi-taper methods. The parameters expected from the user are the following:
 - Channel: Selected channel to use as time series data
 - Fmin and Fmax: The lower and upper frequencies of interest. Fmax can be left empty for infinity.
 - Bandwidth: The bandwidth of the multi taper windowing function in Hz.
 - Adaptive: If true, adaptive weights are used to combine the tapered spectra
 - Low Bias: If true, only tapers with more than 90% spectral concentration within bandwidth are used.
 - Normalisation: Normalisation strategy. If “full”, the power spectral density will be normalised by the sampling rate as well as the length of the signal. Otherwise only the length of the signal is used.
 - Full
 - Length
- The function returns the following:
 - Visualisations:
 - A visualisation of the calculated power spectral density
 - Raw data:
 - A calculated power spectral density

› Alpha delta ratio

- The alpha delta ratio function estimates the power spectral density using welch'. The parameters expected from the user are the following:
 - Channel: Selected channel to use as time series data
 - Window: Selects the window function that will taper the signal. The options are: the same as the Welch function refer to that function for a full list.
 - Nperseg: Length of each segment.
 - Noverlap: Number of points to overlap between segments.
 - Nfft: Length of the fast fourier transform used if zero padded is desired, otherwise the length is the same as nperseg
 - Onesided: If enabled returns one sided spectrum of real data other returns two sided.
 - Scaling: Selects between computing the power spectral density or the power spectrum
 - Density
 - Spectrum
 - Axis: The axis along which the periodogram is computed
 - Average: The method to average periodograms
 - Mean
 - Channel:Median
- The function returns the following:
 - Raw data: The calculated alpha delta ratio

Analytics Engine		
Data Preview	Alpha Delta Ratio Parameterisation	Alpha Delta Ratio Result
Fp2-AV	Channel: Fz-AV, Window: [dropdown], Nperseg: 256	0.11247654430825567
Fp1-AV	Select Channel for Welch: [dropdown], Specify which window to use: [dropdown], Length of each segment: [input]	
F8-AV	Noverlap: [input], Nfft: 256	
F4-AV	Number of points to overlap between segments: [input], Length of the FFT used, Nfft must be equal or higher than Nperseg: [input]	
Fz-AV	Return Onesided: True, Scaling: Density	
F3-AV	If True, return a one-sided spectrum: [checkbox], Selects between computing the power spectral density or the power spectrum: [dropdown]	
F7-AV	Axis: -1, Average: Mean, SUBMIT	
A2-AV	Axis along which the periodogram is computed: [input], Method to use when averaging periodograms: [dropdown]	
T4-AV		
C4-AV		
Cz-AV		
C3-AV		
T3-AV		
A1-AV		
T6-AV		
P4-AV		
Pz-AV		

> Alpha variability

- The alpha variability function estimates the alpha variability of a channel in a specific timeframe. The parameters expected from the user are the following:
 - Channel: Selected channel to use as time series data
 - Tmin & Tmax: The time frame of the signal who alpha variability is calculated.
 - Nperseg: Length if each segment.
 - Window: : Selects the window function that will taper the signal. The options are: the same as the Welch function refer to that function for a full list.
 - Noverlap: Number of points to overlap between segments.
 - Nfft: Length of the fast fourier transform used if zero padded is desired, otherwise the length is the same as nperseg
 - Onesided: If enabled returns one sided spectrum of real data other returns two sided.
 - Scaling: Selects between computing the power spectral density or the power spectrum
 - Density
 - Spectrum
 - Axis: The axis along which the periodogram is computed
 - Average: The method to average periodograms
 - Mean
 - Median
- The function returns the following:
 - Raw data: The calculated alpha variability.

Analytics Engine		
Data Preview	Alpha Variability Parameterisation	Alpha Variability Result
Fp2-AV	Channel: F4-AV, Window: [dropdown], Nperseg: 256	0.09471106731172396
Fp1-AV	Select Channel for Welch, Specify which window to use, Length of each segment	
F8-AV	Tmin: 0, Tmax: [input]	
F4-AV	Tmin: [input], Tmax: [input]	
Fz-AV	Noverlap: [input], Nfft: 256	
F3-AV	Number of points to overlap between segments, Length of the FFT used, Nfft must be equal or higher than Nperseg	
F7-AV	Return Onesided: True, Scaling: Density	
A2-AV	If True, return a one-sided spectrum, Selects between computing the power spectral density or the power spectrum	
T4-AV	Axis: -1, Average: Mean, SUBMIT	
C4-AV	Axis along which the periodogram is computed, Method to use when averaging periodograms	
Cz-AV		
C3-AV		
T3-AV		
A1-AV		
T6-AV		
P4-AV		
Pz-AV		

> Assymetry indices

- The asymmetry indices function calculates the asymmetry indices value of a signal. The parameters expected from the user are the following:
 - Channels: Selected channels to use as time series data
 - Nperseg: Length if each segment.
 - Window: : Selects the window function that will taper the signal. The options are: the same as the Welch function refer to that function for a full list.
 - Noverlap: Number of points to overlap between segments.
 - Nfft: Length of the fast fourier transform used if zero padded is desired, otherwise the length is the same as nperseg
 - Onesided: If enabled returns one sided spectrum of real data other returns two sided.
 - Scaling: Selects between computing the power spectral density or the power spectrum
 - Density
 - Spectrum
 - Axis: The axis along which the periodogram is computed
 - Average: The method to average periodograms
 - Mean
 - Median
- The function returns the following:
 - Raw data: The calculated asymmetry indices

Analytics Engine		
Data Preview	Asymmetry Indices Parameterisation	Asymmetry Indices Result
Fp2-AV	Channel 1: F3-AV, Channel 2: T4-AV, Window: Boxcar	0.04699155251240251
Fp1-AV	Select Channel 1 for Welch: , Select Channel 2 for Welch: , Specify which window to use:	
F8-AV	Nperseg: 256, Noverlap:	
F4-AV	Length of each segment: , Number of points to overlap between segments:	
Fz-AV	Nfft: 256, Return Onesided: True	
F3-AV	Length of the FFT used, Nfft must be equal or higher than Nperseg: , If True, return a one-sided spectrum:	
F7-AV	Scaling: Density	
A2-AV	Selects between computing the power spectral density or the power spectrum:	
T4-AV	Axis: -1, Average: Mean, SUBMIT	
C4-AV	Axis along which the periodogram is computed: , Method to use when averaging periodograms:	
Cz-AV		
C3-AV		
T3-AV		
A1-AV		
T6-AV		
P4-AV		
Pz-AV		

> Spindles

- The spindle detection function takes as input a channel of an EEG signal and computes The parameters expected from the user are the following:
 - Channel: Selected channel to use as time series data
 - Freq Sp Low & High: Spindles frequency range. Default is 12 to 15 Hz
 - Freq Broad Low & High: Broad band frequency range. Default is 1 to 30 Hz.
 - Duration Low & High: The minimum and maximum duration of the spindles. Default is 0.5 to 2 seconds.
 - Min Distance: If two spindles are closer than the specified minimum distance they are merged into a single spindles. Default is 500 ms.
 - Detection thresholds:
 - Threshold Rel Pow: Relative power (= power ratio freq_sp / freq_broad). Default is: 0.2
 - Threshold Corr: Moving correlation between original signal and sigma-filtered signal.). Default is: 0.65
 - Threshold rms: Number of standard deviations above the mean of a moving root mean square of sigma-filtered signal.). Default is: 1.5
 - Multi Only: Define the behavior of the multi-channel detection. If True, only spindles that are present on at least two channels are kept.
 - Remove Outliers: If True, YASA will automatically detect and remove outliers spindles using
- The function returns the following:
 - Visualisations:
 - A Visualisation of the detected spindles in the signal
 - Raw data:
 - Detected spindles

› Slowwaves

- The slowwave detection function takes as input a channel of an EEG signal and computes The parameters expected from the user are the following:
 - Channel: Selected channel to use as time series data
 - Freq Sw Low & High: Slow wave frequency range. Default is 0.3 to 1.5 Hz
 - Duration Negative Low & High: The minimum and maximum duration of the negative deflection of the slow wave. Default is 0.3 to 1.5 second
 - Duration Positive Low & High: The minimum and maximum duration of the positive deflection of the slow wave. Default is 0.3 to 1.5 second
 - Amplitude Positive Low & High: Absolute minimum and maximum positive peak amplitude of the slow-wave. Default is 10 uV to 150 uV.
 - Amplitude Negative Low & High: Absolute minimum and maximum negative trough amplitude of the slow-wave. Default is 40 uV to 200 uV.
 - Amplitude Peak to Peak Low & High: Minimum and maximum peak-to-peak amplitude of the slow-wave. Default is 75 uV to 350 uV.
 - Coupling: If True, will also calculate the phase-amplitude coupling between the slow-waves phase and the spindles-related sigma band amplitude.
 - Remove Outliers: If True, will automatically detect and remove outliers spindles using
 -
- The function returns the following:
 - Visualisations:
 - A Visualisation of the detected Slowwaves in the signal
 - Raw data:
 - Detected Slowwaves

› Predictions

- The parameters expected from the user are the following:
 - Channel: Selected channel to use as time series data
 - Test Size: Test size to use
 - Future Seconds: Number of future seconds to calculate. Positive integer.
 - Start P: The starting value of p , the order (or number of time lags) of the autoregressive (“AR”) model. Must be a positive integer. (default = 1)
 - Start Q: The starting value of q , the order of the moving-average (“MA”) model. Must be a positive integer. (default = 1)
 - Max P: The maximum value of p , inclusive. Must be a positive integer greater than or equal to $start_p$ (default = 5)
 - Max Q: The maximum value of q , inclusive. Must be a positive integer greater than $start_q$ (default = 5)
 - Method: The method determines which solver to be used, and it can be chosen from among the following strings:
 - ‘newton’ for Newton-Raphson
 - ‘nm’ for Nelder-Mead
 - ‘bfgs’ for Broyden-Fletcher-Goldfarb-Shanno (BFGS)
 - ‘lbfgs’ for limited-memory BFGS with optional box constraints (default)
 - ‘powell’ for modified Powell’s method
 - ‘cg’ for conjugate gradient
 - ‘nCG’ for Newton-conjugate gradient
 - ‘basinhopping’ for global basin-hopping solver
 - Information Criterion: Selects which information criterion to use for the best ARIMA model. Available choices:
 - AIC (Akaike Information Criterion, default)
 - BIC (Bayesian Information Criterion)

- HQIC (Hannan-Quinn Information Criterion)
- OOB (Out Of Bag)
- The function returns the following:

› Artifacts using the Independent Component Analysis (ICA) method

- The parameters expected from the user are the following:
 - n_components: Number of principal components (from the pre-whitening PCA step) that are passed to the ICA algorithm during fitting: Number of principal components (from the pre-whitening PCA step) that are passed to the ICA algorithm during fitting
 - method: The ICA method to use in the fit method, namely *fastica*, *infomax*, and *picard*.
 - indices to exclude: which components to exclude
- The function returns the following:
 - Visualisations
 - Plot estimated latent sources given the unmixing matrix.
 - Plot the reconstructed data
 - Raw data
 - Reconstructed data

8.5.3 MRI FUNCTIONS

The MRI functions contain any functionality relevant to the analysis and results of Magnetic resonance imaging data. As already mentioned, we utilise the Freesurfer library in the neurodesk application. The user and system input is being sent as a series of commands via ssh to Neurodesk application. The following MRI functions were created:

Recon-all

The recon-all function of the Freesurfer library, implements a cortical reconstruction process. In our implementation we automatically run the full reconstruction process which follows these steps.

- > Motion Correction
- > Nu intensity correction
- > Talairach
- > Normalisation
- > Skul Strio
- > Automatic Subcortical Segmentation
- > EM Registration
- > CA Normalise
- > CA Register
- > Remove neck

- > EM Registration, with Skull
- > CA Label
- > Aseg Stats
- > Normalization2
- > WM Segmentation
- > Cut/Fill
- > Tesselation
- > Orgin Surface Smoothing
- > Inflation
- > QSphere
- > Automatic Topology Fixer
- > Final Surfaces
- > Cortical Ribbon Mask
- > Spherical Inflation
- > Ipsilateral Surface Registation
- > Contralateral Surface Registation
- > Average Curvature
- > Cortical Parcellation
- > Parcellation Statistics

This process can take a lot of time (more than 6 hours) so the user needs to provide some manual input. In the user interface, he/she can look at the current output of the process and check whether its finalised.

Upon the user confirmation that the process is finished, the output is automatically saved and loaded to the freeview application where the verification process starts. This process aims to ensure that the results

of recon-all are valid. Several screenshots of slices are taken at different coordinates so as to be presented in the user interface, so the trained user can verify the accuracy of the output. In addition the output files are also opened in the MRI visualisation function.

The recon-all results page is shown below. In this page we can see the various metrics of the files produced by the recon-all process and the verification screenshots taken as we specified previously.

- > The function requires no manual parametrisation:

- › The function returns the following:
 - Visualisations
 - MRI visualisation.
 - Verification screenshots
 - Recon-all output table presentation
 - Raw data
 - recon-all output

Analytics Engine

Cortical Parcellation Stats

Whole Brain Measurements - left hemisphere

hemisphere : left

subject : Subj001

source_basename : lh.aparc.a2009s.stats

white_surface_total_area_mm² : 92.5422

brain_segmentation_volume_mm³ : 1251217

brain_segmentation_volume_without_ventricles_mm³ : 1232248

brain_segmentation_volume_without_ventricles_from_surf_mm³ : 1232248

total_cortical_gray_matter_volume_mm³ : 519200.792155

supratentorial_volume_mm³ : 1114299

supratentorial_volume_without_ventricles_mm³ : 1095330

estimated_total_intracranial_volume_mm³ : 1684712.951283

Whole Brain Measurements - right hemisphere

hemisphere : right

subject : Subj001

source_basename : rh.aparc.a2009s.stats

white_surface_total_area_mm² : 94.9559

brain_segmentation_volume_mm³ : 1251217

brain_segmentation_volume_without_ventricles_mm³ : 1232248

brain_segmentation_volume_without_ventricles_from_surf_mm³ : 1232248

total_cortical_gray_matter_volume_mm³ : 519200.792155

supratentorial_volume_mm³ : 1114299

supratentorial_volume_without_ventricles_mm³ : 1095330

estimated_total_intracranial_volume_mm³ : 1684712.951283

Structural Measurements

Recon-All Results

Source file	Structure name	Gray matter volume (mm ³)
lh.aparc.a2009s.stats	G_and_S_frontomargin	2629
lh.aparc.a2009s.stats	G_and_S_occipital_inf	3645
lh.aparc.a2009s.stats	G_and_S_paracentral	2582
lh.aparc.a2009s.stats	G_and_S_subcentral	3546
lh.aparc.a2009s.stats	G_and_S_transv_frontopol	1962

lh.aparc.a2009s.stats	G_and_S_cingul-Mid-Post	2790
lh.aparc.a2009s.stats	G_cingul-Post-dorsal	1646
lh.aparc.a2009s.stats	G_cingul-Post-ventral	579
lh.aparc.a2009s.stats	G_cuneus	2578

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Images - Cortical Measurements

SAMSEG

The samseg function or Sequence Adaptive Multimodal SEGmentation (SAMSEG), is a function that segments brain structures from haid MRI scans without pre-processing. Its main advantage is that it accepts multi-contrast MRI data without prior assumptions on the specific type of scanner or pulse sequences used. In addition, it requires no kind of preprocessing. Finally, it can be run in significantly less time than the recon-all function, although it can still take a while.

Based on all these and the fact that often a combination of those functions is being used, SAMSEG is presented in the same page and run in a similar manner we described above. There is no specific verification method in this function, instead the user can browse the results immediately.

- › The function requires no manual parametrisation:
- › The function returns the following:
 - Visualisations
 - SAMSEG output table presentation
 - Raw data
 - SAMSEG output

The screenshot displays the 'Analytics Engine' interface with a blue header. It features a central table with three columns: 'Data Preview', 'Freesurfer Recon-All', and 'Freesurfer Samseg'. The 'Data Preview' column shows 'File Name: mri_example' and 'File Type: DICOM'. The 'Freesurfer Recon-All' and 'Freesurfer Samseg' columns each have a 'START PROCESS' button, with the latter highlighted by a red box. Below the table, there are two status panels: 'Recon-All Output Status' and 'Samseg Output Status'. Each panel includes a 'CHECK PROGRESS' button, a 'SCROLL DOWN TO LATEST LOG >' button, a 'PROCESS FINISHED' button, and a 'BACK TO TOP >' button. At the bottom of the interface, there are two brain MRI scan images and a 'NeuroDesk' logo on a wooden background.

Analytics Engine

Samseg Results

Measure	Value	Unit
Unknown	670152.082035	mm ³
Skull	233553.136398	mm ³
Soft_Nonbrain_T1	520831.573603	mm ³
Brain-Stem	11512.130308	mm ³
CSF	215683.673334	mm ³
Left-Cerebellum-Cortex	27361.713278	mm ³
Right-Cerebellum-Cortex	33055.102753	mm ³
4th-Ventricle	822.520029	mm ³
Fluid_Inside_Ey	5261.768411	mm ³

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8.5.4 ACTIGRAPHY FUNCTIONS

8.5.4.1 Process Actigraphy data

The data analytics module is able to view and process actigraphy data exported from the capturing device (sample was acquired from a Philips Respironics | Actigraphy monitoring devices), in a dedicated function, before using them in other data analytics functions or as part of hypothesis testing.

First epoch by epoch data. This data is continuous and captured usually a few times every hour, measuring the state of the monitored person. The data includes values for the time it was captured, their activity, whitelight, sleep/wake, interval status and marker. This function allows the user through the plot to select a specific timeframe he wants to use in other data analytics functions and save it as a new file.

› Output:

- Visualisations:

The MES-CoBraD project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No 965422

- Activity, Whitelight, Sleep/wake plot
 - Actigraphy Datatable
 - Raw data:
 - Specified timeframe of actigraphy data

The general actigraphy data functions, on the other hand, presents an overview of statistics of the data gathered by the devices. There is no option given to select a timeframe, because there was no need due to the type of the data.

› Output:

The MES-CoBraD project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No 965422

- Visualisations:
 - Activity, Whitelight, Sleep/wake plot

Data Preview		Actigraphy General Viewer															
File Name: actigraphy_test_data.csv		Actigraphy General Data															
Line	Interval Type	Interval	Date Start	Time Start	Date Stop	Time Stop	Duration Sta...	Invalid sw	Efficiency	Wake time	Sleep time	Sleep	Exposure W...	Average white	Max White	Tall White	Invalid White
Interval Ty...	Interval#	Start Date	Start Time	End Date	End Time	Duration	%Invalid SW	Efficiency	Wake Time	%Wake	Sleep Time	%Sleep	Exposure...	Avg White	Max White	TALL White	Invalid White
REST	1	9 04 2021	10:52:30 pm	10 04 2021	6:38:00 am	465.5	0	NaN	50.5	10.85	415	89.15	12.7	0.03	10.6	0	
REST	2	10 04 2021	11:30:30 pm	11 04 2021	6:21:30 am	411	0	NaN	43	10.46	368	89.54	13.04	0.03	8.35	0	
REST	3	11 04 2021	11:36:00 pm	12 04 2021	7:24:30 am	468.5	0	NaN	58	12.38	410.5	87.62	151.82	0.32	6.17	0	
REST	4	12 04 2021	9:48:30 pm	13 04 2021	6:39:00 am	530.5	0	NaN	71	13.38	459.5	86.62	6.57	0.01	0.48	0	
REST	5	13 04 2021	10:12:30 pm	14 04 2021	6:56:30 am	524	0	NaN	83	15.84	441	84.16	395.54	0.75	32.7	0	
REST	6	14 04 2021	8:52:00 pm	15 04 2021	6:52:30 am	600.5	0	NaN	62.5	10.41	538	89.59	6.57	0.01	0.96	0	
REST	7	15 04 2021	10:31:30 pm	16 04 2021	7:08:30 am	517	0	NaN	65.5	12.67	451.5	87.33	56.2	0.11	11.07	0	
Rest Sum...	n	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	7	7	NaN	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7

8.6 HYPOTHESIS TESTING INTERFACE

8.6.1 OVERVIEW

In this section, an overview of the proposed methods used for testing the hypotheses developed in the deliverable D4.2 is provided.

Specifically, there are some requirements for performing a statistical test or a correlation analysis, which need to be fulfilled. These are the following:

- › The distribution of the data must follow a normal distribution for performing some statistical tests, including ANOVA, etc. For testing the null hypothesis that the data was drawn from a normal distribution, we apply some statistical tests, namely Shapiro-Wilk, Kolmogorov-Smirnov, Anderson-Darling, and D'Agostino's K^2 , which are described in detail in Section 0. Also, methods for observing visually the distribution of the data are supported, i.e., histogram.
 - If the data does not follow a gaussian/normal distribution, then we apply some transformations, including the Box-Cox and Yeo-Johnson, which are described in Section 8.6.2.2.
- › Another assumption needed to be satisfied is the property of homoscedasticity, i.e., the population standard deviations of the groups are all equal. Methods for testing the property of the homoscedasticity are described in Section 8.6.2.4.
 - If the property of homoscedasticity is not satisfied, we use the O'Brien Transform, which is described in Section 8.6.2.5.
- › After having satisfied the abovementioned requirements, we are able to choose one of the correlation functions or statistical tests described in Sections 8.6.2.3 and 8.6.2.6 respectively.

- › The user will be able to run many statistical tests and correlations. The systems shall be able to save these p-values. After performing the statistical tests, the user will be able to choose one of the methods described in Section 8.6.2.7 for adjusting/correcting the p-values.

In addition, some additional methods are going to be discussed:

- › Classification analysis (LDA/SVM), Classification for cut-off determination
- › Principal Component Analysis
- › K-means clustering

8.6.2 METHODS

For each of the following test and method, a sample dataset is utilised.

8.6.2.1 Normality Tests

- › Shapiro-Wilk

The Shapiro-Wilk test is used to calculate whether a random sample of data comes from a normal distribution which is a common assumption used in many statistical tests including regression, ANOVA, t-test, etc. The Shapiro-Wilk test is an appropriate method for small sample sizes (<50 samples).

Decision Rule:

- If the p-value $\leq \alpha$, then we reject the null hypothesis i.e., we assume the distribution of our variable is not normal/gaussian.
- If the p-value $> \alpha$, then we fail to reject the null hypothesis i.e., we assume the distribution of our variable is normal/gaussian.

where α is a significance level.

Input:

1. Array of sample data.

Returns:

1. The test statistic.
2. The p-value for the hypothesis test.

Figure 82 Shapiro-Wilk test

> Kolmogorov-Smirnov

Performs the one-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov test for goodness of fit. The one-sample test compares the underlying distribution $F(x)$ of a sample against a given normal distribution. The test is valid only for continuous distributions. Compared to the Shapiro-Wilk test, the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test is used for $n \geq 50$.

Input:

1. Array of sample data.
2. The “alternative” parameter, which defines the null and alternative hypotheses, with the following three options: ‘two-sided’, ‘less’, ‘greater’

Returns:

1. The test statistic.
2. The critical values for this distribution.

Figure 83 - Kolmogorov-Smirnov test

> Anderson-Darling

Performs the Anderson-Darling test which tests the null hypothesis that a sample is drawn from a population that follows a particular distribution. In general, the hypothesis can be tested with normal, exponential, logistic, or Gumbel (Extreme Value Type I) distributions, however, in the context of normality test only the normal distribution is selected.

Input:

1. Array of sample data.

Returns:

1. The test statistic.
2. The critical values for this distribution.
3. The significance levels for the corresponding critical values in percentage.

Figure 84 - Anderson-Darling test

> D’Agostino’s K^2

Performs the D’Agostino test, which tests whether a sample differs from a normal distribution.

Input:

1. The array containing the sample to be tested.
2. The “axis” parameter with which to compute test. Default is 0. If None, compute over the whole array a.
3. The “nan_policy” parameter, which defines how to handle when input contains nan, with the following three options: ‘propagate’, ‘raise’, ‘omit’

Returns:

1. The test statistic.
2. The p-value for the hypothesis test.

Figure 85 - D'Agostino's K² test

8.6.2.2 Data Transformation

› Box-Cox

Returns a dataset transformed by a Box-Cox power transformation. The Box-Cox requires the input data to be positive.

Input:

1. The array to be transformed.
2. The “lmbda” parameter.
3. The “alpha” parameter which returns the confidence interval for lmbda parameter

Returns:

1. The Box-Cox power transformed array.
2. If the lmbda parameter is None, the lmbda that maximises the log-likelihood function.
3. A tuple of floats which represents the minimum and maximum confidence limits given alpha, in case of lmbda parameter is None and alpha is not None

Figure 86 - Box-Cox test

> Yeo-Johnson

Returns the requested dataset transformed by a Yeo-Johnson power transformation. Unlike Box-Cox, Yeo-Johnson does not require the input data to be positive.

Input:

1. The 1-dimensional array to be transformed.
2. The “lmbda” parameter.

Returns:

1. The Yeo-Johnson power transformed array.
2. If the lmbda parameter is None, the lambda that maximises the log-likelihood function.

Figure 87 - Yeo-Johnson test

8.6.2.3 Correlation

> Pearson Correlation

Computes the Pearson correlation coefficient and p-value for testing non-correlation.

The Pearson correlation coefficient measures the linear relationship between the two provided datasets.

This function also performs a test of the null hypothesis that the distributions underlying the samples are uncorrelated and normally distributed.

The p-value roughly indicates the probability of an uncorrelated system producing datasets that have a Pearson correlation at least as extreme as the one computed from the provided datasets.

Input:

1. Two arrays.
2. The “alternative” parameter, which defines the null and alternative hypotheses, with the following three options: ‘two-sided’, ‘less’, ‘greater’

Returns:

1. The Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient
2. The p-value associated with the chosen alternative.

Figure 88 - Pearson Correlation test

> Spearman Correlation

Computes the Spearman correlation coefficient with associated p-value.

The Spearman rank-order correlation coefficient is a nonparametric measure of the monotonicity of the relationship between two datasets. Unlike the Pearson correlation, the Spearman correlation does not assume that both datasets are normally distributed.

The p-value roughly indicates the probability of an uncorrelated system producing datasets that have a Spearman correlation at least as extreme as the one computed from these datasets.

Input:

1. Two arrays. One or two 1-D or 2-D arrays containing multiple variables and observations.
2. The “axis” parameter, providing an interpret of how the variables and observations are recorded in the provided arrays.
3. The “nan_policy” parameter, which defines how to handle when input contains nan, with the following three options: ‘propagate’, ‘raise’, ‘omit’
4. The “alternative” parameter, which defines the null and alternative hypotheses, with the following three options: ‘two-sided’, ‘less’, ‘greater’

Returns:

1. The Spearman correlation matrix or correlation coefficient.
2. The p-value for a hypothesis test who’s null hypothesis is that two sets of data are uncorrelated.

Figure 89 - Spearman Correlation test

> Kendalltau Correlation

Computes the Kendall's tau correlation measure for ordinal data. Kendall's tau is a measure of the correspondence between two rankings.

Input:

1. Arrays of rankings, of the same shape.
2. The "nan_policy" parameter, which defines how to handle when input contains nan, with the following three options: 'propagate', 'raise', 'omit'
3. The "method" parameter, which defines the method to be used to calculate the p-value, with the following three options: 'auto', 'asymptotic', 'exact'
4. The "alternative" parameter, which defines the null and alternative hypotheses, with the following three options: 'two-sided', 'less', 'greater'
5. The "variant" parameter, which defines which variant of Kendall's tau is returned.

Returns:

1. The Kendalltau statistic.
2. The p-value for a hypothesis test whose null hypothesis is an absence of association.

Analytics Engine		
Data Preview	Select method for Kendall's tau correlation measure	Result Visualisation
Unnamed: 0 Age ALB ALP ALT AST BIL CHE CHOL CREA GGT PROT label Sex	Column: Age Column: ALB Select Column 01 for correlation check Select Column 02 for correlation check Nan policy: propagate Defines how to handle when input contains nan. Method: auto Defines which method is used to calculate the p-value. Variant: b Alternative: two-sided Defines which variant of Kendall's tau is returned. Defines the alternative hypothesis. SUBMIT	Kendall's tau correlation coefficient : -0.0998961485886489 p value : 0.000364843755035738

Figure 90 - Kendall's tau Correlation test

> Point Biserial Correlation

Computes the point biserial correlation coefficient and its p-value.

The point biserial correlation is used to measure the relationship between a binary variable, x, and a continuous variable, y.

Input:

1. Two arrays.

Returns:

1. The correlation value.
2. Two-sided p-value.

Analytics Engine		
Data Preview	Select columns	Result Visualisation
Unnamed: 0 Age ALB ALP ALT AST BIL CHE CHOL CREA GGT PROT label Sex	Column 1: Age Column 2: ALB SUBMIT Select First column for correlation Select Second column for correlation	Point biserial correlation : -0.19109363679578337 p_value : 0.0000029977681450316387

Figure 91 - Point Biserial Correlation test

8.6.2.4 Homoscedasticity

> Levene

Computes the Levene test statistic for equal variances. The Levene test tests the null hypothesis that all input samples are from populations with equal variances.

Input:

- 1-D Arrays of sample data.
- The “center” parameter, which determines the function of the data to be used in the test, with the following three options: ‘mean’, ‘median’, ‘trimmed’

Returns:

- The test statistic.
- The p-value of the test.

Analytics Engine		
Data Preview	Select method for Homoscedasticity check	Result Visualisation
Unnamed: 0 Age ALB ALP ALT AST BIL CHE CHOL CREA GGT PROT label Sex	Column <input type="text" value="Age"/> Select Column 01 for Homoscedasticity check Method <input type="text" value="Levene"/> Specify which method to use. <input type="text" value="trimmed"/> Keyword argument controlling which function of the data is used in computing the test statistic. The default is 'median'. <input type="button" value="SUBMIT"/>	Column <input type="text" value="ALB"/> Select Column 02 for Homoscedasticity check Statistic : 325.52056526074 p value : 1.1471269138159562e-63

Figure 92 - Levene test

> Bartlett

Computes the Bartlett's test statistic for equal variances. The Bartlett's test tests the null hypothesis that all input samples are from populations with equal variances. For samples from significantly non-normal populations, Levene's test is more robust.

Input:

- 1-D Arrays of sample data.

Returns:

- The test statistic.
- The p-value of the test.

Analytics Engine		
Data Preview	Select method for Homoscedasticity check	Result Visualisation
Unnamed: 0 Age ALB ALP ALT AST BIL CHE CHOL CREA GGT PROT label Sex	Column <input type="text" value="Age"/> Select Column 01 for Homoscedasticity check Method <input type="text" value="Bartlett"/> Specify which method to use. <input type="text" value="median"/> Keyword argument controlling which function of the data is used in computing the test statistic. The default is 'median'. <input type="button" value="SUBMIT"/>	Column <input type="text" value="ALB"/> Select Column 02 for Homoscedasticity check Statistic : 198.24638218920398 p value : 1.0056170221811226e-41

Figure 93 - Bartlett test

> Fligner-Killeen

Computes the Fligner-Killeen test statistic for equality of variance. The Fligner’s test tests the null hypothesis that all input samples are from populations with equal variances.

Input:

- 1-D Arrays of sample data.

Returns:

- The test statistic.
- The p-value of the test.

Analytics Engine		
Data Preview	Select method for Homoscedasticity check	Result Visualisation
Unnamed: 0 Age ALB ALP ALT AST BIL CHE CHOL CREA GGT PROT label Sex	Column Age Select Column 01 for Homoscedasticity check Method Fligner-Killeen Specify which method to use. mean Keyword argument controlling which function of the data is used in computing the test statistic. The default is 'median'. SUBMIT	Statistic : 200.70900848345963 p value : 3.491131951034585e-42

Figure 94 - Fligner-Killeen test

8.6.2.5 Data Transformation for use in an ANOVA

> O'Brien Transform

Returns the O'Brien transform on input data. Used to test for homogeneity of variance prior to running one-way stats.

Input:

1. Any number of arrays.

Returns:

1. Transformed data for use in an ANOVA. The first dimension of the result corresponds to the sequence of transformed arrays.

Analytics Engine																														
Data Preview	Select columns	Result Visualisation																												
Unnamed: 0 Age ALB ALP ALT AST BIL CHE CHOL CREA GGT PROT label Sex	Column 1: Age <small>Select First column for correlation</small> Column 2: BIL <small>Select Second column for correlation</small> <input type="button" value="SUBMIT"/>	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Transformed column 1 data:</th> <th>Transformed column 2 data:</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr><td>238.22721249628202</td><td>12.151023408602763</td></tr> <tr><td>238.22721249628202</td><td>50.53961291595596</td></tr> <tr><td>238.22721249628202</td><td>23.99205326177061</td></tr> <tr><td>238.22721249628202</td><td>62.023876553267755</td></tr> <tr><td>238.22721249628202</td><td>1.758249923569908</td></tr> <tr><td>238.22721249628202</td><td>1.3892113583993748</td></tr> <tr><td>238.22721249628202</td><td>6.099274344411499</td></tr> <tr><td>238.22721249628202</td><td>25.63290551408551</td></tr> <tr><td>238.22721249628202</td><td>16.7445246080604</td></tr> <tr><td>238.22721249628202</td><td>585.9964262844038</td></tr> <tr><td>238.22721249628202</td><td>38.05458259633235</td></tr> <tr><td>208.31570146938404</td><td>28.09704346909715</td></tr> <tr><td>208.31570146938404</td><td>15.928813378935018</td></tr> </tbody> </table>	Transformed column 1 data:	Transformed column 2 data:	238.22721249628202	12.151023408602763	238.22721249628202	50.53961291595596	238.22721249628202	23.99205326177061	238.22721249628202	62.023876553267755	238.22721249628202	1.758249923569908	238.22721249628202	1.3892113583993748	238.22721249628202	6.099274344411499	238.22721249628202	25.63290551408551	238.22721249628202	16.7445246080604	238.22721249628202	585.9964262844038	238.22721249628202	38.05458259633235	208.31570146938404	28.09704346909715	208.31570146938404	15.928813378935018
Transformed column 1 data:	Transformed column 2 data:																													
238.22721249628202	12.151023408602763																													
238.22721249628202	50.53961291595596																													
238.22721249628202	23.99205326177061																													
238.22721249628202	62.023876553267755																													
238.22721249628202	1.758249923569908																													
238.22721249628202	1.3892113583993748																													
238.22721249628202	6.099274344411499																													
238.22721249628202	25.63290551408551																													
238.22721249628202	16.7445246080604																													
238.22721249628202	585.9964262844038																													
238.22721249628202	38.05458259633235																													
208.31570146938404	28.09704346909715																													
208.31570146938404	15.928813378935018																													

Figure 95 - O'Brien Transform

8.6.2.6 Statistical Tests

Independent t-test

Computes the T-test for the means of two independent samples of scores. This is a test for the null hypothesis that 2 independent samples have identical average (expected) values. This test assumes that the populations have identical variances by default.

Input:

1. Arrays of sample data. The arrays must have the same shape, except in the dimension corresponding to axis.
2. The “axis” parameter, which is used to compute test.
3. equal_var: True (default). Assumes equal population variances.
4. The “alternative” parameter, which defines the null and alternative hypotheses, with the following three options: ‘two-sided’, ‘less’, ‘greater’
5. The “nan_policy” parameter, which defines how to handle when input contains nan, with the following three options: ‘propagate’, ‘raise’, ‘omit’

Returns:

1. The test statistic.
2. The p-value of the test.

Analytics Engine		
Data Preview	Select data for Independent t-test	Result Visualisation
Unnamed: 0 Age ALB ALP ALT AST BIL CHE CHOL CREA GGT PROT label Sex	Column: ALP Column: ALT Select Column 01 for correlation check Select Column 02 for correlation check Nan policy: propagate Alternative: two-sided <small>Defines how to handle when input contains NaNs. Defines the alternative hypothesis.</small> <input type="button" value="SUBMIT"/>	Statistic : 30.303809220632647 p value : 1.4835123867575177e-149 mean_positive : 68.12308998302207 mean_negative : 26.575382003395585 standard_deviation_positive : 25.899057870922846 standard_deviation_negative : 20.845402038444735

Figure 96 - Independent t-test

> Welch t-test

Computes the T-test for the means of two independent samples of scores. This is a test for the null hypothesis that 2 independent samples have identical average (expected) values. This test does not assume equal population variance.

Input:

1. Arrays of sample data. The arrays must have the same shape, except in the dimension corresponding to axis.
2. The “axis” parameter, which is used to compute test.
3. equal_var: False (Default). Does not assume equal population variance.
4. The “alternative” parameter, which defines the null and alternative hypotheses, with the following three options: ‘two-sided’, ‘less’, ‘greater’
5. The “nan_policy” parameter, which defines how to handle when input contains nan, with the following three options: ‘propagate’, ‘raise’, ‘omit’

Returns:

1. The test statistic.
2. The p-value of the test.

Figure 97 - Welch t-test

> t-test on TWO RELATED samples of scores

Computes the t-test on TWO RELATED samples of scores. This is a test for the null hypothesis that two related or repeated samples have identical average (expected) values.

Input:

1. Arrays of sample data. The arrays must have the same shape.
2. The “axis” parameter, which is used to compute test.
3. The “alternative” parameter, which defines the null and alternative hypotheses, with the following three options: ‘two-sided’, ‘less’, ‘greater’
4. The “nan_policy” parameter, which defines how to handle when input contains nan, with the following three options: ‘propagate’, ‘raise’, ‘omit’

Returns:

1. The test statistic.
2. The p-value of the test.

Analytics Engine		
Data Preview	Select TWO RELATED samples of scores for t-test	Result Visualisation
Unnamed: 0 Age ALB ALP ALT AST BIL CHE CHOL CREA GGT PROT label Sex	Column: ALP Column: ALT Select Column 01 for correlation check Select Column 02 for correlation check Nan policy: <i>omit</i> Alternative: <i>two-sided</i> <small>Defines how to handle when input contains NaNs. Defines the alternative hypothesis.</small> <input type="button" value="SUBMIT"/>	Statistic : 34.23520115522349 p value : 4.146127478462094e-142 mean_positive : 68.12308998302207 mean_negative : 26.575382003395585 standard_deviation_positive : 25.899057870922846 standard_deviation_negative : 20.845402038444735

Figure 98 - RELATED samples t-test

› Mann-Whitney U rank test

Perform the Mann-Whitney U rank test on two independent samples. The Mann-Whitney U test is a nonparametric test of the null hypothesis that the distribution underlying sample x is the same as the distribution underlying sample y. It is often used as a test of difference in location between distributions. The Mann-Whitney U test is a non-parametric version of the t-test for independent samples. When the means of samples from the populations are normally distributed, then the independent t-test can be used.

Input:

1. N-d Arrays of sample data.
2. The “axis” parameter, which is used to compute test.
3. The “alternative” parameter, which defines the null and alternative hypotheses, with the following three options: ‘two-sided’, ‘less’, ‘greater’
4. The “nan_policy” parameter, which defines how to handle when input contains nan, with the following three options: ‘propagate’, ‘raise’, ‘omit’
5. The “method” parameter, which defines the method to be used to calculate the p-value, with the following three options: ‘auto’, ‘asymptotic’, ‘exact’

Returns:

1. The Mann-Whitney U statistic corresponding with sample x.
2. The associated p-value for the chosen alternative.

Analytics Engine		
Data Preview	Select samples of scores for Mann-Whitney U rank test	Result Visualisation
Unnamed: 0 Age ALB ALP ALT AST BIL CHE CHOL CREA GGT PROT label Sex	Column: Age Column: ALP Select Column 01 for correlation check Select Column 02 for correlation check Method: asymptotic Nan policy: propagate Specify which method to use. Defines how to handle when input contains nan. Variant: two-sided Defines the alternative hypothesis. <input type="button" value="SUBMIT"/>	Statistic : 65542.5 p value : 2.6817159230183548e-76 mean_positive : 47.41765704584041 mean_negative : 68.12308998302207 standard_deviation_positive : 9.922899410500207 standard_deviation_negative : 25.899057870922846

Figure 99 - Mann-Whitney U rank test

› Wilcoxon signed-rank test

Computes the Wilcoxon signed-rank test. The Wilcoxon signed-rank test tests the null hypothesis that two related paired samples come from the same distribution. It tests whether the distribution of the differences $x - y$ is symmetric about zero. It is a non-parametric version of the paired T-test.

Input:

1. Two 1-D Arrays of sample measurements.
2. The “zero_method” parameter, which is used for handling pairs of observations with equal values (“zero-differences”, or “zeros”), with the following three options: “wilcox”, “pratt”, “zsplitt”
3. The “alternative” parameter, which defines the null and alternative hypotheses, with the following three options: ‘two-sided’, ‘less’, ‘greater’
4. The “nan_policy” parameter, which defines how to handle when input contains nan, with the following three options: ‘propagate’, ‘raise’, ‘omit’
5. The “method” parameter, which defines the method to be used to calculate the p-value, with the following three options: ‘auto’, ‘asymptotic’, ‘exact’
6. The “correction” parameter, for applying continuity correction. If set to True, the Wilcoxon rank statistic shall be adjusted by 0.5 towards the mean value when computing the z-statistic if a normal approximation is used.

Returns:

1. The test statistic. If alternative is “two-sided”, the sum of the ranks of the differences above or below zero, whichever is smaller. Otherwise, the sum of the ranks of the differences above zero.

2. The associated p-value for the chosen alternative.

Analytics Engine		
Data Preview	Wilcoxon rank-sum statistic	Result Visualisation
Unnamed: 0 Age ALB ALP ALT AST BIL CHE CHOL CREA GGT PROT label Sex	Column: ALP Column: ALT Nan policy: omit Select sample 01: Select sample 02: Defines how to handle when input contains NaNs. Alternative: greater Defines the alternative hypothesis. SUBMIT	Statistic : 26.70387526955932 p value : 2.121742560452084e-157 mean_positive : 68.12308998302207 mean_negative : 26.575382003395585 standard_deviation_positive : 25.899057870922846 standard_deviation_negative : 20.845402038444735

Figure 100 - Wilcoxon signed-rank test

> one-way ANOVA

Computes the one-way ANOVA. The one-way ANOVA tests the null hypothesis that two or more groups have the same population mean. The test is applied to samples from two or more groups, possibly with differing sizes.

The ANOVA test has some important assumptions, which need to be satisfied including: (i) The samples are independent, (ii) Each sample is from a normally distributed population, and (iii) the property of homoscedasticity. If these assumptions are not satisfied, then the Kruskal-Wallis H-test or the Alexander-Govern test can be used (with some loss of power).

Input:

Arrays of sample measurements for each group.

Returns:

1. The computed F statistic of the test.
2. The associated p-value from the F distribution.

Figure 101 - one-way ANOVA test

› Kruskal-Wallis H-test

Computes the Kruskal-Wallis H-test for independent samples. The Kruskal-Wallis H-test tests the null hypothesis that the population median of all of the groups is equal. It is a non-parametric version of ANOVA.

Input:

- 1-D Arrays of sample measurements.
- The “nan_policy” parameter, which defines how to handle when input contains nan, with the following three options: ‘propagate’, ‘raise’, ‘omit’

Returns:

- The Kruskal-Wallis H statistic, corrected for ties.
- The p-value for the test using the assumption that H has a chi square distribution.

Figure 102 - Kruskal-Wallis H-test

> Alexander Govern test

Computes the Alexander Govern test. The Alexander-Govern approximation tests the equality of k independent means over the heterogeneity of variance. The test is applied to samples from two or more groups, possibly with differing sizes. Unlike one-way ANOVA, this test does not assume on homoscedasticity.

Input:

1. Arrays of sample measurements.
2. The “nan_policy” parameter, which defines how to handle when input contains nan, with the following three options: ‘propagate’, ‘raise’, ‘omit’

Returns:

1. The test statistic.
2. The associated p-value.

Figure 103 - Alexander Govern test

> Wilcoxon rank-sum statistic

Compute the Wilcoxon rank-sum statistic for two samples. The Wilcoxon rank-sum test tests the null hypothesis that two sets of measurements are drawn from the same distribution. The alternative hypothesis is that values in one sample are more likely to be larger than the values in the other sample.

Input:

1. Two arrays of sample from continuous distributions.
2. The “alternative” parameter, which defines the null and alternative hypotheses, with the following three options: ‘two-sided’, ‘less’, ‘greater’
3. The “nan_policy” parameter, which defines how to handle when input contains nan, with the following three options: ‘propagate’, ‘raise’, ‘omit’

Returns:

1. The test statistic under the large-sample approximation that the rank sum statistic is normally distributed.
2. The p-value of the test.

Figure 104 - Wilcoxon rank-sum test

> one-way chi-square test

Compute the one-way chi-square test. The chi-square test tests the null hypothesis that the categorical data has the given frequencies.

Input:

1. Two arrays (observed and expected) of frequencies in each category. If expected is missing it is assumed that the expected frequencies are uniform and given by the mean of the observed frequencies.

Returns:

1. The chi-squared test statistic.
2. The p-value of the test.

Figure 105 - One-way chi-square test

8.6.2.7 Multiple Testing and P-Value Correction

The correction methods aim to counteract the multiple comparisons problem.

Input:

1. 1-D Array of uncorrected p-values
2. The “alpha” parameter, which determines the family-wise error rate
3. The “method” parameter, with which one of the following methods is selected for the test:
 - > Bonferroni: one-step correction of p-values.
 - > Šidák: one-step correction of p-values.
 - > Holm: step-down method using Bonferroni adjustments.
 - > Holm-Sidak: step down method using Sidak adjustments
 - > Simes-Hochberg: step-up method (independent)
 - > Hommel: closed method based on Simes tests (non-negative)
 - > FDR Benjamini-Hochberg: Benjamini/Hochberg (non-negative)
 - > FDR Benjamini-Yekutieli: Benjamini/Yekutieli (negative)
 - > FDR 2-stage Benjamini-Hochberg: two stage fdr correction (non-negative)
 - > FDR 2-stage Benjamini-Krieger-Yekutieli: two stage fdr correction (non-negative)

› FDR adaptive Gavrilov-Benjamini-Sarkar:

Returns:

1. True if a hypothesis is rejected, False if not
2. The adjusted p-values for multiple hypothesis testing.
3. [Šidák] The corrected alpha for Sidak method
4. [Bonferroni] The corrected alpha for Bonferroni method

Figure 106 - One-way chi-square test

8.6.2.8 Classification analysis (LDA/SVM), Classification for cut-off determination

This method applies classification algorithms, including the Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA) and Support Vector Machines (SVMs), for addressing the hypotheses introduced in D4.2.

Input:

1. Features-independent variables
2. Output-Dependent Variable
3. Method: SVM with linear kernel or LDA

Returns:

1. Weights assigned to the feature
2. Constant term

8.6.2.9 Principal Component Analysis

Principal Component Analysis is a statistical technique for reducing the dimensionality of the dataset, in

order to increase the interpretability while preserving the maximum information.

Input:

1. Features
2. `n_components`: number of components to keep

Returns:

1. Percentage of variance explained by each of the selected components.
2. The singular values corresponding to each of the selected components.
3. Principal axes in feature space, representing the directions of maximum variance in the data. Equivalently, the right singular vectors of the centered input data, parallel to its eigenvectors.

8.6.2.10 K-means Clustering

K-means clustering constitutes an unsupervised technique, where similar data points are grouped together, i.e., into the same cluster. Then, the underlying patterns can be discovered.

Input:

1. Features
2. `n_clusters`: The number of clusters to form as well as the number of centroids to generate.

Returns:

1. Coordinates of cluster centers.
2. Labels of each point
3. `inertia`: Sum of squared distances of samples to their closest cluster center.

8.7 ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

The Artificial Intelligence module provides the capability to analyse, detect similarities and predict the next steps of the Expert System. Access to big data for model training and optimisation will be necessary for the creation of AI solutions that are both replicable and adaptable to clinical practice. However, it's important to know that algorithms are trained on several complex data, that is why the system just gives a recommendation to the scientists and not a sure solution.

The AI module, with the help of the workflow module it is embedded on, will mimic human intelligence to perform medical diagnosis using a set of known algorithms and tools. Based on the scientific protocol and methods, each diagnosis and treatment process will be redirected through the known path of actions, in order to use the possible AI algorithms to support clinicians in making an appropriate decision.

As the workflow system proceeds to the next step each time, there is an option to use AI techniques to analyse the input data based on previous experience.

The final result of the system using artificial intelligence, is to give a recommendation to the scientist in order to perform another workflow or processes or get an end result.

8.8 USER INTERFACE

8.8.1 TECHNOLOGIES, PACKAGES

The user interface is hosted by the main portal, The main portal is implemented using JSF technologies, and in particular «Primefaces 10» package.

8.8.2 PORTAL UI

The portal is the place where the whole visualisation of the system is hosted. There are specific pages for components used, and there are pages generally used by the system, like the dashboard, alerts, notifications, administration, login/logout.

The landing page is presented in the next figure:

Figure 107 - Landing page

The main dashboard, presented in the next figure, contains:

- › Portal menu
- › Main dashboard elements displaying a global image of the system
- › Alerts and notifications

Figure 108 - Main dashboard

The dataset page contains elements for visualization and editing of the datasets used by the system. It is presented in the next figure and the areas of the page refer to:

- › Menu
- › Data table with dataset content
- › Actions column (Download, delete)
- › Upload area

Figure 109 - Dataset page

The analysis page is the place where results of running analytics procedures will be displayed. The page has as main area, the placement of specific iFrames produced by Advanced Analytics tools. The areas of the page, displayed in the next figure, are:

- › Main menu
- › iFrames area

Figure 110 - Analysis page

Clinical processes page, manages the data used during the clinical processes, like clinical trials or diagnosis. The page displayed in the next figure has as main areas:

- › Menu
- › Wizard page
- › Specific submenus and commands

Figure 111 - Clinical processes page

9 INTEGRATION

The present chapter will show how the Expert System modules are integrated together to achieve a high-level sharing capability. The data that are inserted as a data input in all modules are transferred via application programming interface (API) in the MES-CoBraD platform. The integration is capable because of the general architecture of the modules, which is generic microservices and require more fragmented functionalities. That means that each service is a modular, unique process that can be deployed independently.

9.1 INTEGRATION BETWEEN COMPONENTS

The whole MES-CoBraD system is designed to use many components, developed in different technologies, with a very well-defined functional role. They are all placed on the same platform, using a distributed architecture, and all are cooperating to reach a common goal. For this reason, a deep integration mechanism is designed and implemented, and this integration is based on:

- › Integration at data level, by using the sane Data Lake
- › Integration at process level, by implementing a choreography mechanism based on message exchanges
- › Integration at UI level, by placing specific HMI in the same Portal.

In the next subchapters, we will describe in detail how the integration was designed.

9.1.1 INTEGRATION CHALLENGES

Before treating the integration process, we have identified several challenges specific for such a complex system.

- › There is a large number of **functionalities specific** to only one pilot use case (PUC). The following PUCs are considered:
 - PUC 1: MES-CoBraD Multidisciplinary Multisource Real-World Data Assessment Protocol
 - PUC 2: MES-CoBraD Advanced Analytics Deep-Phenotyping and Prognostication
 - PUC3: MES-CoBraD Real-World Therapy Repurposing and Approved Indication Reassessment
 - PUC4: Development and Validation of a multidisciplinary expert system for the assessment and management of complex brain disorders – MES-CoBraD”
- › There are strong system **security** requirements related to **pilot(s)**. Few data can be used by several pilots (or are relevant to several pilots)
- › There is a need for some **common data collection** and normalisation for all or for many pilots
- › There are **common rules** which all pilots should comply with, and which should be monitored at central level

- › There is a need for **governance** of all pilots, at the same time with a big autonomy of each one

9.1.2 INTEGRATION PRINCIPLES

As already presented in D7.1, the MES-CoBraD project develops an integrated system covering the complete value chain. The construction of this toolkit is as follows the steps:

- › Create an optimised framework
- › Place all the tools in the framework
- › Place Edge plug-ins on client systems

Open standards and protocols are used for all components placed in the system both in terms of development and ease of use.

As integration principles we have establish that:

- › Raw data is stored only on edge components. Anonymised data only is stored on the central platform
- › All data for the central platform is stored in a data Lake
- › Communication between components is done exclusively via REST API

9.1.3 INTEGRATION MECHANISMS

The usage of technologies and tools deployed as the standalone supporting environment is considering the following rationale:

- › The operating system chosen is Linux Ubuntu[141], since it is an open source and proven reliable operating system
- › The containers are managed by Docker[142]. We have chosen Docker as it is open source and a widely used container management system.
- › **Docker container** (or docker) is a lightweight, standalone, executable package of software that includes everything needed to run an application: code, runtime, system tools, system libraries, and settings)
- › **Docker Engine** is an open-source containerisation technology for building and containerising your applications. Docker Engine acts as a client-server application with:
 - A server with a long-running daemon process called **dockerd**[143].
 - APIs specify interfaces that programs can use to talk to and instruct the Docker daemon.
 - A command-line interface (CLI) client called Docker.

- › The CLI uses Docker APIs[144] to control or interact with the Docker daemon through scripting or direct CLI commands. Many other Docker applications use the underlying API and CLI. The daemon creates and manages Docker objects, such as images, containers, networks, and volumes.
- › The docker engine will run all the containers developed as part of the MES-CoBraD project.
- › User Authentication and Authorisation are based on Keycloak [145].
- › **Keycloak** is an open-source identity and access management solution which mainly aims at applications and services. Users can authenticate with Keycloak rather than individual applications. So, the applications don't have to deal with login forms, authenticating users, and storing users. Once logged in to Keycloak, users don't have to log in again to access different applications. The same thing applies to sign-out. Keycloak offers identity management as a sophisticated user management tool, without having to log on repeatedly with every login and into every system-as well as system security, social logins, support for mobile apps, and integration into other solutions. Keycloak has implementations to LDAP and Active Directory as well. Trying Keycloak is quick and easy.
- › The web Server and beans container used is Apache Tomee[xx]. It is used to run the Portal.
- › **Apache TomEE** [146] is the Java Enterprise Edition of **Apache** Tomcat that combines several Java enterprise projects including **Apache** OpenEJB [147], **Apache** OpenWebBeans [148], **Apache** OpenJPA [149], **Apache** MyFaces [150], and others. It is community-led development since 1999. It is the most used JEE web server.
- › The reverse proxy used is NGINX [151].
- › **NGINX** is open-source software for web serving, reverse proxying, caching, load balancing, media streaming, and more. In addition to its HTTP server capabilities, NGINX can also function as a proxy server for email (IMAP, POP3, and SMTP) and a reverse proxy and load balancer for HTTP, TCP, and UDP servers.

The Portal is a monolithic web JEE application, developed as part of the project and deployed on top of Apache Tomee. The security is offered by Keycloak.

- › **APIs.** All technology providers have included in the chapter below the extended documentation about the API functions that will be exposed in the dashboard
- › **Docker images.**

9.1.3.1 Continuous Integration/Continuous Deployment (CI/CD)

Considering the complexity of the system, and the necessity to have a running system in each phase of the development process, we are considering a CI/CD system based on:

- Source code placement on GIT
- Usage of Github Actions CI/CD tool

- Deployment on the platform of each new release, run automated tests, and create release notes.

9.2 INTEGRATION WITH THE MES-COBRA D PLATFORM

9.2.1 READ DATA FROM OTHER SYSTEMS

It is possible to have input from external systems. The input can be received as:

- › Offline files, which can be uploaded in the system. There is no restriction on the file formats, but the interpretation of data is specific for each component.
- › JSON messages, accepted by a Kafka Message Broker
- › REST API calls

10 TESTING

This section provides the testing methodologies of all the components inside WP6. Application testing is an activity that almost all software testers do regularly to check if the application modules operate as intended. In this section, we will focus on Functional tests and specifically on Unit Tests, which a software engineer creates, to check each component of the application for its proper operation. Testing methodologies, in more details will be analysed on deliverables “7.3 Overall system testing report – v1” and its final release “7.5 Overall system testing report – final”.

Specifically in the following tables, the test actions describe the unit tests, which need to be executed to ensure the functions operate correctly. Distinctions in their implementation will be expanded upon in the actual testing in the next iteration.

10.1 EXPERT SYSTEM - PROCESS MODELLING AND MANAGEMENT

The table below describes the methods used to validate that the Expert System module will be executed as always expected. These tests are created during the implementation phase and executed, to test the validity, during the implementation and the deployment of the module.

Table 12 - Testing methods for Expert System

Index	Title of test	Test Methods/Actions
1	Test workflow functionality	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Validate input fields 2. Validate if input requirements are matched 3. Validate that components retrieve the correct workflow 4. Validate if workflow can be self-deleted 5. Validate if soft-deleted workflow can be reverted to its normal state
2	Test workflow-run functionality	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Validate input fields 2. Validate if input requirements are matched 3. Validate that components retrieve the correct workflow-run
3	Test workflow engine functionality	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Validate that a workflow engine can be instantiated 2. Validate that a workflow engine can continue at a non-starting point 3. Validate that a workflow engine can provide the next step given the state that exists at that point

10.2 QUERY BUILDER

Table 13 Testing methods for Query Builder

Index	Title of test	Test Actions
1	Select Table	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> (Backend) Test the connection with DataLake (Backend) Validate the data input
2	Build Select SQL test	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> (Backend) Validate the structure and the format of the input (Backend) Validate the existence of the required fields (Backend) Validate the input complies with the SQL queries logic
3	Build Select with Group By SQL query test	
4	Build Join SQL test	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> (Backend) Validate the structure and format of the input
5	Execute the SQL query test	
6	Save the output of the execution in the Object Storage test	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> (Backend) Test the connection with the Object Storage
7	Select Object from the Object Storage test	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> (Backend) Validate the data input

10.3 DATA ANALYTICS

Table 14 Functional Testing Data Analytics

Index	Title of Test	Test Actions
1	Auto correlation function test	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> (Backend) Validate successful function initialisation data from workflow <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Validate successful download of files if necessary Validate successful creation of temporary run configuration files
2	Partial auto function correlation	
3	Welch function test	
4	Find peaks function test	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> (Frontend) Validate function initialisation data sent from backend
5	Periodogram function test	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> (Frontend) Validate information retrieved from backend used in UI creation
6	Short time Fourier transform function test	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> (Frontend) Validate user input for parametrisation given in forms.
7	Power spectral density function test	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> (Backend) Validate data parameters sent from frontend (Backend) Validate function run results before sending to frontend
8	Alpha delta ratio function test	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> (Frontend) Validate returned data output
9	Alpha variability test function test	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Visualisation tested in Data and Results Visualisation test 3 .
10	Asymmetry functions test	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> (Backend) Validate output data to be stored in datalake. (Backend) Validate workflow related data sent to Workflow

11	Actigraphy functions	manager.
11	Recon-all- test	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. (Backend) Validate successful function initialisation data from workflow <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Validate successful download of files if necessary b. Validate successful creation of temporary run configuration files 2. (Frontend) Validate function initialisation data sent from backend 3. (Frontend) Validate function initialised from user and log read and update. 4. (Backend) Validate received requests from frontend and its execution in Neurodesk environment 5. (Backend) Validate function run results before sending to frontend
12	Samseg test	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 6. (Frontend) Validate returned data output <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Visualisation tested in Data and Results Visualisation test 3 . 7. (Backend) Validate output data to be stored in datalake. 8. (Backend) Validate workflow related data sent to Workflow manager.

10.4 HYPOTHESIS TESTING INTERFACE

Table 15 Hypothesis Testing Interface Functional Testing

Index	Title of test	Test Methods/Actions
1	Normality tests functionality	1. (Backend) Validate successful function initialisation
2	Transformation (Normalilty) tests functionality	a. Validate successful download of requested datasets from the DataLake
3	Correlation tests functionality	b. Validate result objects to initialise form fields
4	Homoscedasticity tests functionality	2. (Frontend) Validate function initialisation data sent from backend
5	Transformation (Homoscedasticity) tests functionality	3. Validate input fields
6	T-Tests functionality	4. Validate if input requirements are matched
7	Rank tests functionality	5. (Backend) Validate request and its parameters, sent from the frontend, that match the requirements (type, size, etc.)
8	Anova test functionality	6. (Backend) Validate function's return paths
9	Chi-square test functionality	7. (Frontend) Validate response
10	Multiple comparisons tests functionality	8. (Frontend) Validate the creation of Visualisations based on response (charts, dashboards, etc.)
11	K-means clustering functionality	9. (Frontend) Validate output report object
12	Principal component analysis	10. (Backend) Validate if report object is received from the frontend and successfully stored in

Index	Title of test	Test Methods/Actions
	functionality	DataLake.
13	General statics functionality	11. (Backend) Validate the response back to workflow manager.

10.5 DATA AND RESULTS VISUALISATION

Table 16 Data and Results Visualisation Functional Testing

Index	Title of Test	Test Methods/actions
1	EEG View	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. (Backend) Validate successful function initialisation data from workflow <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Validate successful download of files if necessary b. Validate successful creation of temporary run configuration files 2. (Frontend) Validate function initialisation data sent from backend 3. (Frontend) Validate information retrieved from backend used in UI creation 4. (Frontend) Validate user input for parametirisation given in forms. 5. (Backend) Validate data parameters sent from frontend 6. (Backend) Validate creation of temporary notebook files 7. (Backend) Validate execution in Neurodesk environment 8. (Backend) Validate saving and retrieval of annotations 9. (Frontend) Validate returned data and visualisation output created in the iframe 10. (Backend) Validate output data to be stored in datalake if needed. 11. (Backend) Validate workflow related data sent to Workflow manager.
2	MRI View	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. (Backend) Validate successful function initialisation data from workflow <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Validate successful download of files if necessary b. Validate successful creation of temporary run configuration files 2. (Frontend) Validate function initialisation data sent from backend 3. (Backend) Validate execution in Neurodesk environment of the Freeview application 4. (Frontend) Validate returned visualisation output

		created in the iframe
		<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 5. (Backend) Validate output data to be stored in datalake if needed. 6. (Backend) Validate workflow related data sent to Workflow manager.
3	In page visualisations	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. (Frontend) Validate visualisation data. 2. (Frontend) Validate visualisaiton created correctly.
		<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. (Backend) Validate successful function initialisation data from workflow <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Validate successful download of files if necessary b. Validate successful creation of temporary run configuration files 2. (Frontend) Validate function initialisation data sent from backend 3. (Frontend) Validate information retrieved from backend used in UI creation and sent in backend. 4. (Frontend) Validate created visualisation data retrieved from backend and re creation in front end. 5. (Backend) Validate workflow related data sent to Workflow manager.
4	Dashboard	

10.6 ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

The table below describes the methods used to validate that the Artificial Intelligence module will be executed as always expected. These tests are created during the implementation phase and executed, to test the validity, during the implementation and the deployment of the module.

Table 17 - Testing methods for Artificial Intelligence

Index	Title of test	Test Methods/Actions
1	Test prediction functionality	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Validate input fields 2. Validate if input requirements are matched 3. Validate if prediction algorithm returns a list of tasks at any given state

11 CONCLUSIONS AND NEXT STEPS

The present deliverable provides the basic structure of the algorithm that includes all variables that have been identified and result in the creation of the basic structure that hosts the data analysis. The system can receive a variety of variables analysed through AI algorithm and provide the end users with the appropriate results.

The Landscape Analysis has been reported including Evidence-Based Medicine, Hypothesis Testing in Medicine, Process Modelling and Management, Data Analytics and Processing and Artificial Intelligence Landscape analysis provides an overview of the clinical decision-making process of evidence-based medicine with reference to the historical background, the methodological process, observation studies and advantages and limitations. Moreover, hypothesis testing is stated, indicating the significance and statistical analysis of the procedure. A state of the art of process modelling and management is reported with reference to healthcare systems, clinicians, and medical research. Data analytics and processing is provided including analysis of structured, inhomogeneous, and multimodal data, feature selection, diagnosis Classification and visualisation and statistical overview. Artificial Intelligence and its role and benefits in medical systems in analysed with reference to explainable and trustworthy AI.

The State-Of-The-Art Analysis has also been reported providing Expert System - Process Modelling and Management – Comparative Analysis, Data Analytics and Visualisations – Comparative Analysis, Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning – Comparative Analysis.

In this chapter a state of the art of expert systems is provided, identifying, analysing, and comparing their characteristics. Comparative analysis of process modelling management tools including data analytics and visualizations is also provided giving an overview of weaknesses and strengths. For each tool the features, compatibility, activity, open-Source information, analytics, and visualisations are summarised. A comparative analysis of Artificial Intelligence and machine learning is also provided.

Requirements' Elaboration: Expert System - Process Modelling and Management, Query Builder, Data Analytics, Hypothesis Testing Interface, Data and Results Visualisation, Artificial Intelligence, Integration.

The present section elaborates on the system requirements defining and coding the description. Integration aspects referring to Advanced Analytics components and the MES-CoBraD Platform are also reported.

The section of Advanced Analytics Architecture provides the overall architecture of the advanced analytics components and workflow management. Different features are presented as: UI Process Designer, Process Executor, Task Optimiser, Process Optimiser. The Query Builder serves as a connecting role in the MES-CoBraD ecosystem. Data Lake Interface specifications and Query Builder Modules providing also visualizations are reported.

Advanced Analytics Mockups: User Interface, Expert System - Process Modelling and Management, Query Builder, Data Analytics, Hypothesis Testing Interface, Data, and Results Visualisation. The section presents the analysis of the advanced analytics mockups providing the presentation of user interface, information on the expert system and process modelling and management, query builder and data analytics. Information on the hypothesis testing interface, visualizations and AI are also reported.

APIs' Specification has been analysed providing Query Builder and MES-CoBraD Data Lake, Expert System - Process Modelling and Management, Data Analytics, Data and Results Visualisation, Artificial Intelligence.

The section of Implementation provided the Overview, Expert System - Process Modelling and Management, Query Builder, Data Analytics, Hypothesis Testing Interface, Data and Results Visualisation, Artificial Intelligence, User Interface.

Integration: Integration between components, Integration with the MES-CoBraD Platform.

Testing: Expert System - Process Modelling and Management, Query Builder, Data Analytics, Hypothesis Testing Interface, Data and Results Visualisation, Artificial Intelligence, Integration Testing.

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ANNEX I : Data Analytics Tools Information Collection

Table 18 – Statistical Methods & Data Processing for Electrophysiology Data

#	Statistical Methods & Data Processing	Short Description	How and when do you use this method in your medical research?	Importance	Tools (you may know) that implement this method	Visualisations for this method (Line chart, Bar chart, Image, Radar Chart, Heat map, Hypnogram, Table etc.)	Comment
1	Spectral analysis (wavelet transform) - topoplots	The WT can be thought of as an extension of the classic Fourier transform, except that, instead of working on a single scale (time or frequency), it works on a multi-scale basis. This multi-scale feature of the WT allows the decomposition of a signal into a number of scales, each scale representing a particular coarseness of the signal under study.	absolutely. All packages have some level of FFT or something similar	Must have		power-frequency plot and power-frequency-time plot	
2	Time series forecasting	Forecasting whether an EEG trace in seconds indicates a patient is having a seizure or not. (ARIMA, etc.)	past use	Good to have	SPSS has a good one. FORTRAN is crap. Matlab used to be ok. Not sure of python quality of ARIMA	bar chart for residuals and line for time series	
3	Time series analysis	Time series analysis involves developing models that best capture or describe an observed time series in order to understand the underlying causes. This field of study seeks the "why" behind a time series dataset. This often involves making assumptions about the form of the data and decomposing the time series into constituent components. Examples: Autocorrelation	the AR part of ARIMA is that. I would combine it with the above.. Would add also things like a periodogram	Must have	I guess for these R or Python packages should be good. Not aware of specifics.	line chart mostly	
4	Actigraphy Data analysis	(i) detection of rest periods, (ii) advanced signal processing functions (Cosinor Analysis, Detrended Fluctuation Analysis, Locomotor Inactivity during sleep, Singular Spectrum Analysis), (iii) Calculation of typical wake/sleep cycle-related variables, including sleep regularity index, activity of rest fragmentation, and more.	in clinical practice and research for people with insomnia or circadian disorders	Must have	Philips tools for now. I believe I had forwarded an email in the past with a link to such a toolbox either to ENG, NTUA, or EVOL.	line chart and radar chart can work.	
5	Event detection in sleep	Sleep spindles, slow waves, rapid-eye movements	use it for fun through Compumedics software, but not as helpful in practice, since we score manually/visually. Helpful though for automated scoring tools.	Good to have	again, I had send a link to an EU Horizon project that focused exactly on that.	highlight the respective event	
6	Automatic sleep staging	Correctly identifying sleep stages is important in diagnosing and treating sleep disorders.	not using it, but would be useful to have an example as a use case	Good to have	enso	hypnogram	

#	Statistical Methods & Data Processing	Short Description	How and when do you use this method in your medical research?	Importance	Tools (you may know) that implement this method	Visualisations for this method (Line chart, Bar chart, Image, Radar Chart, Heat map, Hypnogram, Table etc.)	Comment
e	Signal processing	(i) filtering, i.e., bandpass, lowpass, highpass, etc.	always!!!	Must have	all packages usually have something. Would be nice to have one that gives you more options in the approach the use (first, second etc. order of tapering etc.)		
8	Repairing artifacts	Artifacts are parts of the recorded signal that arise from sources other than the source of interest (i.e., neuronal activity in the brain). As such, artifacts are a form of interference or noise relative to the signal of interest. There are 3 basic options when faced with artifacts in your recordings: (i) Ignore the artifact and carry on with analysis (ii) Exclude the corrupted portion of the data and analyze the remaining data (iii) Repair the artifact by suppressing artifactual part of the recording while (hopefully) leaving the signal of interest intact	cardiac artifact correction is useful. Notch filtering also important. Many use ICA approaches and event synchronous subtraction (for cardiac), i.e., option iii mostly in clinical practice. Option ii when looking at a steady state analysis of time series data for other automated analyses)	Good to have	many packages have something	detrended signal	
9	Correlations	(i) Pearson, (ii) Spearman, (iii) Point-Biserial, (iv) Kendall Tau	absolutely.	Must have		tables	
10	Average/Relative bandpower of an EEG signal using (i) Welch and (ii) multitaper spectral estimation methods	The average bandpower is also a very relevant metric for sleep research because it allows to differentiate between the different sleep stages. For instance, deep sleep is characterized by its predominance of slow-waves with a frequency range comprised between 0.5 to 4 Hz (i.e. delta band), which reflects a synchronized brain activity. Conversely, wakefulness is characterized by very little delta activity and much more higher-frequencies activity. Therefore, if you were to compute the delta bandpower for both deep sleep and wakefulness, the former would be very high and the latter very low.	I would consider this in relation to spectral analyses above.				

#	Statistical Methods & Data Processing	Short Description	How and when do you use this method in your medical research?	Importance	Tools (you may know) that implement this method	Visualisations for this method (Line chart, Bar chart, Image, Radar Chart, Heat map, Hypnogram, Table etc.)	Comment
11	Time frequency analysis	The time frequency analysis of EEG signals provide the correct visualization of EEG signals to extract the various rhythms of frequencies like alpha, beta, gamma waves. Examples: (i) spectrograms (STFT) (ii) Sleep is a continuous, dynamic neural process involving the complex interaction of many different networks within the brain. Long-standing clinical practice, however, breaks up sleep into discrete sleep stages through time-consuming, subjective, visual inspection of 30-second segments of electroencephalogram (EEG) data. As a result, vital information about brain activity is lost. Multitaper spectral analysis is therefore a powerful tool for finding new insights into the physiological mechanisms underlying sleep and for developing new ways of diagnosing and tracking sleep and diagnosing related disorders.	again, similar to spectral above				
12	Down-up sampling	As the name suggests, the process of converting the sampling rate of a digital signal from one rate to another is Sampling Rate Conversion. Increasing the rate of already sampled signal is Upsampling whereas decreasing the rate is called downsampling.	would not trust upsampling (if there is no data present, then you still get the original information with redundant (duplicate) information. Maybe only useful when trying to compare time series. Have not used it.				

Table 19 – Statistical Methods & Data Processing for MRI

#	Statistical Methods & Data Processing	Short Description	How and when do you use this method in your medical research?	Importance	Tools (you may know) that implement this method	Visualisations for this method (Line chart, Bar chart, Image, Radar Chart, Heat map, Hypnogram, Table etc.)	Comment
1	Method of least squares	The least-squares method is a statistical procedure to find the best fit for a set of data points by minimizing the sum of the offsets or residuals of points from the plotted curve.					

#	Statistical Methods & Data Processing	Short Description	How and when do you use this method in your medical research?	Importance	Tools (you may know) that implement this method	Visualisations for this method (Line chart, Bar chart, Image, Radar Chart, Heat map, Hypnogram, Table etc.)	Comment
2	6-parameter rigid-body spatial transformation (Realignment)	Within modality coregistration – usually this means realigning each of the images in a functional time series so that they're all in the same orientation	Very important to register within-individuals multimodal data	Must have	Several Neuroimaging package. Freesurfer, FSL, ANTS	Specific visualization toolbox. (freeview, fsleyes)	This should go BEYOND 6-degrees of freedom. Till 12 for linear
3	Undistortion	Deals with similar problem as unwarping – adjust images to correct for distortions caused by magnetic field inhomogeneities.	Very important for EPI-based MRI (such as DW-MRI).	Good to have	eddy function (from FSL package)		
4	Slice time correction	Adjust the values in the image to make it appear that all voxels have been acquired at the same time	Important for rsfMRI	Good to have	AFNI package		
5	Coregistration	Cross modality registration – realigning images collected using different acquisition sequences. Most commonly registering T1 weighted structural image to T2* weighted functional images.	Very similar to #2.	Must have	Several Neuroimaging package. Freesurfer, FSL, ANTS	Specific visualization toolbox. (freeview, fsleyes)	
6	Normalisation	Registration between different brains. Transforming one brain so its shape matches that of a different brain.	Very similar to #2 and #5. I would add non-linear registrations (local-deformations) that are useful for high-resolution MRI data	Must have	Several Neuroimaging package. Freesurfer, FSL, ANTS	Specific visualization toolbox. (freeview, fsleyes)	
7	Smoothing	Spatial averaging - replace the value at each voxel with a weighted average of the values in surrounding voxels	Last step of preprocessing prior to statistical analyses	Must have	fslmaths (from FSL package), or mri_smooth (Freesurfer)		
8	Clustering	Cluster analysis is a data-driven method that can assist in identifying voxels exhibiting similar patterns of task-related brain activity. Neuroimaging applications currently use several clustering algorithms, including the K-means approach, fuzzy clustering, hierarchical clustering methods, a hybrid hierarchical K-means DuBois Bowman approach, and dynamical cluster analysis (DCA). The performances of clustering methods are largely influenced by characteristics of the data. Many algorithms are capable of detecting well-separated clusters.	-				Same tools that described in General. At the end, MRI data is just a 3D matrix, which can be treated as "general data" and perform the clustering afterwards

#	Statistical Methods & Data Processing	Short Description	How and when do you use this method in your medical research?	Importance	Tools (you may know) that implement this method	Visualisations for this method (Line chart, Bar chart, Image, Radar Chart, Heat map, Hypnogram, Table etc.)	Comment
9	Independent Component Analysis	The basic goal of ICA is to express the observed 3D brain images as linear combinations of statistically independent latent component signals.	Important, specially for data-driven analyses, and for rsfMRI analyses	Good to have	FSL package and AFNI package (also ANTs)		
10	Diffusion-weighted magnetic resonance imaging (DW-MRI)	Diffusion-weighted magnetic resonance imaging (DWI or DW-MRI) is the use of specific MRI sequences as well as software that generates images from the resulting data that uses the diffusion of water molecules to generate contrast in MR images.	This is a data type, not a tool per-se. I would change the view and propose a pipeline with basic preprocessing steps to have an outcome from this image-type that might be useful				
11	Correlation	correlation or dependence is any statistical relationship, whether causal or not, between two random variables or bivariate data.	Commonly used. However, in neuroimaging, 99% of times we include nuisance factors (so a GLM is preferred)	Must have			
12	Regression - General Linear Model (GLM)	GLM can be thought of as an extension of a more familiar statistical technique: linear regression. Linear regression, sometimes called trend-line analysis, is a method used to calculate the "best fitting" line for a set of experimental data.	To assess relationships between neuroimaging measures and demographics, controlling by nuisance factors (e.g age or sex)	Must have	Most neuroimaging softwares (FSL, Freesurfer)		
13	Bayesian Hierarchical Modeling	Bayesian hierarchical modelling is a statistical model written in multiple levels (hierarchical form) that estimates the parameters of the posterior distribution using the Bayesian method.	Never used				
14	Spatial and temporal filter	Spatial filter is one method by convolving an image with a filter in spatial domain. This technique reduces the variance in the image but blurs sharp edges by an amount related to the shape of the function used in the convolution. This process is equivalent to reduce high spatial frequencies in the image.	The spatial filter is similar to smoothing. The temporal filter is not as commonly used	Not important			
15	Anisotropic Diffusion filter	In this approach the image u is only convolved in the direction orthogonal to	Never used				

#	Statistical Methods & Data Processing	Short Description	How and when do you use this method in your medical research?	Importance	Tools (you may know) that implement this method	Visualisations for this method (Line chart, Bar chart, Image, Radar Chart, Heat map, Hypnogram, Table etc.)	Comment
		the gradient of the image which ensures the preservation of edges.					
16	Nonlocal means filter	The NLM filter exploits the redundancy of information contained within the images to remove the noise. The restored intensity value of the voxel is calculated as the weighted average of all the voxel intensities within the image.	Might be useful to correct some distortion/noise and improve SNR	Good to have	DIPY (python packages), Mtrix package		
17	Wavelet transformation	Wavelets are mathematical functions that decompose data into different frequency components that can be studied with a resolution matched to their scale. Wavelet transforms are multiresolution representations of signals and images.	Never used	Not important			
18	Contourlet transform	The contourlets have the property of capturing contours and fine details in images. The Contourlet transform by Do and Vetterli is a geometrical image transform, which represents images containing contours and textures, and provides sparse representation at both spatial and directional resolutions. It offers a flexible multiresolution and directional decomposition for images, since it allows for a different number of directions at each scale.	Never used	Not important			
19	ROC	The receiver operator characteristic (ROC) method is used to compare the efficacy of various steps in calculating an activation map in the study of a single subject based on optimizing the ratio of the number of detected activations to the number of false-positive findings.	-	Must have	Several python and R packages		I don't think this is unique to neuroimaging. Its very important to have this tool, but for general use (any data, not just neuroimaging)
20	PCA	Principal components analysis (PCA) is a classical multivariate statistical tool, developed primarily by Hotelling (1933). The goal of PCA is to find linear combinations of the original variables	Might be useful for data-driven analyses. No super commonly used	Good to have			

#	Statistical Methods & Data Processing	Short Description	How and when do you use this method in your medical research?	Importance	Tools (you may know) that implement this method	Visualisations for this method (Line chart, Bar chart, Image, Radar Chart, Heat map, Hypnogram, Table etc.)	Comment
		that parsimoniously describe the dependence structure of the data.					
NEW	Non parametric statistical tests	Statistical tests that do not assume normality of the data to test an hypothesis.	When the data is not normal (specially, demographics, since the smoothing step is performed to guarantee normalization of the neuroimaging data) we need to use non-parametric tests	Must have	PALM, randomise (from FSL) package		

Table 20 – Statistical Methods & Data Processing for General Analysis

#	Statistical Methods & Data Processing	Short Description	How and when do you use this method in your medical research?	Importance	Tools (you may know) that implement this method	Visualisations for this method (Line chart, Bar chart, Image, Radar Chart, Heat map, Hypnogram, Table etc.)	Comment
1	Benchmarking	Benchmarking is a way of standardising – levelling the playing field – so that your data and results are meaningful in context. It involves taking outside factors into account so that you can adjust the parameters of your research and have a more precise understanding of what’s happening.	Almost never	Not important			
2	Regression Analysis	Regression is a statistical technique used for working out the relationship between two (or more) variables.	Most statistical analyses w/ continuous variables	Must have	Several R and python packages. Freesurfer and FSL for neuroimaging.	Scatterplot; beta-visualization	

#	Statistical Methods & Data Processing	Short Description	How and when do you use this method in your medical research?	Importance	Tools (you may know) that implement this method	Visualisations for this method (Line chart, Bar chart, Image, Radar Chart, Heat map, Hypnogram, Table etc.)	Comment
3	T-test	The T-test is a tool for comparing two data groups which have different mean values. For example, do women and men have different mean heights? The T-test allows the user to interpret whether differences are statistically significant or merely coincidental	Parametric data	Must have	Several R and python packages. Freesurfer and FSL for neuroimaging.	Violin/Box plots	
4	Analysis of variance (ANOVA) tests	Like the T-test, ANOVA (analysis of variance) is a way of testing the differences between groups to see if they're statistically significant. However, ANOVA allows you to compare three or more groups rather than just two.	Parametric data	Must have	Several R and python packages. Freesurfer and FSL for neuroimaging.	Violin/Box plots	
5	Cluster Analysis	Cluster analysis is a way of processing datasets by identifying how closely related the individual data points are. Using cluster analysis, you can identify whether there are defined groups (clusters) within a large pool of data, or if the data is quite evenly spread out.	Data-driven analyses to differentiate between groups without a-prioris	Good to have	antspy (neuroimaging), pytorch, several other packages	tSNE	
6	Factor Analysis	Factor analysis is a way to reduce the complexity of your research findings by trading a large number of initial variables for a smaller number of deeper, underlying ones. In performing factor analysis, you uncover "hidden" factors that explain variance (difference from the average) in your findings.	Never used	Good to have	-		

#	Statistical Methods & Data Processing	Short Description	How and when do you use this method in your medical research?	Importance	Tools (you may know) that implement this method	Visualisations for this method (Line chart, Bar chart, Image, Radar Chart, Heat map, Hypnogram, Table etc.)	Comment
7	z-test	A z-test is a statistical test to determine whether two population means are different when the variances are known and the sample size is large. A z-test is a hypothesis test in which the z-statistic follows a normal distribution.	Very similar to t-test? Specific case scenario?	Good to have		Violin/Box plots	
8	chi-square test	The Chi Square statistic is commonly used for testing relationships between categorical variables. The null hypothesis of the Chi-Square test is that no relationship exists on the categorical variables in the population; they are independent.	Prior to statistical analyses. Important to differentiate between groups. Mainly demographics data.	Must have	Several R packages		
9	MacNemar test	McNemar's test assesses the dependence of categorical data that are matched or paired.	Never heard of this one	Not important			
10							
11	Kruskal-Wallis rank sum test	Non-parametric version of ANOVA	Crucial when data do not follow a normal distribution	Must have	Several R and python packages. A very useful one is R package StatsExpressions	Violin/Box plots	
12	Permutation test	Use a bootstrap permutation of data to generate an actual/real null distribution to test if the hypothesis is true or rejected	Crucial when data do not follow a normal distribution	Must have			
13	Robust Correlation	Perform several iterations of a same correlation analyses with different subsamples of the initial sample	Correlation analyses might be driven/biased due to few outliers. With a robust correlation, one can have a more reliable measure on the	Must have	StatsExpressions in R		

#	Statical Methods & Data Processing	Short Description	How and when do you use this method in your medical research?	Importance	Tools (you know) may that implement this method	Visualisations for this method (Line chart, Bar chart, Image, Radar Chart, Heat map, Hypnogram, Table etc.)	Comment
			correlation between two continous variables				
14	Spearman's rank correlation coefficient	Association between two variables, that follow non-normal distribution, based on ranks	Crucial to study the association between two non-normal continous variables	Must have	Several packages in R and python		

ANNEX II : Metadata Manager OpenAPI v3

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```



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  }  
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```



```
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```
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```
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```



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    ],
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    {
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}
```



```
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    {
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```
    "stscategories_variables"  
  ],  
  "parameters": [  
    {  
      "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.stscategories_variables.category_id"  
    },  
    {  
      "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.stscategories_variables.variable_id"  
    },  
    {  
      "$ref": "#/parameters/preferReturn"  
    }  
  ],  
  "responses": {  
    "204": {  
      "description": "No Content"  
    }  
  }  
},  
"patch": {  
  "tags": [  
    "stscategories_variables"  
  ],  
  "parameters": [  
    {  
      "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.stscategories_variables.category_id"  
    },  
    {  
      "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.stscategories_variables.variable_id"  
    },  
    {  
      "$ref": "#/parameters/body.stscategories_variables"  
    },  
    {  
      "$ref": "#/parameters/preferReturn"  
    }  
  ],  
  "responses": {  
    "204": {  
      "description": "No Content"  
    }  
  }  
}  
},  
"/translations": {  
  "get": {  
    "tags": [  
      "translations"  
    ],  
  }  
}
```



```
"parameters": [  
  {  
    "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.translations.translation_id"  
  },  
  {  
    "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.translations.question"  
  },  
  {  
    "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.translations.question_id"  
  },  
  {  
    "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.translations.language_id"  
  },  
  {  
    "$ref": "#/parameters/select"  
  },  
  {  
    "$ref": "#/parameters/order"  
  },  
  {  
    "$ref": "#/parameters/range"  
  },  
  {  
    "$ref": "#/parameters/rangeUnit"  
  },  
  {  
    "$ref": "#/parameters/offset"  
  },  
  {  
    "$ref": "#/parameters/limit"  
  },  
  {  
    "$ref": "#/parameters/preferCount"  
  }  
],  
"responses": {  
  "200": {  
    "schema": {  
      "items": {  
        "$ref": "#/definitions/translations"  
      },  
      "type": "array"  
    },  
    "description": "OK"  
  },  
  "206": {  
    "description": "Partial Content"  
  }  
}
```



```
    },  
    "post": {  
      "tags": [  
        "translations"  
      ],  
      "parameters": [  
        {  
          "$ref": "#/parameters/body.translations"  
        },  
        {  
          "$ref": "#/parameters/select"  
        },  
        {  
          "$ref": "#/parameters/preferReturn"  
        }  
      ],  
      "responses": {  
        "201": {  
          "description": "Created"  
        }  
      }  
    },  
    "delete": {  
      "tags": [  
        "translations"  
      ],  
      "parameters": [  
        {  
          "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.translations.translation_id"  
        },  
        {  
          "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.translations.question"  
        },  
        {  
          "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.translations.question_id"  
        },  
        {  
          "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.translations.language_id"  
        },  
        {  
          "$ref": "#/parameters/preferReturn"  
        }  
      ],  
      "responses": {  
        "204": {  
          "description": "No Content"  
        }  
      }  
    }  
  },  
}
```



```
"patch": {
  "tags": [
    "translations"
  ],
  "parameters": [
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.translations.translation_id"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.translations.question"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.translations.question_id"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.translations.language_id"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/body.translations"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/preferReturn"
    }
  ],
  "responses": {
    "204": {
      "description": "No Content"
    }
  }
},
"/variables": {
  "get": {
    "tags": [
      "variables"
    ],
    "parameters": [
      {
        "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.variables.variable_id"
      },
      {
        "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.variables.name"
      },
      {
        "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.variables.creation_date"
      },
      {
        "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.variables.measure_level"
      }
    ],
```



```
{
  "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.variables.data_type"
},
{
  "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.variables.measure_unit"
},
{
  "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.variables.direct"
},
{
  "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.variables.formula"
},
{
  "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.variables.answer_number"
},
{
  "$ref": "#/parameters/select"
},
{
  "$ref": "#/parameters/order"
},
{
  "$ref": "#/parameters/range"
},
{
  "$ref": "#/parameters/rangeUnit"
},
{
  "$ref": "#/parameters/offset"
},
{
  "$ref": "#/parameters/limit"
},
{
  "$ref": "#/parameters/preferCount"
}
],
"responses": {
  "200": {
    "schema": {
      "items": {
        "$ref": "#/definitions/variables"
      },
      "type": "array"
    },
    "description": "OK"
  },
  "206": {
    "description": "Partial Content"
  }
}
```



```
    }
  }
},
"post": {
  "tags": [
    "variables"
  ],
  "parameters": [
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/body.variables"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/select"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/preferReturn"
    }
  ],
  "responses": {
    "201": {
      "description": "Created"
    }
  }
},
"delete": {
  "tags": [
    "variables"
  ],
  "parameters": [
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.variables.variable_id"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.variables.name"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.variables.creation_date"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.variables.measure_level"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.variables.data_type"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.variables.measure_unit"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.variables.direct"
    }
  ]
}
```



```
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.variables.formula"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.variables.answer_number"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/preferReturn"
    }
  ],
  "responses": {
    "204": {
      "description": "No Content"
    }
  }
},
"patch": {
  "tags": [
    "variables"
  ],
  "parameters": [
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.variables.variable_id"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.variables.name"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.variables.creation_date"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.variables.measure_level"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.variables.data_type"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.variables.measure_unit"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.variables.direct"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.variables.formula"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.variables.answer_number"
    }
  ],

```



```
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/body.variables"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/preferReturn"
    }
  ],
  "responses": {
    "204": {
      "description": "No Content"
    }
  }
}
},
"definitions": {
  "concepts": {
    "required": [
      "concept_id",
      "name"
    ],
    "properties": {
      "concept_id": {
        "maxLength": 8,
        "format": "character",
        "type": "string",
        "description": "Note:\nThis is a Primary Key.<pk/>"
      },
      "name": {
        "format": "text",
        "type": "string"
      },
      "parent_id": {
        "maxLength": 8,
        "format": "character",
        "type": "string"
      },
      "type": {
        "maxLength": 8,
        "format": "character",
        "type": "string"
      }
    }
  },
  "type": "object"
},
"concepts_variables": {
  "required": [
    "concept_id",
    "variable_id"
  ]
}
```



```
    ],
    "properties": {
      "concept_id": {
        "maxLength": 8,
        "format": "character",
        "type": "string",
        "description": "Note:\nThis is a Primary Key.<pk/>\nThis is a Foreign Key to `concepts.concept_id`.<fk table='concepts' column='concept_id'/>"
      },
      "variable_id": {
        "maxLength": 8,
        "format": "character",
        "type": "string",
        "description": "Note:\nThis is a Primary Key.<pk/>\nThis is a Foreign Key to `variables.variable_id`.<fk table='variables' column='variable_id'/>"
      }
    },
    "type": "object"
  },
  "languages": {
    "required": [
      "language_id"
    ],
    "properties": {
      "language_id": {
        "maxLength": 2,
        "format": "character",
        "type": "string",
        "description": "Note:\nThis is a Primary Key.<pk/>"
      },
      "name": {
        "format": "text",
        "type": "string"
      }
    }
  },
  "type": "object"
},
"questionnaires": {
  "required": [
    "questionnaire_id",
    "creation_date",
    "respondent"
  ],
  "properties": {
    "questionnaire_id": {
      "maxLength": 8,
      "format": "character",
      "type": "string",
      "description": "Note:\nThis is a Primary Key.<pk/>"
    }
  }
}
```



```
    },
    "creation_date": {
      "format": "date",
      "type": "string"
    },
    "respondent": {
      "format": "text",
      "type": "string"
    },
    "language_id": {
      "maxLength": 2,
      "format": "character",
      "type": "string",
      "description": "Note:\nThis is a Foreign Key to `languages.language_id`.<fk
table='languages' column='language_id'/>"
    },
    "type": "object"
  },
  "questions": {
    "required": [
      "question_id",
      "question_en"
    ],
    "properties": {
      "question_id": {
        "maxLength": 8,
        "format": "character",
        "type": "string",
        "description": "Note:\nThis is a Primary Key.<pk/>"
      },
      "question_en": {
        "format": "text",
        "type": "string"
      },
      "questionnaire_id": {
        "maxLength": 8,
        "format": "character",
        "type": "string",
        "description": "Note:\nThis is a Foreign Key to
`questionnaires.questionnaire_id`.<fk
column='questionnaire_id'/>"
      }
    },
    "type": "object"
  },
  "questions_variables": {
    "required": [
      "question_id",
```



```
    "variable_id"
  ],
  "properties": {
    "question_id": {
      "maxLength": 8,
      "format": "character",
      "type": "string",
      "description": "Note:\nThis is a Primary Key.<pk/>\nThis is a Foreign Key to
`questions.question_id`.<fk table='questions' column='question_id'/>"
    },
    "variable_id": {
      "maxLength": 8,
      "format": "character",
      "type": "string",
      "description": "Note:\nThis is a Primary Key.<pk/>\nThis is a Foreign Key to
`variables.variable_id`.<fk table='variables' column='variable_id'/>"
    }
  },
  "type": "object"
},
"stscategories": {
  "required": [
    "category_id",
    "name"
  ],
  "properties": {
    "category_id": {
      "maxLength": 8,
      "format": "character",
      "type": "string",
      "description": "Note:\nThis is a Primary Key.<pk/>"
    },
    "name": {
      "format": "text",
      "type": "string"
    },
    "parent_id": {
      "maxLength": 8,
      "format": "character",
      "type": "string"
    }
  },
  "type": "object"
},
"stscategories_variables": {
  "required": [
    "category_id",
    "variable_id"
  ],
  "type": "object"
},

```



```
"properties": {
  "category_id": {
    "maxLength": 8,
    "format": "character",
    "type": "string",
    "description": "Note:\nThis is a Primary Key.<pk/>\nThis is a Foreign Key to
`stscategories.category_id`.<fk table='stscategories' column='category_id'/>"
  },
  "variable_id": {
    "maxLength": 8,
    "format": "character",
    "type": "string",
    "description": "Note:\nThis is a Primary Key.<pk/>\nThis is a Foreign Key to
`variables.variable_id`.<fk table='variables' column='variable_id'/>"
  }
},
"type": "object"
},
"translations": {
  "required": [
    "translation_id"
  ],
  "properties": {
    "translation_id": {
      "maxLength": 8,
      "format": "character",
      "type": "string",
      "description": "Note:\nThis is a Primary Key.<pk/>"
    },
    "question": {
      "format": "text",
      "type": "string"
    },
    "question_id": {
      "maxLength": 8,
      "format": "character",
      "type": "string",
      "description": "Note:\nThis is a Foreign Key to `questions.question_id`.<fk
table='questions' column='question_id'/>"
    },
    "language_id": {
      "maxLength": 8,
      "format": "character",
      "type": "string",
      "description": "Note:\nThis is a Foreign Key to `languages.language_id`.<fk
table='languages' column='language_id'/>"
    }
  },
  "type": "object"
}
```



```
},
"variables": {
  "required": [
    "variable_id",
    "name",
    "creation_date"
  ],
  "properties": {
    "variable_id": {
      "maxLength": 8,
      "format": "character",
      "type": "string",
      "description": "Note:\nThis is a Primary Key.<pk/>"
    },
    "name": {
      "format": "text",
      "type": "string"
    },
    "creation_date": {
      "format": "date",
      "type": "string"
    },
    "measure_level": {
      "format": "text",
      "type": "string"
    },
    "data_type": {
      "format": "text",
      "type": "string"
    },
    "measure_unit": {
      "format": "text",
      "type": "string"
    },
    "direct": {
      "format": "boolean",
      "type": "boolean"
    },
    "formula": {
      "format": "text",
      "type": "string"
    },
    "answer_number": {
      "format": "integer",
      "type": "integer"
    }
  }
},
"type": "object"
}
```



```
},  
"parameters": {  
  "preferParams": {  
    "name": "Prefer",  
    "description": "Preference",  
    "required": false,  
    "in": "header",  
    "type": "string",  
    "enum": [  
      "params=single-object"  
    ]  
  },  
  "preferReturn": {  
    "name": "Prefer",  
    "description": "Preference",  
    "required": false,  
    "in": "header",  
    "type": "string",  
    "enum": [  
      "return=representation",  
      "return=minimal",  
      "return=none"  
    ]  
  },  
  "preferCount": {  
    "name": "Prefer",  
    "description": "Preference",  
    "required": false,  
    "in": "header",  
    "type": "string",  
    "enum": [  
      "count=none"  
    ]  
  },  
  "select": {  
    "name": "select",  
    "description": "Filtering Columns",  
    "required": false,  
    "in": "query",  
    "type": "string"  
  },  
  "on_conflict": {  
    "name": "on_conflict",  
    "description": "On Conflict",  
    "required": false,  
    "in": "query",  
    "type": "string"  
  },  
  "order": {
```



```
    "name": "order",
    "description": "Ordering",
    "required": false,
    "in": "query",
    "type": "string"
  },
  "range": {
    "name": "Range",
    "description": "Limiting and Pagination",
    "required": false,
    "in": "header",
    "type": "string"
  },
  "rangeUnit": {
    "name": "Range-Unit",
    "description": "Limiting and Pagination",
    "required": false,
    "default": "items",
    "in": "header",
    "type": "string"
  },
  "offset": {
    "name": "offset",
    "description": "Limiting and Pagination",
    "required": false,
    "in": "query",
    "type": "string"
  },
  "limit": {
    "name": "limit",
    "description": "Limiting and Pagination",
    "required": false,
    "in": "query",
    "type": "string"
  },
  "body.concepts": {
    "name": "concepts",
    "description": "concepts",
    "required": false,
    "schema": {
      "$ref": "#/definitions/concepts"
    },
    "in": "body"
  },
  "rowFilter.concepts.concept_id": {
    "name": "concept_id",
    "required": false,
    "format": "character",
    "in": "query",
```



```
    "type": "string"
  },
  "rowFilter.concepts.name": {
    "name": "name",
    "required": false,
    "format": "text",
    "in": "query",
    "type": "string"
  },
  "rowFilter.concepts.parent_id": {
    "name": "parent_id",
    "required": false,
    "format": "character",
    "in": "query",
    "type": "string"
  },
  "rowFilter.concepts.type": {
    "name": "type",
    "required": false,
    "format": "character",
    "in": "query",
    "type": "string"
  },
  "body.concepts_variables": {
    "name": "concepts_variables",
    "description": "concepts_variables",
    "required": false,
    "schema": {
      "$ref": "#/definitions/concepts_variables"
    },
    "in": "body"
  },
  "rowFilter.concepts_variables.concept_id": {
    "name": "concept_id",
    "required": false,
    "format": "character",
    "in": "query",
    "type": "string"
  },
  "rowFilter.concepts_variables.variable_id": {
    "name": "variable_id",
    "required": false,
    "format": "character",
    "in": "query",
    "type": "string"
  },
  "body.languages": {
    "name": "languages",
    "description": "languages",
```



```
    "required": false,
    "schema": {
      "$ref": "#/definitions/languages"
    },
    "in": "body"
  },
  "rowFilter.languages.language_id": {
    "name": "language_id",
    "required": false,
    "format": "character",
    "in": "query",
    "type": "string"
  },
  "rowFilter.languages.name": {
    "name": "name",
    "required": false,
    "format": "text",
    "in": "query",
    "type": "string"
  },
  "body.questionnaires": {
    "name": "questionnaires",
    "description": "questionnaires",
    "required": false,
    "schema": {
      "$ref": "#/definitions/questionnaires"
    },
    "in": "body"
  },
  "rowFilter.questionnaires.questionnaire_id": {
    "name": "questionnaire_id",
    "required": false,
    "format": "character",
    "in": "query",
    "type": "string"
  },
  "rowFilter.questionnaires.creation_date": {
    "name": "creation_date",
    "required": false,
    "format": "date",
    "in": "query",
    "type": "string"
  },
  "rowFilter.questionnaires.respondent": {
    "name": "respondent",
    "required": false,
    "format": "text",
    "in": "query",
    "type": "string"
  }
```



```
},
"rowFilter.questionnaires.language_id": {
  "name": "language_id",
  "required": false,
  "format": "character",
  "in": "query",
  "type": "string"
},
"body.questions": {
  "name": "questions",
  "description": "questions",
  "required": false,
  "schema": {
    "$ref": "#/definitions/questions"
  },
  "in": "body"
},
"rowFilter.questions.question_id": {
  "name": "question_id",
  "required": false,
  "format": "character",
  "in": "query",
  "type": "string"
},
"rowFilter.questions.question_en": {
  "name": "question_en",
  "required": false,
  "format": "text",
  "in": "query",
  "type": "string"
},
"rowFilter.questions.questionnaire_id": {
  "name": "questionnaire_id",
  "required": false,
  "format": "character",
  "in": "query",
  "type": "string"
},
"body.questions_variables": {
  "name": "questions_variables",
  "description": "questions_variables",
  "required": false,
  "schema": {
    "$ref": "#/definitions/questions_variables"
  },
  "in": "body"
},
"rowFilter.questions_variables.question_id": {
  "name": "question_id",
```



```
    "required": false,
    "format": "character",
    "in": "query",
    "type": "string"
  },
  "rowFilter.questions_variables.variable_id": {
    "name": "variable_id",
    "required": false,
    "format": "character",
    "in": "query",
    "type": "string"
  },
  "body.stscategories": {
    "name": "stscategories",
    "description": "stscategories",
    "required": false,
    "schema": {
      "$ref": "#/definitions/stscategories"
    },
    "in": "body"
  },
  "rowFilter.stscategories.category_id": {
    "name": "category_id",
    "required": false,
    "format": "character",
    "in": "query",
    "type": "string"
  },
  "rowFilter.stscategories.name": {
    "name": "name",
    "required": false,
    "format": "text",
    "in": "query",
    "type": "string"
  },
  "rowFilter.stscategories.parent_id": {
    "name": "parent_id",
    "required": false,
    "format": "character",
    "in": "query",
    "type": "string"
  },
  "body.stscategories_variables": {
    "name": "stscategories_variables",
    "description": "stscategories_variables",
    "required": false,
    "schema": {
      "$ref": "#/definitions/stscategories_variables"
    }
  },
}
```



```
    "in": "body"
  },
  "rowFilter.stscategories_variables.category_id": {
    "name": "category_id",
    "required": false,
    "format": "character",
    "in": "query",
    "type": "string"
  },
  "rowFilter.stscategories_variables.variable_id": {
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    "required": false,
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    "in": "query",
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  },
  "body.translations": {
    "name": "translations",
    "description": "translations",
    "required": false,
    "schema": {
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    }
  },
  "in": "body"
},
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  "required": false,
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  "in": "query",
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"rowFilter.translations.question": {
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  "required": false,
  "format": "text",
  "in": "query",
  "type": "string"
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"rowFilter.translations.question_id": {
  "name": "question_id",
  "required": false,
  "format": "character",
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  "type": "string"
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"rowFilter.translations.language_id": {
  "name": "language_id",
  "required": false,
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    "format": "character",
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  "body.variables": {
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    "description": "variables",
    "required": false,
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    },
    "in": "body"
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  "rowFilter.variables.variable_id": {
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  "rowFilter.variables.name": {
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    "required": false,
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    "in": "query",
    "type": "string"
  },
  "rowFilter.variables.creation_date": {
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    "required": false,
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    "in": "query",
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  "rowFilter.variables.measure_level": {
    "name": "measure_level",
    "required": false,
    "format": "text",
    "in": "query",
    "type": "string"
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  "rowFilter.variables.data_type": {
    "name": "data_type",
    "required": false,
    "format": "text",
    "in": "query",
    "type": "string"
  },
  "rowFilter.variables.measure_unit": {
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    "required": false,
    "format": "text",
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    "type": "string"
  },
  "rowFilter.variables.direct": {
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    "required": false,
    "format": "boolean",
    "in": "query",
    "type": "string"
  },
  "rowFilter.variables.formula": {
    "name": "formula",
    "required": false,
    "format": "text",
    "in": "query",
    "type": "string"
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  "rowFilter.variables.answer_number": {
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    "required": false,
    "format": "integer",
    "in": "query",
    "type": "string"
  }
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"externalDocs": {
  "url": "https://postgrest.org/en/v9.0/api.html",
  "description": "PostgREST Documentation"
}
}
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